

D4.2

PoDIUM LLs integration and pre-evaluation testing report

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building
trust and sustainability for CCAM

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AIC	Artificial Intelligence Camera
AD	Automated Driving
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
ASN.1	Abstract Syntax Notation One
C-ACC	Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CAN	Controller Area Network
CAV	Connected & Automated Vehicle
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport System
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CV	Connected Vehicle
C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything
DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
DT	Digital Twin
ECU	Electronic Control Unit
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
EV	Emergency Vehicle
gNB	gNodeB
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HMI	Human Machine Interface
IVIM	Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LDM	Local Dynamic Map
LoS	Line of sight

MAPEM	Map Extended Message
MCM	Manoeuvre Coordination Message
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
NSA	Non-Standalone
OBU	On-Board Unit
OD	Origin-Destination
PCAP	Packet Capture
PC5	5G reference point for direct communication between user equipments
PDI	Physical-Digital Infrastructure
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
QoS	Quality of Service
RLA	Risk Level Assessment
RSU	Roadside Unit
SA	Standalone
SEN	Service Edge Node
SPATEM	Signal Phase and Timing Extended Message
SPU	Sensor Processing Unit
SQL	Structured Query Language
TCC	Traffic Control Centre
TJA	Traffic Jam Alert
TMC	Traffic Management Centre
TMS	Traffic Management System
V2V	Vehicle to vehicle
V2I	Vehicle to infrastructure
VA	Video Analytics
VM	Virtual Machine
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VRU	Vulnerable Road User

Executive Summary

Deliverable D4.2 details the progress in integrating and pre-evaluating PoDIUM use cases at three European Living Labs—Germany, Spain, and Italy. Each Lab has tested specific Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) scenarios.

The **German Living Lab** focused on one Use case 1 (**UC1**). It has integrated two Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) and a connected vulnerable road user (VRU). The first CAV is a VW Golf Variant provided by Bosch and the second is a Mercedes E-Class provided by UULM. The connected VRU is provided by Nokia. Tests focused on cooperative corridor management and communication over multiple channels. The vehicles and the VRU successfully sent position and environmental data to a Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) server and reacted to cooperative manoeuvres. Additionally, the Bosch vehicle was also supported through offloaded functionality for perception and planning on the MEC.

The **Spanish Living Lab** comprised two distinct use cases (UC2 and UC3). In both UCs, MILLA's Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) was not available due to pending permits, with CAV trials planned from September onwards, conditional on obtaining these permits. Therefore, trials took place with the rest of the connected vehicles.

- **UC2** (urban roads in Barcelona): An Emergency Vehicle (EV) and a CV were successfully integrated. The platform gave priority to the EV by synchronising the traffic lights along the predefined corridor to facilitate uninterrupted flow. The Artificial Intelligence Cameras (AIC) detected VRUs and communicated their presence to the connected roadside equipment, which evaluated potential collision risks. Communication between vehicles and infrastructure was enabled through the exchange of Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs) and Decentralized Environmental Notification Message (DENMs), which were managed by MEC-hosted services.
- **UC3** (C32 highway near Barcelona): Two Connected Vehicles (CVs) equipped with Cohda MK6 OBUs, laptops, HMIs, and 5G modems were tested. Scenarios validated included real-time incident detection and warnings, and traffic strategies diffusion via CAM, MCM, IVIM and DENM messages. Available VRU applications included the PoDIUM Safety App and the On-Demand Shuttle Service App for smartphones.

The **Italian Living Lab** tested two use cases:

- **UC4** (Turin urban site): Implemented to enhance intersection safety, especially protecting VRUs using infrastructure sensors and CAV data integration and fusion. Pre-demo testing activities demonstrated effective integration of Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications, although RSU short-range communication (PC5) was pending completion. Extensive tests have been conducted in order to reach a final achievement of the scenarios prior to the non-functional tests phase in which optimization and performance is addressed.
- **UC5** (Autostrada del Brennero highway): Demonstrated infrastructure-assisted CCAM within highway tunnels. Key integration included C-ITS infrastructure, Roadside Units (RSUs), and vehicle prototypes. Validation covered scenarios such as Road Works Warnings (RWW) and Traffic Jam Alerts (TJA). Some integrations, notably roadside camera installations, remained pending and at the moment one of the two roadside units could not be installed, yet.

The deliverable outlines these achievements and highlights the remaining technical and operational steps required to complete full validation and LL demonstration of the PoDIUM platform under real-world conditions.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project intro

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UCs) of connected and cooperative automated mobility in real traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs (LLs) in Germany, Italy, and Spain, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for the availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital parts of the Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) platform. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions will be pursued:

1. A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability, and redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system.
2. Advanced data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards Digital Twins (DTs).
3. New Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) messages for enabling the specific advanced CCAM use cases.
4. Ensure software integrity, trust, and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange, and their processing.
5. Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with the integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The aim of PoDIUM is to enhance CCAM services in Europe. To reach this goal, the project focuses on the development and integration of the PDI needed to ensure the vehicle's connectivity via certain network technologies. A total of five PoDIUM UCs will be tested and validated under real-life conditions in the three LLs, located in Germany, Spain, and Italy. These UCs require advancing several technologies and elements that will be integrated under the common PoDIUM architecture. In previous deliverables, the development of the technologies (WP3) and the establishment of the data logging methods (WP4) was explained.

The objective of Deliverable D4.2 is to provide an overview of the integration activities and the pre-testing verifications in each LL. D4.2 is the joint outcome of Task 4.2, Task 4.3 and Task 4.4 each describing the German, Italian and Spanish LL respectively. In each of these tasks, the LL partners have integrated the proposed PDI innovations developed in WP3 in each LL. This includes the deployment of new and/or adaptation and validation of existing equipment of the LLs, WP3 developments' integration in each LL based on the needs of the corresponding UCs, and finally the testing of the data logging sequences defined in T4.1.

1.3. Intended audience

This deliverable is classified as "Public", therefore, it will be uploaded on the PoDIUM website, where it will be available for all project partners and any interested readers, as stakeholders and experts

involved in the development of CCAM systems. Nevertheless, the consortium members are the main intended audience of this document.

1.4. Structure of the deliverable and its relationship with other work packages/deliverables

Deliverable 4.2 is structured as follows:

1. Section 2: German LL
2. Section 3: Spanish LL
3. Section 4: Italian LL

Each section will describe, for each LL:

- **Living Lab description:** existing infrastructure, vehicles and test facilities.
- **Integration of PoDIUM PDI Innovations:** Description of how the proposed PDI innovations developed in WP3 have been integrated into each LL, based on the specific needs of the corresponding Use Cases (UCs).
- **Preparation for pre-testing evaluation:**
 - Checklist of UC requirements for the preparation of each LL to become “demonstration ready”.
 - Description of pre-testing verification methodologies, plans and tools.
 - Data logging setup and data storage for each UC, as planned in D4.1 [2].
- **Pre-testing Activity Report:** Summary of pre-testing activities for the integrated PDI technologies, broken down per scenario and UC.
- **Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) a testing:** For relevant UCs, testing of CAVs up to SAE Level 4, implementing automated manoeuvres enabled (or not) by PDI data. Vehicle motion control strategies are tested in real traffic, with or without actuator engagement, while logging data in real time to assess KPI compliance.

This deliverable concludes the work carried out in WP4, which focused on the integration and roll-out of the PDI technologies developed in WP3 across the three PoDIUM Living Labs in Germany, Italy, and Spain. The integration involved contributions from various stakeholders, including OEMs, MNOs, vendors, and integrators, ensuring interoperability and functionality within a comprehensive end-to-end testing environment.

The work succeeding this deliverable - the demonstrations and final assessment – is performed in WP5 and is reported in deliverable D5.2.

2. German Living Lab

Use Case 1 (UC1) explores the benefits of a cooperative local environment model and a cooperative planner for managing complex urban traffic situations with the goal to support the ambitious EU safety and environmental targets by improving road safety and efficiency. The focus is on corridor management in situations where not all lanes of a road are available, e.g. when one is blocked by a parked vehicle. Various situations are considered in which an obstacle on one lane needs to be bypassed by traffic approaching simultaneously from both directions, e.g., with two vehicles that rely only on their onboard sensors or a vehicle and a cyclist for which infrastructure sensors are available. To improve availability and redundancy, UC1 also includes multiple communication channels (5G mobile network with cm- and mm-wave and 60GHz Wi-Fi) that are realized and assessed.

2.1. Use Case 1

In this chapter we describe the UC1 activities of the German LL.

As a brief reminder, UC1 addresses the following scenarios:

- **Scenario 1:** In the first scenario, an obstacle (e.g. a parked truck) blocks one lane. Two CAVs approaching from opposite directions perform a cooperative manoeuvre to bypass the obstacle. This scenario is investigated under two conditions a) using only dynamic traffic information available from the CAVs (lightweight solution) and b) with additional support from the infrastructure sensors (baseline solution).
- **Scenario 2:** In this scenario, a connected VRU without cooperation capabilities and a CAV bypass the obstacle. This scenario is implemented only with support from infrastructure-based sensor.

In the following chapters, we will describe:

- a) the LL testbed, including the deployment of new and/or adaptation of existing equipment of the LL and the preparation of the test vehicles and other testing facilities
- b) the integration of the WP3 PDI innovations into the LL testbed, and their validation
- c) the testing methodologies, data loggers, and test plan
- d) the pre-demo testing activities relevant to this UC, aligned with the checklist of Functional and Non-Functional requirements as described in D2.2 [1]

A checklist for the LL preparation and integration validation is also provided in the Annex.

2.1.1. LL description

The German LL is deployed in Ulm-Lehr at three wings of the T-junction equipped with infrastructure sensing, data processing, and communication gear.

Figure 1: Depiction of the infrastructure sensors available in UC1

Infrastructure sensors (cameras and RADARs) are mounted at the streetlight poles, and Sensor Processing Units (SPUs) process the sensor data and deliver object detections from each pole. The infrastructure sensors on a pole are hard-wired to the corresponding SPU. Figure 1 shows the status of the test site at the beginning of the PoDIUM project.

In PoDIUM, the SPUs are connected to a MEC server via a prototype 5G mobile network and feature at least one additional redundant communication channel to the RSU at the LL. The RSU is connected, via the prototype 5G mobile network and fibre, to the MEC server and provides connectivity to road users via 60GHz-Wi-Fi as well as to the infrastructure sensor SPUs via 60GHz-Wi-Fi. The 60GHz-Wi-Fi at the SPUs and fibre connections were installed during the PoDIUM project. In addition to 5G macro cells, 5G mm-Wave micro cells were made available at the Ulm LL for the duration of PoDIUM.

Deliverable 4.1 “Deployment of PoDIUM architecture to the LLS and development of data collection tools” presents the PoDIUM architecture deployment plan for UC1. Especially, section 2.1.3 of D4.1 [2] outlines when components and services were added for PoDIUM and became available. For instance, the above mentioned MEC server was successfully integrated in May 2024, 60GHz-Wi-Fi was installed in September 2024, and CAVs were ready in October 2024.

2.1.1.1. Description of the LL infrastructure (existing and newly installed)

- Existing:
 - **SPU:** The SPUs detect both regular vehicles as well as VRUs in the environment. The detections are then sent to the MEC server. The communication to the MEC is realized via 5G cm-Wave (FR1). During PoDIUM, an additional communication to the MEC over 60-GHz-Wi-Fi with the RSU acting as a gateway has been realized.
 - **5G cm-Wave:** Band 38 (2.6GHz, TDD) is used to serve the German LL. The 5G Non-Standalone (NSA) architecture is used, while a switch to 5G Standalone (SA) is supported, if needed.

- New:
 - **60GHz-Wi-Fi:** Three 802.11ad routers were installed at the intersection in Ulm-Lehr, each facing one arm of the crossing (north, west, east). One of them is shown in Figure 2. The 60GHz Wi-Fi routers, manufactured by MicroTik, each offer a bandwidth of 2.16 GHz and range of approximately 150m. These 60GHz routers are connected to the RSU.

Figure 2: One of the installed 60-GHz-Wi-Fi access points at the LL

- **5G mm-Wave:** Three sector cells operating in Band 258 (24.25 - 27.5GHz, TDD) were installed at the intersection in Ulm-Lehr, as shown in Figure 3. The sector pointing north has an available bandwidth of 800MHz. A bandwidth of 400MHz is available for both the sector cell covering the area west of the intersection, and the one covering the area to the east. The cells are connected via dark fibre to the base station located in the Nokia lab (so-called front-haul connection).

Figure 3: Two of the three installed mmWave remote radio heads at the LL

- **MEC:** A MEC server was acquired with sufficient capacity to support the UC1 scenarios. It is simultaneously connected to an upgraded LTE (4G) core (called Evolved Packet Core, or EPC) which was defined in the 5G non-standalone (5G NSA) network architecture solution, as well as to a 5G core network (called 5G Core or 5GC), which was specified as 5G standalone (5G SA) network architecture solution. Additionally, a direct fibre connection between the RSU and MEC exists. The 5G NSA configuration is used only in combination with 5G mm-Wave.

- **Scheduler:** The scheduler on the MEC server is a software program utilizing the domain specific language P4 to allow traffic flow management across multiple communication channels, ensuring availability and redundancy. The scheduler is integrated on into the MEC and on the CAVs. The scheduler on the MEC side is divided into a software part running on the physical MEC host and a set of rules running within the application VM hosted on the MEC.
- **RSU:** The RSU establishes the direct communication to connected road users via 60-GHz-Wi-Fi and dark fibre to connect to the MEC server and acts as gateway for the SPUs to connect to the MEC server via 60-GHz-Wi-Fi. During PoDIUM, the dark fibre to the MEC as well as the 60-GHz-Wi-Fi were implemented.

2.1.1.2. Vehicles description

There are two CAVs involved in German LL, a VW Golf Variant from Bosch, shown in Figure 4, and a Mercedes E-Class from UULM, shown in Figure 5. Both CAVs are equipped with state-of-the-art sensor set for environment perception. The CAVs are upgraded with 5G cmWave, 5G mmWave and 60-GHz-Wi-Fi, which are managed from a communication PC with schedulers. The scheduler software is running on a dedicated Communication PC (ComPC) which is placed between the CarPC running the application and dedicated communication hardware for each communication technology. The scheduler on the ComPC possesses an API for external reconfiguration at runtime. The CAVs periodically send status updates of their location, object tracks (based on the vehicle sensor data), and planned route. The Bosch CAV can additionally send sensor data (e.g. radar locations, vehicle odometry, or GNSS data) to offload computations to the MEC server. Schedulers are used to choose the communication technology for data transmission, based on the QoS demands needed for the data transmission and the available communication technologies. If required, data can be duplicated and simultaneously transmitted using multiple communication technologies to increase the transmission reliability and add redundancy. Cooperative driving manoeuvres computed by the MEC server are transmitted back to the CAVs as suggestions, which the CAVs accept or decline according to their state and environment model.

Figure 4: The UULM CAV with the newly installed communication hardware

Figure 5: The UULM CAV with the newly installed communication hardware

2.1.1.3. Other test facilities

The VRU device in the German LL is a Nokia XR20. Its 5G cmWave connection is used for communication. The VRU periodically send status updates of the location, speed and planned route. This allows the VRU to be integrated into cooperative traffic manoeuvres which are computed by the edge server and then transmitted to the VRU.

2.1.2. PoDIUM PDI innovations' integration & validation

2.1.2.1. PDI internal integrations

- **All data integrated in the Digital Twin:** The Digital Twin fuses the road user detections from all SPUs and incoming CCAM messages (CAM, VAM, and CPM) into a complete environment model. During PoDIUM, the CCAM message versions were updated in D3.3 [3] and then integrated into the Digital Twin.
- **Self-Assessment integrated in Digital Twin:** The Digital Twin uses model-based multi-sensor multi-object tracker for the fusion of the information from the SPUs. The self-assessment monitors some of the assumptions that are made within the fusion algorithm. During PoDIUM, the methods described in [4] and [5] have been developed and integrated into the Digital Twin.
- **Digital Twin deployed on MEC:** The Digital Twin with the new features has been deployed on the new MEC server as docker container based on Ubuntu 24.04 and ROS2 Jazzy.
- **Scheduler integrated on MEC:** The integration of the scheduler within the MEC provides the necessary framework to enable multi-connectivity, with the specific configuration being dynamically adaptable at runtime. The scheduler is directly deployed on the MEC without any containerization. It consists of a user space program that is attached to the network stack of the physical MEC. Exchanged data packets that arrive at the MEC are first decapsulated and mapped to a deduplication data structure. If any duplicates of these data packets are observed on *other* incoming interfaces in the network stack, they are deduplicated. In the reverse direction, data packets intended for the CAV that are received from the application VM are encapsulated and duplicated on the outgoing paths (5G/60GHz).
- **Cooperative Planner deployed on MEC:** The developed cooperative manoeuvre planning service has successfully been deployed and integrated within the PoDIUM PDI. Deployed onto the MEC was done as a docker container that is based on Ubuntu 24.04 and ROS2 Jazzy. To exchange message with the digital twin and C-ITS message and user handling, the container is

started with inter-process communication within the same subnetwork. The integration was tested after validating the digital twin and C-ITS message and user handling services.

2.1.2.2. Vehicle-related integrations

- Communication hardware:** The CAVs were both upgraded with two roof-mounted 5G mmWave modems and two 60-GHz-Wi-Fi APs in addition to one 5G cmWave modem, as shown in Figure 5 for the UULM CAV. For 5G mmWave and 60-GHz-Wi-Fi, one antenna is facing front, and another is facing back to allow for a line of sight (LoS) with the equipment installed on the traverse in both driving directions. All the communication interfaces are managed by a communication PC (ComPC) that is directly wire-connected to the CarPC and has a scheduler running on it.
- Message scheduler:** The scheduler integration into the CAV systems serves as the counterpart to the scheduler on the MEC, enabling equivalent dynamically adaptable multi-connectivity. The scheduler on the CAV is placed on a separate Communication PC (ComPC) which is directly wire-connected to the main CarPC as well as to dedicated communication hardware. The ComPC runs Linux and the scheduler P4 program as a user space program connected to the network stack via P4. The scheduler encapsulates and duplicates incoming packets from the CarPC that are intended to the MEC and places the packet duplicates on the respective outgoing links to the dedicated communication hardware. On the CAV, we run dedicated hardware for each communication technology type, allowing fine-grained debugging and driver isolation. On the receiving side, the scheduler possesses a deduplication data structure that keeps track of packets observed before. The scheduler decapsulates and forwards the packets from the MEC that are intended for the CarPC while updating the deduplication data structure. If the same packet (i.e. a clone) is observed and matched coming from a different communication technology, then it is silently deduplicated and not forwarded to the CarPC.
- MCM handling:** To integrate MCMs within the AD functions of the Bosch CAV, a software solution implemented in a previous project has been generalized and enhanced to meet the requirements of the UC1. Given that the waypoint density of a suggested manoeuvre is not constrained by the message format, the in-vehicle processing of MCMs has been upgraded to effectively handle different levels of waypoint sparsity. Additionally, the handling of MCMs in the vehicle AD stack has been improved to support manoeuvres that require the CAV to use an oncoming lane, which is essential for the cooperative corridor handling of UC1. For the executing manoeuvre suggestions, the waypoints and constraints contained in the MCMs are provided as inputs to the in-vehicle motion planning module. A solution with similar capabilities that meet the same requirements has been developed for the UULM CAV.
- ETSI message definitions:** Starting point for the exchange of ETSI messages (CAM, CPM, MCM) via AMQP between the CAVs and the edge server was the implementation of the preceding project LUKAS [8]. However, two main enhancements had to be developed: Refactoring of AMQP message exchange due to replacement of LUKAS specific AMQP communication library with Apache QPid Proton [6]. Update of ETSI message specification for CPMs; the ASN.1 specification of CAM, CPM and MCM in use is given in [7]. The first work package involved the adaptation to the API of the QPid Proton library and mainly focused on improvements regarding code quality and runtime performance. The second work package comprised the adaptation of the ROS message definition for CPMs and of the conversion between ASN.1 and ROS messages. Each ETSI message received via AMQP in ASN.1 format is transformed into a corresponding ROS message before further processing and each calculated ETSI message in ROS format is transformed into a corresponding ASN.1 message before sending via AMQP. The

huge number of changes in the CPM specification was directly reflected in the effort for adapting the converters, especially since each received value must be validated against the ASN.1 specification. Since there are different implementations of the described ETSI message exchange for the UULM CAV resp. edge server on the one hand and for the Bosch CAV on the other hand, the development was performed incrementally. That means, there was a series of test-runs and code improvement steps between the first working version and the final one. Problems arose for example due to mismatches of AMQP message properties and handling of ETSI timestamps in the two code stacks.

2.1.2.3. Roadside entities integrations

- The 60 GHz Wi-Fi routers were mounted on the structure at the crossing in Ulm-Lehr and connected to the RSU in the local infrastructure in the roadside cabinet. To keep the communication paths disjoint, routing at the RSU is adapted accordingly to forward uplink packets to the MEC only through the connected fibre (not 5G) and correspondingly in the reverse direction.

2.1.2.4. VRU related integrations

- **Communication hardware for VRUs:** For tests in the German LL the VRU uses a 5G cm-Wave communication hardware modem from a Nokia XR20. For the VRU scenario, the Nokia XR20 is mounted on a bicycle in front of the bicyclist, shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: The smartphone with the VRU app is mounted on the bicycle

- **Handling of VAM:** For the integration of the VAMs for the Digital Twin, the VRU periodically sends status updates to the edge server. The corresponding data, e.g., location and speed of the VRU, are transmitted to the MEC server for further processing.
- **Handling of MCM:** For the integration of MCMs for the cooperative traffic manoeuvres of the VRU a software module implemented in a preceding project has been updated and extended in terms of functionality to handle the requirements of the PoDIUM Use Case 1. Arbitrary number of waypoints are supported for the manoeuvre when receiving an MCM and the HMI

design is chosen to support the representation of any number of waypoints required for the manoeuvre.

- Updated ETSI message definitions:** The exchange of ETSI messages (VAM, MCM) via AMQP between the VRU and the edger server was implemented within the preceding project LUKAS [8]. The basic functionality for PoDIUM has been extended to make the message interface compatible with the PoDIUM ASN.1 message update. There have been a few problems with the ASN.1 compiler / parser currently used in the Android project. To fix these incompatibilities, the ASN.1 messages had to be adapted to be backwards compatible. The messages are converted internally to Rust and processed accordingly. Several test runs were carried out for communication tests between VRU and edge server to ensure compatible communication.

2.1.3. Pre-demo testing methodology

Based on the deployment milestones identified in D4.1 [2], the following pre-test conditions must be met before the test.

2.1.3.1. Pre-test conditions

Table 1: Pre-test conditions for UC 1

Pre-test condition	Fulfilled	Comments
MEC deployed	fulfilled	
5G cm-wave works	Fulfilled	Functionality affirmed with drive tests
Road user detection deployed on SPUs	Fulfilled	Functionality affirmed with drive tests
V2X communication works	Fulfilled	Functionality affirmed with packet capture logs and end-to-end communication tests
60GHz-Wi-Fi works	Fulfilled	Functionality affirmed with packet capture logs
Digital Twin deployed	Fulfilled	Functionality affirmed with drive tests
5G mm-wave works	Fulfilled	Functionality affirmed with drive tests
Scheduler deployed	Fulfilled	Functionality affirmed with packet capture logs
CAV AD functions deployed	Fulfilled	Functionality affirmed with drive tests
Cooperative Planner deployed	fulfilled	Functionality affirmed with drive tests
VRU app deployed	fulfilled	

2.1.3.2. Description of pre-demo testing methodologies, plans and tools

Scenario 1:

The pre-demo testing followed a three-staged approach to verify the functionality and safety of the developed modules. The three test phases were: simulation, evaluation on a test track and integration tests in real traffic environment.

Initially, the developed modules were tested in a simulated environment. For the cooperative manoeuvre planner an in-house simulator to validate the closed-loop behaviour was used. The simulation test phase had the following objectives: a) Validation of the decision-making logic of the cooperative planner in various traffic scenarios, b) evaluation of performance under varying traffic conditions, c) identification of potential sources of error before physical testing. After successful validation in the simulation phase, tests were conducted on a test track. This was necessary as driving strategies involving lane changes onto the opposite lane to avoid obstacles had not been previously

tested in the Bosch CAV. Initially, a virtual blockade was projected into the scene by integrating a static obstacle into the vehicle's object detection system. Subsequently, tests were conducted using real vehicles as obstacles to evaluate interaction with dynamic objects. The main objective of the test track evaluation was the assurance that the generated manoeuvres are realistic and safely executable by the Bosch CAV. The simulation and real-world tests on the test track enabled the analysis of manoeuvres in a controlled environment before proceeding to the tests on public road.

Like on the test track, initial testing was performed using a virtual blockade. After positive assessment of the system performance, tests with real vehicles as obstacles were continued. Due to the safety-critical nature of these tests on public road, the CAVs were initially driven manually, while the received manoeuvre instructions were recorded and analysed retrospectively. Upon successful validation based on the recorded data, the pre-demo use case tests were continued using the automated driving functions.

For communication, first the individual communication channels were tested separately, and then the communication over all channels with the ComPC and scheduler was tested.

Because the cooperative planner and the successful execution of the manoeuvres depend directly or indirectly on all other developed PoDIUM components, e.g., the environment model of the digital twin, the described methodology is testing the whole system.

It enabled a safe and systematic evaluation of the deployed services. Findings from each test phase were iteratively used to optimize the system, ensuring a reliable and safe implementation.

Scenario 2:

For the second scenario, the same methodology as for scenario 1 was used. The additional components of the VRU were tested as follows:

In a first phase, the individual building blocks of the VRU app for Use Case 1 were tested with a local setup. The VRU app was started using the Android Emulator, which is part of the Android SDK. The Android emulator was then connected to a local AMQP broker with a simulated edge server service in order to exchange messages. In this phase, ETSI messages were exchanged to validate the communication regarding encoding and decoding of the ASN.1 interfaces but also functionalities like the logical processing of the ETSI messages can be verified. After a successful communication test of the ETSI messages, it was possible to proceed to the next phase.

In a second phase, the simulated edge server service was replaced by the edge server service functionality deployed within the German LL. This now enables initial integration with the cooperative planner deployed on the edge server. The test objective of this phase was to ensure the compatibility of the communication between VRU and Bosch cooperative planner on the edge server. Furthermore, the logical processing of the MCM message and its parameters was also evaluated. In this phase it was also ensured that the basic functionality between the VRU and the deployed software on the edge server was compatible, i.e. it is continuously checked when new software is deployed either on the VRU side or on the edge server side whether the systems are still compatible with each other. At this time, the VRU scenario was also tested logically in a slimmed-down form, e.g. with dummy manoeuvres.

In the third phase, the VRU app was deployed to a real mobile device, i.e. the Android emulator is replaced by the Nokia XR20. The Nokia device was tested directly at the German LL and the complete scenario can be carried out. To do this, the device was mounted on the bicycle so that the traffic manoeuvre in its entirety can be safely tested in road traffic.

2.1.3.3. Data logging setup and data storage

In UC1, several data are collected for validation and evaluation of the components and the overall system. Compared to the data collection and storage plan as developed in D4.1 [2] have been made. However, no data from the pre-demo tests will be made public.

2.1.4. Report of pre-demo testing activities

2.1.4.1. Functional tests

All functional components of the PoDIUM system required to realize UC1 were tested according to the requirements definition in D2.2 [1]. Our implementation fulfilled all requirements. The detailed checklist of the requirements is summarized in Annex 1 .

To achieve this goal, several tests had been necessary. The following section gives an overview of the conducted tests at the LL with their objectives and findings. Note that, only tests involving two or more partners are recorded here. Living Lab tests involving only one partner as well as simulated tests are not recorded. For all tests, we had the prerequisite that all PoDIUM components were operational, especially network connection was crucial for almost all tests.

The following tests were mainly between UULM and BOSCH with the main goal to realize the functional aspect of the use case, i.e., the interplay between road user detection, digital twin, cooperative planner, and realization of the cooperative manoeuvres by the two vehicles. If not noted otherwise, these tests were performed without the scheduler, i.e., with only one communication channel.

- **13.09.2024 Test with UULM and BOSCH:** The objective of this test was to verify the CCAM message compatibility between BOSCH and UULM, tests of the AMQP connection, recording of CAM and CPM messages for offline tests of the DT, and recording of data of UC tests with a simulated obstacle for offline tests of the cooperative planner. Based on this test, the DT was modified to include the association of a CAM into the environment model. This was needed by the cooperative planner.
- **8.10.2024 Test with UULM and BOSCH:** The objective of this test was to verify the combination of the cooperative planner on the MEC and the realization of the cooperative manoeuvres on the CAVs. Several problems were identified: Problems with the cooperative planner, problems with the digital twin, problems with the combination of the digital twin and cooperative planner, and problems with the realization of the cooperative manoeuvres on the UULM CAV. These problems were addressed by each partner individually and by the following tests.
- **25.10.2024 Test with UULM and BOSCH:** The objective of this test was to address the identified issues of the last test and to test the developed solutions. As a result, more individual development on the modules was done.
- **28.01.2025 Test with UULM and Bosch:** The objective was to test the system with a real blockage. For this another vehicle from UULM was used. For safety reasons, only one CAV was involved in the manoeuvre. Additionally, the 5G cm-Wave and mm-Wave was configured and tested on the BOSCH vehicle. Based on tests, the cooperative planner was re-parameterized to produce better trajectories, which afterwards both vehicles could successfully realize.
- **10.02.2025 Test with UULM and BOSCH:** The objective of this test was the realization of the full UC1. There was an issue with the environment model representation of the CAVs which caused the cooperative planner to abort manoeuvres. This was addressed by prioritizing the CAMs in the track-to-track fusion.
- **05.03.2025 Test with UULM and BOSCH:** The objective of this test was the recording of video data supporting the presentations at the German LL demo. Because of some issues with the localization of the BOSCH vehicle, no video data was recorded.

- **18.03.2025 Test with UULM and BOSCH:** During this test, the video data was recorded successfully. The implementation showed a robust performance of scenario 1 of UC1.
- **19.03.2025 Test with UDE and BOSCH:** The objective of this test was to determine whether the scheduler functioned correctly on BOSCH's CAV. Issues with the 5G mmWave and 60 GHz Wi-Fi connections were identified and resolved by the respective partners.
- **25.03.2025 Test with UDE and BOSCH:** The objective of this test was to confirm that the scheduler worked as intended on BOSCH's CAV. All tested components functioned correctly.
- **02.04.2025 Test with UULM and BOSCH:** The objective of this test was to establish a radio protocol to enhance the timing of the use case.
- **08.04.2025 Test with UULM and BOSCH:** The objective of the last test before the German LL demo was to perform a performance check of all components.

The following gives an overview over the tests involving multi-connectivity and the scheduler.

We decided to test the scheduler first on the UULM CAV and only afterwards deploy the tested to the BOSCH CAV.

- **27.11.2024 Test with UDE and Nokia:** The objective of this test was to determine why the developed packet duplication feature in the scheduler did not function correctly with the 5G cmWave and 5G mmWave modems. Dummy traffic and appropriate network devices were used in the Nokia Lab. The issue was traced to a compatibility problem between the hardware running the scheduler and the 5G cmWave/mmWave modems. This was resolved by introducing an intermediate device between the modem and the scheduler.
- **29.11.2024 Test with UDE and Nokia:** The objective of this test was to determine why the packet deduplication feature on the scheduler did not function on the MEC. This was tested using dummy traffic and the appropriate network devices in the Nokia Lab. A conflict between the pre-existing MEC network configuration and the newly added scheduler configuration was identified and resolved by adapting both configurations.
- **06.12.2024** The objective of this test was to investigate why the bandwidth achieved when using the scheduler was significantly lower than expected. Issues such as mismatched maximum segment sizes in the network, inconsistent network configurations, and an unstable 60 GHz Wi-Fi connection were identified. These issues were addressed individually by the partners.
- **06.03.2025 Test with UULM and UDE:** The objective of this test was to verify that the network and scheduler operated correctly on the MEC and UULM's CAV. All tested components functioned as intended.

2.1.4.2. Non-functional tests

All non-functional components of the PoDIUM system required to realize UC1 were tested according to the requirements definition in D2.2 [1]. Our implementation fulfilled all requirements. The detailed tests are summarized in Annex 1. In comparison to the previous chapter, no additional tests have been necessary to achieve this goal.

3. Spanish Living Lab

The Spanish LL is divided to 2 independent use cases which share certain common elements, such as the CAV shuttle, the CV vehicle of IDIADA, the Edge-Cloud infrastructure. Both use cases are located inside and close to the city of Barcelona.

3.1. Use Case 2

The UC2 activities of the Spanish LL are described in this chapter. UC2 will explore and demonstrate how real-time data exchange between connected vehicles and traffic infrastructure can enhance urban mobility through dynamic traffic signal control, cooperative manoeuvres, and predictive traffic management, by enabling key CCAM functionalities in complex city environments.

As a brief reminder, UC2 explores three scenarios:

- **Scenario 1:** prioritisation of emergency vehicles through GNSS-based positioning and cooperative responses;
- **Scenario 2:** optimisation of traffic flow using live CAM data and a Digital Twin for dynamic control strategies;
- **Scenario 3:** protection of vulnerable road users by detecting collision risks and triggering timely warnings to vehicles and VRUs.

In the following chapters we will describe:

- a) the LL testbed, including the deployment of new and/or adaptation of existing equipment of the LL and the preparation of the test vehicles and other test facilities
- b) the integration of the WP3 PDI innovations in the LL testbed, and validation
- c) the testing methodologies, data loggers, and test plan
- d) The pre-demo testing activities relevant for this UC, in line with the checklist of Functional and Non-Functional requirements as described in D2.2 [1].

A checklist for the LL preparation and integration validation is also provided in the Annex.

3.1.1. LL description

3.1.1.1. Description of the LL infrastructure (existing and newly installed)

Use Case 2 within the Spanish LL takes place in the heart of the city centre of Barcelona. The selected area (see Figure 7), agreed with the Barcelona City Council, offers good characteristics for the demonstration of the three UC2 scenarios proposed in the project: a large emergency corridor to test priority to emergency vehicles (red line), a grid of certain dimensions to test traffic optimisation in case of incidents (blue perimeter), and the existence of infrastructure for VRUs (pedestrians and cyclists) to test protection services for this type of users (green circle).

Figure 7: General view of the selected area for demonstrations in UC2

With the aim of testing the three proposed scenarios it's important to rely on the physical and digital infrastructure already installed in the city of Barcelona. below is a description of this infrastructure depending on different types. New infrastructure to be installed is also considered, allowing for the deployment of developed services in UC2 and testing of the scenarios:

Barcelona has a well-developed **urban traffic management infrastructure** which includes the following. The integration of this infrastructure with PoDIUM functionalities is described in section 3.1.2.1:

- **Traffic Control Centre (TCC):** The city uses a centralized TCC equipped with advanced physical infrastructure, including large video walls, control consoles, and dedicated communication systems that allow operators to monitor and manage the city's traffic in real time by operating an extensive network of traffic cameras, sensors, inductive loop detectors, adaptive traffic lights and air quality sensors installed throughout the city.
- **Traffic controllers:** Barcelona's Distributed Urban Traffic Control System (SDCTU, a product from ETRA) manages over 1,600 traffic controllers across the city. These controllers are located at intersections and are part of the city's intelligent traffic infrastructure, which includes inductive loop sensors, infrared sensors, artificial vision and Bluetooth devices, with centralized coordination through the TCC. Particularly for the 1 focusing on the management of high-priority vehicles, there are around 20 traffic controllers with traffic lights along the Gran Via corridor selected for the tests and demonstrations.
- **Smart Mobility digital infrastructure:** The MISTRAL Smart Mobility Platform (a product from ETRA) enhances Barcelona's traffic management by integrating real-time data from traffic lights, sensors, and public transport into a centralized system. It enables faster incident response, prioritizes public transport at intersections, and supports data-driven decision-making for long-term mobility planning. The following modules have been incorporated to the current version of MISTRAL installed in Barcelona for demonstrating the scenarios 1 and 2:

emergency priority service (EMEBO) with information about convoys management and priorities; traffic analytics service for visualising traffic metrics and O-D matrices from connected vehicles; SQL Server database; and incidents management service, including new actions to warn connected vehicles.

Barcelona's emergency management system for the Fire Prevention, Extinction and Rescue Service (SPEIS) integrates advanced technologies to enhance coordination, response times, and overall efficiency. Particularly for the scenario 1, it includes the following infrastructure, whose integration with PoDIUM functionalities is also described in 3.1.2.1:

- The **L'Eixample Fire Station**, currently operating from a temporary facility in *Joan Miró* urban park, operates responding to fire emergencies within the *L'Eixample* district where the selected emergencies corridor for demonstrations is located.
- **Mycelium Emergency Management System**: The Mycelium system is a multi-agency dispatch platform utilized by both the Local Police body "Guàrdia Urbana" and SPEIS. It provides a centralized platform for effective incident management, by integrating real-time data from various sources, including emergency calls, field units, and other agencies, to facilitate coordinated responses to emergencies. Particularly of interest for PoDIUM functions, it is responsible for opening and cancelling the emergencies corridor and assigning the vehicle to the emergency.
- **Communications manager**: The GCOM (Gestor de Comunicacions) system is a vital component of Barcelona's emergency communication infrastructure, particularly for the SPEIS whose primary function is to manage and streamline communications during emergency incidents. It integrates with other critical systems like the Mycelium emergency management system and the EMEBO service to give priority to emergency vehicles.

3.1.1.2. Vehicles description

There are three vehicles involved in Use Case 2 within the Spanish LL: the connected vehicle (CV), the connected and automated vehicle (CAV) and the emergency vehicle (EV).

Connected vehicle (provided by IDIADA):

Figure 8: IDIADA's connected vehicle with sensors

IDIADA's Connected Vehicle (CV) is a development platform used in PoDIUM UC2 and UC3 which acts as a vehicle with connected and perception capabilities (Figure 8). This vehicle will be driven by a human driver in UC2, reacting to the warnings and performing the recommended manoeuvres shown

in the vehicle’s HMI. At the time of this deliverable, the vehicle is fully equipped with a LiDAR, three front cameras and a front radar as part of perception system, and a Cohda Wireless MK6 C-V2X OBU and a 5G modem (Quectel RM500QGL) for the connectivity with other C-V2X stations (RSU and vehicles), with the MEC and the Cloud services.

Connected and Automated Vehicle (the shuttle, provided by MILLA):

Figure 9: MILLA’s connected vehicle with sensors

MILLA Connected and Autonomous Vehicle (CAV) is a level 4 SAE autonomous shuttle (Figure 9). The platform is automated, allowing the driver to control the steering and braking actuators with the help of on-board or off-board control intelligence. The MILLA CAV uses serial platforms from Renault Master Electric vehicles. The platform has M2 crash-test homologation.

The automated system consists of:

- A Steering Robotization System (ADSM*) installed on the column between the rack and the steering wheel,
- A Brake Robotization System (ADBS*) which acts directly on the MasterVac. The system is active, and in case of loss of hydraulic pressure or electrical problem, the main brake is automatically activated,
- Automatic Parking Brake (DPBS*) which acts on the emergency brake cable,
- An Emergency Brake System (EMBS*) which acts on both the main brake and on the parking brake,

- Perception sensors installed in the grille, bumpers and roof (LIDAR). Cameras in the passenger compartment and geolocation and connectivity antennas on the roof.
- Connectivity System composed by a Cohda Wireless MK6 C-V2X OBU and a 5G modem resp. for V2X communication with infrastructure (RSU) and for 4G/5G communication.
- Independent electrical harnesses dedicated to Robotization and Perception are installed in parallel with the vehicle harnesses.
- None of the vehicle's functions have been modified (Airbag, ABS, Power steering, etc.).

In addition to the automated system, the vehicle features conventional driver space and passengers' space; these two spaces embark safety onboard equipment.

The driver's cabin can be activated by the safety operator if needed. The driver's cabin of the original vehicle remains intact, with all controls (steering wheel, gas pedal and brake pedals, indicators, headlights, mirrors, wipers, demisters, etc.).

The safety operator's intervention has priority over the automated system.

In areas not intended for automated driving, the safety operator drives the shuttle in manual mode. MILLA Connected and Autonomous Vehicle (CAV) is supervised since a supervision centre located in Meudon (France). The supervision center ensures real-time monitoring of shuttle operations (vehicle state of health, analysis of the context of road events, smooth running of the service), remote operation (shutdown of the shuttle, opening of doors at stopping position) and facilitates remote and on-site intervention (preventive maintenance data) via MILLA Cloud services.

Emergency vehicle (Barcelona firefighters' truck or auxiliary vehicle):

Figure 10: Emergencies vehicles from Barcelona Firefighters service

Two emergency vehicles provided by the Barcelona Firefighters' Service will be used to test the scenario involving priority for emergency vehicles (Figure 10). The vehicle on the left is an auxiliary vehicle (type MIKE) used for additional tasks in emergencies. The vehicle on the right is a heavy truck (type BRAVO) designed for rapid response to a wide range of emergencies that plays a more active role in emergency operations, as it is equipped with high-capacity water pumps, water tanks, ladders, rescue equipment, and medical supplies.

3.1.1.3. Other test facilities

In addition to the aforementioned facilities and vehicles, there are others related to scenario 3 concerning the protection of VRUs. The area selected for the deployment of activities in this scenario is also located in Barcelona, specifically at the intersection between Gran Via de les Corts Catalanes Avenue and Girona Street (see Figure 7, marked with a green circle). This location was chosen because it meets all the necessary conditions, including the presence of bike lanes and pedestrian crossings, motor vehicle traffic, available space for installing equipment on public infrastructure and adequate visibility for user detection.

Next Figure 11 shows an image of the selected intersection, identifying the locations of the bike lanes, the pedestrian crossings, and the physical infrastructure installed at the intersection, including the cameras, the RSU, and the cabinet mounted above one of the two existing traffic controllers. This cabinet holds the router and the local risk estimation processor, as well as additional devices that ensure the equipment operates safely and efficiently. Section 3.1.2.3 includes pictures of the infrastructure installed on the road.

Figure 11: Selected intersection and location of the equipment

Other equipment related to road users (CV drivers and VRUs) will be used in different scenarios:

- **HMI:** Developed by IDIADA, it will be a tablet which can show the driver warnings related to the three scenarios: emergency vehicle approaching, traffic incident along their routes and risk of collision with a VRU. Next section 3.1.2.1 shows pictures of the HMI for two of the three scenarios.
- **VRU APP:** Developed by ETRA, it will show the VRUs warnings when there is a risk of collision with a motor vehicle (CV/CAV). Next section 3.1.2.4 shows pictures of this App.

3.1.2. PoDIUM PDI innovations’ integration & validation

3.1.2.1. PDI internal integrations

MEC integration

In the context of PoDIUM, Namla supports MEC deployments for UC3 and UC2, enabling several key capabilities. These include deploying and managing edge devices across multiple locations, ensuring the availability and security of edge infrastructure and handling application deployment and management across distributed edge servers.

Namla also provides a full-stack observability and monitoring solution. This covers hardware with real-time resource utilization, applications with in-depth monitoring and networking with comprehensive insights. This holistic view of the entire infrastructure and its operations allows for quick responses and efficient troubleshooting.

Namla’s orchestration is built on Kubernetes, extending clusters to the edge and providing a cloud-native environment where any container or VM-based application can be deployed at the edge. As depicted in Figure 12, UC3 implements a private 5G network connected to the MEC through a dedicated network.

UC2 is supported by a private virtual network on top of a public 5G network, ensuring that all traffic is encrypted and securely transported between edge devices (e.g., RSU, OBU) and the MEC platform. An IPsec tunnel has been implemented between the Mobile Operator Network (MNO) and the MEC premises to ensure the security of all exchanged information.

Figure 12: PoDIUM 5G network and MEC architecture for UC2 and UC3

To deploy the Namla platform and all associated applications at the MEC, three different servers have been deployed to support the various configurations and scenarios evaluated in UC2 and UC3, shown in Figure 13 and Figure 14.

Figure 13: Server 1 and Server 2 (Lenovo SE450)

Figure 14: Server 3 (Lenovo SE350)

Figure 15 presents the Namla web administration interface, which allows partners to easily integrate and deploy applications. This interface is accessible from outside the MEC premises with the support of a VPN connection that was set up to secure connectivity, in addition to a specific login and password allocated to each partner. Thanks to this setup, partners can connect from anywhere and seamlessly deploy and administer PoDIUM applications on different servers and locations.

Figure 15: Namla web administration interface

The presented MEC infrastructure (servers and Namla platform) is a key component of the Spanish Living Lab (LL). This solution is designed and implemented to support real deployments, aligning with PoDIUM's ambition to examine feasibility and sustainability concepts in real traffic conditions.

Integration with Barcelona Traffic and Emergencies Systems

Next are the pre-established systems that currently manage Barcelona's mobility and emergency services, as well as an update on how these systems are being modified to enable the operation of the PoDIUM services developed in UC2 (see Figure 16):

Traffic Management Systems:

- SDCTU (Distributed Urban Traffic Control System): Operates over 1,600 intersections and handles signal timings and real-time traffic flow.
- MISTRAL: The city's traffic management dashboard and decision-support tool. Recently updated to integrate PoDIUM-related modules (Traffic Analytics, Incident Manager).
- NSC: Communication system with traffic equipment (unchanged in PoDIUM).
- EMEBO: Module that manages emergency vehicle routes and signal priority. Updated in PoDIUM to process real-time GPS data.

Emergency Services Infrastructure:

- Mycelium: Emergency incident management platform for services like SPEIS (fire department).
- GCOM: Communication platform linking Mycelium with external systems and emergency vehicles.

Figure 16: Architecture for integration with the Barcelona TMC

UC2 has introduced new hardware and software components aimed at augmenting Barcelona’s existing infrastructure and allowing the functioning of all the developments and innovations in the three scenarios. On the streets, new AI-enabled cameras are deployed to detect VRUs. These cameras are connected to a local processing unit (NVIDIA Jetson Orin), which locally processes video images to estimate collision risks. This setup also includes an RSU, which communicates ETSI C-ITS messages directly to vehicles. All this roadside hardware is securely connected to a dedicated 5G VPN, ensuring real-time, encrypted data transmission.

In the backend, UC2 has developed and deployed software services across a cloud platform (hosted by the University of Murcia) and a new virtual machine at Barcelona’s TCC, known as “BCN AURORA CCAM.” These services include the Connected Vehicle Manager, which monitors communication with CAVs; the Traffic Metrics Generator, which processes vehicle data to create origin-destination matrices and travel time statistics; and the Cooperative Manoeuvre Recommender, which generates real-time messages for vehicles to clear the lane to approaching emergency vehicles. Other microservices manage emergency vehicle priority, incident notifications, and secure message brokering using MQTT. The integration with Barcelona’s traffic and emergency systems is designed to be seamless and secure. Communication between the cloud and the TCC platform is enabled through an MQTT “bridge” architecture, allowing filtered message exchange between brokers while maintaining isolation between different services. The GCOM platform serves as a critical intermediary, relaying emergency vehicle data from Mycelium to the EMEBO service to prioritize traffic signals accordingly (scenario 1). At the traffic management level, vehicle data collected is utilized by MISTRAL for analytics, incident forecasting and strategic planning for the traffic optimisation (scenario 2).

3.1.2.2. Vehicle-related integrations

Three different types of vehicles are involved in UC2: the connected vehicle provided by IDIADA, the connected and automated vehicle provided by MILLA, and the emergency vehicle provided by the Barcelona Firefighters’ Service. The integration of each type of vehicle is described below:

Connected vehicle integrations

For the scenarios described in this UC2 section, IDIADA needs to send to ETRA certain messages received by the ITS platform. In the same way, ETRA will send messages that IDIADA shall publish on the ITS platform (broker) to reach the clients.

IDIADA and ETRA agreed that, regardless the direction of the data flow, the communication data format will be JSON, being very similar to the Unigone JSON but with metric units instead of ETSI units and some structure changes as well.

OUT Interface (IDIADA->ETRA):

As described in the scenarios, ETRA is expecting only the CAM messages sent by all vehicles of the scenarios – the EV, CV and CAV –. This way, the OUT interface (Figure 17) only needs to capture the CAM messages arriving in the external broker, transform them to the agreed JSON format and send them to ETRA.

The CAM messages exchanged will vary depending on the vehicle source and the scenario. For each, a transformation from ETSI fields to metric units shall be performed, having a final result of a metric-based JSON CAM.

Figure 17: Image of the functional view IDIADA->ETRA

IN interface (ETRA → IDIADA):

ETRA will send JSON information (with the agree convention) which shall be understood as commands to publish ITS messages. Upon receiving a JSON message, the IN interface (Figure 18) shall transform it into a Unigone JSON to finally obtain the DTO that will be inserted into the ITS Message Manager to publish the message on the broker.

Figure 18: Image of the functional view ETRA->IDIADA

To enable correct message exchange on both the IN and OUT interfaces, several rounds of integration testing were carried out between ETRA and IDIADA for the three scenarios in a simulated environment. This included testing the HMIs developed by IDIADA. Below are two images (Figure 19) of the HMI developed for scenarios 2 (traffic optimisation) and 3 (VRUs protection). Each image shows two views: on the left is the vehicle view, which the driver will see on the tablet displaying the HMI; on the right is the infrastructure view.

Figure 19: HMIs pictures for scenario 2 (above) and scenario 3 (below)

Connected and automated vehicle integrations

The standalone integration tests of MILLA CAV are done at two levels (CAV Sub-System level and CAV System level):

MILLA CAV Sub-System level (MILLA- internal reports):

- *AD System (localisation, perception, AD functions)- Verification & Validation tests:*

These Sub-System tests focus on the AD functions of the MILLA CAV shuttle: unitary tests, end-of-end tests, key functional tests and key safety tests. Some of these tests are done with a software in the loop bench; others are done in the MILLA CAV shuttle on closed circuit at low speed (from 10km/h to 50km/h) and at high speed (from 60km/h to 80km/h).

The aim of these tests is to make qualitative and quantitative assessments on all the AD sub-System (HW and SW) components to validate, to verify, to confirm the compliance with traffic regulation, national authorities' requirements, MILLA design requirements and PODIUM project requirements. These tests are done without MEC connection, in MILLA CAV-standalone conditions, ensuring that AD functions receive all the commands from ITS messages and then the MILLA CAV shuttle applies the corresponding behaviour with success (according to the technical demonstration "UC scenarios" requirements and the commercial demonstration "on-demand service" requirements) in safe conditions.

– *Robotization System- Verification & Validation tests:*

These sub-System tests focus on the Robotization functions of the MILLA CAV shuttle: unitary tests, end-of-end tests, key functional tests and key safety tests. Some of these tests are done with a Hardware/Software in the loop bench; others are done in the MILLA CAV shuttle on closed circuit at low speed (from 10km/h to 50km/h) and at high speed (from 60km/h to 80km/h).

The aim of these tests is to conduct qualitative and quantitative tests on all the Robotization sub-System (HW and SW) components to validate, verify, and confirm the compliance with traffic regulation, national authorities' requirements, MILLA design requirements, and PoDIUM project requirements. These tests are done without MEC connection, in MILLA CAV-standalone conditions by ensuring that the MILLA CAV shuttle can apply the corresponding behaviour with success (according to the technical demonstration "UC scenarios" requirements and the commercial demonstration "on-demand service" requirements) in safe conditions.

– *4G/5G Connectivity System - Verification & Validation tests:*

These sub-System tests focus on the 4G/5G functions of the MILLA CAV shuttle: unitary tests, end-of-end tests, key functional tests and tele supervision tests.

The aim of these tests is to conduct qualitative and quantitative tests on all 4G/5G sub-System (HW, SW and cloud) components to validate, verify, and confirm the compliance with traffic regulation, national authorities' requirements, MILLA design requirements and PoDIUM project requirements. These tests are done without MEC connection, in MILLA CAV-standalone conditions by ensuring that the MILLA CAV shuttle can apply the corresponding behaviour with success (according to the technical demonstration "UC scenarios" requirements and the commercial demonstration "on-demand service" requirements) in safe conditions.

– *V2X Connectivity System - Verification & Validation tests:*

These sub-System tests are focus on the V2X functions of the MILLA CAV shuttle: unitary tests, end-of-end tests, key functional tests and tele supervision tests.

For these tests, we used the MILLA-V2X architecture (V2X components defined and designed by MILLA), not the PoDIUM-V2X architecture (with OBU provided by IDIADA/i2CAT, embedded V2X SW stack). Some of these tests were done in Static conditions via Json files shared by IDIADA/i2CAT; others are done in the MILLA CAV shuttle on a route equipped by RSUs at low speed (up to 50km/h). The compatibility between the connected infrastructure and the PoDIUM connected infrastructure has been ensured. The reception and transmission of the ITS messages have been successfully validated (CAM, DENM, IVIM, MCM and CPM).

The aim of these tests is to conduct qualitative and quantitative tests on all V2X sub-System (HW, SW) components to validate, verify, and confirm compliance with MILLA design requirements and PoDIUM project requirements. These tests were done without MEC connection, in MILLA CAV- standalone conditions to ensure that the V2X functional compatibility between the MILLA CAV shuttle and a connected infrastructure meets the technical demonstration "UC scenarios" requirements and the commercial demonstration "on-demand service" requirements in safe conditions.

Milla CAV System level:

- *Shuttle reception- Verification report:*

These verifications are done to ensure the compliance between MILLA requirements and the CAR provider (CAR refers to all MILLA CAV components except AD system components, Robotization system components, 4G/5G system components, V2X system components).

- *Automated system- Verification & Validation tests,*
 These tests focus on AD system fully integrated in the MILLA CAV shuttle: functional tests and safety tests. A part of these tests is done on a closed circuit. Another part of these tests is done on “reference” an open circuit. Both are done at low speed (from 10km/h to 50km/h) and at high speed (from 60km/h to 80km/h).
 The aim of these tests is to conduct qualitative and quantitative tests on all AD system integrated in the MILLA CAV shuttle to validate, verify, and confirm compliance with traffic regulation, national authorities’ requirements, MILLA design requirements.
 These tests are done without MEC connection, in MILLA CAV- standalone conditions by ensuring that the MILLA CAV shuttle can operate in full autonomous mode (with supervision centre) in safe conditions.

- *Field trials on closed route, on closed circuit (UC2 and UC3 scenarios tests + MILLA scenarios tests) in Satory (France):*
 These tests focus on MILLA CAV in field trials for UC scenarios and MILLA key scenarios. All these tests are done on a close circuit according to UC scenarios sequences at low speed (from 10km/h to 50km/h) and at high speed (from 60km/h to 80km/h).
 The aim of these tests is to conduct qualitative and quantitative tests on all connected, automated and supervised system integrated to validate, verify, and confirm compliance with UC scenarios and key MILLA scenarios. These tests are done without MEC connection, in MILLA CAV- standalone conditions.

- *Field trials on open circuit in Louvois (France):*
 These tests focussed on MILLA CAV daily field trials in manual mode and AD mode in real life situations, on an open circuit.
 The aim of these tests is to conduct qualitative and quantitative tests on all connected, automated and supervised shuttle to validate, verify, and confirm compliance with ODD, traffic regulation, national authorities’ requirements, and MILLA design requirements in real life situations. These tests are done without MEC connection, in MILLA CAV- standalone conditions.

In addition to these standalone integrations, others were carried out by different partners (MILLA, IDIADA and i2CAT) for the V2X stack integration in the CAV. There were two sets of tests:

Report on work carried out for V2X integration:

Two integration tests were performed on the 15th and 16th of October 2024:

- A static test was performed on the first day at MILLA premises in Paris, focusing on hardware and software integration (Figure 20 and Figure 21). For hardware integration, components such as the OBU, 5G modem, and Ethernet switch were temporarily installed and powered using an external battery. On the software side, the IDIADA and i2CAT stacks were deployed and tested on laptops due to limitations with the vehicle's battery. However, some components, like the PoDIUM 5G modem, were not used, and MEC services were emulated using laptops and a cloud-based MQTT broker.

It was successfully validated the real-time location converted to CAM messages and transmitted via C-V2X and 5G, and the emergency vehicle approximation which triggered a DENM successfully reaching the LDM.

Figure 20: In-vehicle setup used in the tests

Figure 21: HW installation on the MILA shuttle for the integration tests

- A dynamic test was performed on the second day at the Circuit de Versailles-Satory (Figure 22), focusing on scenario-based validation. Several scenarios in both UC2 and UC3 were tested: a DENM message triggering a reroute in the vehicle (UC2); a DENM transmitted through C-V2X and received by the LDM and an IVIM message causing the vehicle to reduce and maintain its speed at 30 km/h (UC3); and for the

VRU collision risk scenario (UC2 and UC3), the CAV performed a safety stop upon receiving the relevant DENM.

Scenario validation was also conducted using the MILLA CAV in standalone mode, including a pedestrian crossing scenario, an intersection priority scenario, and a high-speed scenario.

Figure 22: Image of the Versailles-Satory where the dynamic test took place

Following the previous tests, additional integration tests were performed on the 6th of March once the MILLA vehicle arrived in Barcelona. They were done in an underground parking spot where the vehicle was parked. Because of that, integration progress was limited due to environmental constraints—unstable cellular connection and no GPS signal in the underground parking, preventing full continuation of tests.

Despite this issue some achievements were made:

- IDIADA MEC services were validated with vehicle stack over 5G for the following scenarios: UC2 Emergency Vehicle (with HMI), UC2 Traffic Management (with HMI and MILLA interface) and UC3 Road Hazard (with HMI).
- It could be confirmed that the integration between i2CAT and IDIADA vehicle stacks via 5G (no C-V2X), and between IDIADA and MILLA vehicle stacks, was successful.

A list of the checks performed is also included in the UC3 vehicle-related integrations (see section 3.2.2.2).

Emergency vehicle integrations

Barcelona’s Emergency Management system is being upgraded with two key innovations representing a significant advancement in emergency response infrastructure, enhancing operational efficiency and reducing response times. First, vehicle localisation based on *TETRA* technology is being replaced by GNSS tracking, enabling real-time and more accurate positioning of emergency vehicles. Second, instead of relying on beacon activations to estimate arrival times at intersections, the system will now use vehicle GNSS data, allowing for more precise and dynamic traffic signal prioritisation.

GNSS-based vehicle positioning:

Barcelona’s emergency vehicles positioning system will test an evolution from localisation based on *TETRA* technology to GNSS tracking, enabling continuous and more accurate vehicle positioning. This shift allows real-time transmission of vehicle location through C-ITS (ETSI CAM

messages) using the Communications Manager (GCOM), enhancing prediction of arrival times at intersections, route optimisation and dynamic traffic signal prioritisation via the PoDIUM services.

Dynamic Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) calculation via GNSS:

In the current emergency management system, the baseline logic for emergency vehicle (EV) prioritisation along a predefined emergency corridor relies on a series of strategically placed beacons that detect its presence. These activations serve as input to estimate the ETA at upcoming intersections, using a pre-configured speed profile, which are used to send commands to the traffic controllers to activate green light phases along the EV’s path. While functional, this approach offers limited flexibility, as it does not account for dynamic variations in vehicle speed, traffic conditions, or unexpected delays.

The new approach leverages real-time GNSS data to calculate arrival times to intersections dynamically, improving responsiveness to real traffic conditions and enabling more precise signal control at intersections.

3.1.2.3. Roadside entities integrations

This chapter describes the implementation and integration of technologies in the scenario 3 – protection of VRUs – aimed at detecting them, assessing collision risks with motor vehicles, and communicating these risks via ETSI CAM messages to both VRUs and connected vehicles.

According to Figure 11, the setup includes the installation of two cameras Dahua Technology IPC-HDBW2241R-ZS cameras and a Cohda MK6 Roadside Unit on lampposts positioned between the main carriageway and service lanes (see pictures in Figure 23).

Figure 23: Cameras and RSU installed at the intersection

Next Figure 24 shows the connection architecture between the devices, including electrical protection, all of which is wired and complies with the protocols required by the Barcelona City Council for the installation of this type of equipment.

Figure 24: Connection diagram between all the equipment

The metal cabinet is mounted on top of the existing traffic controller installed at the intersection (see Figure 25). It houses a communications router (model Milesight UR75) and a local processing unit (NVIDIA Jetson Orin 3011), electrical protection components and a fan to ensure safe and reliable operation, as shown in the connection diagram above. As the cabinet is made of metal, an external antenna model 4X4 MiMo 4G/5G L[X]A[X]M4-7-42[-X] (Figure 26) has been installed on the top of the cabinet to prevent communication failures. This setup avoids interferences caused by the Faraday cage effect.

Figure 25: Cabinet on the traffic controller

Figure 26: External antenna installed on the cabinet

The data transmitted, which in no case will be images detected by the cameras (personal data protection requirement), between the cameras and the local processing equipment, as well as to external services, is channelled through the router using the 5G mobile network, which in turn is integrated with the VPN that provides security for the entire communications network. Therefore, the security measures implemented at the local level are the same as those adopted in the VPN network (see Figure 12).

3.1.2.4. VRU related integrations

To enable the functionalities related to VRUs (both connected and non-connected) in UC2, a series of integrations have been completed. These consist of two different main components:

Detection of VRUs and risk estimation:

- Edge AI infrastructure has been deployed, including two high-resolution cameras and a video processing unit (NVIDIA Jetson Orin Nano).
- The following functional modules have been containerised and deployed on the NVIDIA unit: object detection, surface segmentation, trajectory calculation, pixel-to-world mapping and risk management (described in deliverable D3.3 [3]).
- These components are integrated into a processing pipeline that detects, tracks and predicts the movement of road users, generating collision risk alerts in real time.
- Integration with the RSU ensures that the alerts are transmitted to connected VRUs and vehicles.

VRU Application:

- A mobile VRU App (developed in Flutter for Android) integrates location-based querying of a risk event database to inform VRUs of potential collision risks.
- The VRU App periodically collects the user's position and queries a Google Firebase service for nearby risk events, triggering visual notifications and alerts.
- Although full connectivity to Google Firebase is pending, the app has been validated in a laboratory at ETRA to demonstrate its end-to-end functionality.

3.1.3. Pre-demo testing methodology

Based on the deployment milestones identified in D4.1 [2], the following pre-test conditions must be met before the test.

3.1.3.1. Pre-test conditions

Table 2: Pre-test conditions for UC 2

Pre-test condition	Fulfilled	Comments
Common conditions for all scenarios:		
Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials.	Partial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •CAV permissions: pending (18 July): red plates and AD permissions (DGT), followed by Barcelona City Council permissions for AD tests. •Permits for the circulation of the emergency vehicles have been granted •CVs don't require permissions, except for those intended to circulate along bus lanes (grated)
CAVs/CVs with the PoDIUM equipment and software installed (OBU)	Yes	
PoDIUM platform service infrastructure ready and enabled (or disabled, when capturing data for the baseline situation)	Yes	
Conditions for scenario 1: Prioritisation of emergency vehicles		
EV with the PoDIUM equipment and software installed	Yes	Software to connect emergency and traffic systems developed and integrated with local partners
Data model of the emergency corridor provided	Yes	
At least fair results of KPI_UC2_1 should have been previously obtained with long guard times.	Not yet	Dependant on the KPIs calculation phase (demos)
Guard times configuration reduced	Not yet	This is a work in progress, as the EV scenario is being tested in a series of phases
The planned routes of CAVs/CVs for the demo should include some common road segments with pre-defined EV corridors, and be timed to facilitate the coincidence of EVs and CAVs/CVs in some of the road segments	Yes	
Conditions for scenario 2: Optimisation of traffic flow		
O-D zones modelled	Yes	
City data model available	Yes	
Conditions for scenario 3: Protection of VRUs		
PoDIUM equipment installed in the intersection, including an RSU and an Edge computer with PoDIUM software installed (including the Collision Risk estimation functionality)	Yes	

Cameras with AI functionality for VRU detection installed at the intersection pointing to the potential collision risk areas between vehicles and VRUs	Yes	
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3.1.3.2. Description of pre-demo testing methodologies, plans and tools

The UC2 demonstration in Barcelona will take place in the Gran Via area and its surrounding areas, which are highly dynamic and complex environments. This urban corridor is characterised by heavy traffic, including dedicated bus lanes for public transport, large numbers of private vehicles and taxis, frequent tourist and private buses, and unpredictable behaviour from VRUs, such as motorcyclists. These factors pose significant challenges to the safe and efficient execution of the three planned test scenarios. To ensure the demonstrations are successful, robust safety measures must be implemented, such as traffic cones and clear signage, and coordination with the local police is required. Time slots must also be carefully selected to avoid peak congestion periods. It is also important to identify specific road stretches for cooperative manoeuvres that minimise the impact of public transport and other traffic interferences (when feasible), thereby creating a more controlled and representative testing environment. All these issues have been considered when planning the tests for the following three scenarios.

Scenario 1:

Scenario 1 focuses on the management of emergency vehicles. The process begins with the reception of an emergency alert, after which the emergency system requests the TMS to open a corridor. At the same time, it continuously sends the EV position and speed. In response, the TMS dynamically adjusts traffic plans by modifying traffic lights as the EV approaches intersections. Additionally, the TMS informs CVs/CAVs about the lane reserved for the EV so that they can leave the lane to the EV.

To validate the performance and impact of the emergency vehicle priority system developed in the PoDIUM project, a series of controlled **pre-demonstration tests** have been designed. These tests aim to assess both the baseline priority management logic and the PoDIUM-enhanced approach, which integrates real-time vehicles’ positioning data, dynamic prediction of the Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) of the EV to the intersections, and cooperative interaction with CAVs. The testing methodology relies on repeated iterations under varying conditions, using connected infrastructure and vehicles to collect data. This structured approach allows for iterative refinement of system parameters (e.g. guard time configurations) before public deployment in the live demonstration phase.

Following the test cases identified in deliverable D5.1 [9] and based on the last conditions, the test starts with the activation of the emergency corridor, followed by the start of the EV’s journey. The test explores two configurations: one with the PoDIUM service enabled (enhanced logic) and another without it (baseline logic using beacons).

If PoDIUM is enabled, the system receives real-time CAM messages from the EV, which allow for accurate estimation of arrival times (ETA) at intersections. This data is used by the PoDIUM service developed to give priority to the EV (EMEBO) to activate green light priority with sufficient anticipation. In the baseline, only beacon triggers and a pre-configured speed profile are used to estimate ETA, and EMEBO acts accordingly without real-time input. An experimental variable is the progressive reduction of guard times to evaluate the effect on traffic signal responsiveness and impact on cross-traffic delays (KPI_UC2_4).

Simultaneously, the CV/CAV begins its journey along the corridor and continuously sends CAM messages to the Cooperative Manoeuvre Recommender (CMR). When the system detects a potential coincidence, a spatial-temporal overlap between an EV and a CV/CAV, the CMR sends DENM messages to the vehicles. CAVs react autonomously, while CVs use the HMI to alert the driver and prompt a cooperative manoeuvre.

Once the EV overtakes the CV/CAV, it continues through the corridor crossing intersections. After the final intersection, the system checks whether the EV had to stop or slow down at any point. If not, the guard time reduction process may continue. If it did, the guard time reduction is stopped.

At the end of the test, logs are used to evaluate KPI_UC2_1, KPI_UC2_4 and KPI_UC_5, as described in deliverable D5.1 [9].

The different innovations are planned to be tested in **four progressive phases**, as described in section 3.1.4.3. In phases 1 and 2, EV positioning will be tested using GNSS and ETSI CAM messages sent by the EV. In phase 3, priority for the EV will be tested. Finally, cooperative manoeuvring between the EV and the CV/CAV will be tested.

These are the general conditions for testing the scenario 1, as well as some that are specific to iterations:

- Location: Firefighters' corridor along the Gran Via Avenue in Barcelona city, which is internally identified by the emergencies management system with the numbers 9 and 10 (red line, see Figure 7).
- Starting point for vehicle circulation:
 - The EV starts at the "L'Eixample (Central) fire station"
 - The IDIADA CV and MILLA CAV vehicles start at a certain point of the corridor so that the cooperative manoeuvre takes place along the corridor between Bruc and Bailén Streets.
- The cooperative manoeuvre takes place along the two bus lanes on the corridor to avoid interference with the heavy private traffic on the other three lanes.
- Estimated test duration: around 6–7 minutes to complete the corridor, plus an additional 10–12 minutes to return to the starting point.
- Time: morning between 10:00 and 12:30 and afternoon between 15:00 and 17:00, trying to avoid peak traffic hours on the corridor.
- Two basic sub-scenarios:
 - Baseline: without the actuation of the PoDIUM service developed to prioritise the EV. In this case, the estimated time of arrival (ETA) of the EV at the intersection is calculated based on beacon triggering and a pre-configured EV speed profile.
 - PoDIUM- enabled: ETA is calculated based on EV positioning via CAM messages.

Scenario 2:

Scenario 2 focuses on improving urban traffic management by leveraging real-time data from CVs.

Through continuous transmission of CAM messages, including vehicle position, speed, and origin-destination data, the PoDIUM platform enables the generation of detailed traffic metrics and dynamic incident response. The integration of these metrics with the city's DT and TMS supports predictive analysis and enables traffic control measures (e.g. route recommendations or incident warnings) communicated back to vehicles via DENM messages so that they can react accordingly.

Pre-demonstration testing is essential to validate the functionality and responsiveness of this system under realistic traffic conditions. It follows a structured methodology based on real-world traffic simulation using CVs. The tests are executed across multiple origin-destination pairs within the pilot area to ensure broad spatial coverage, which will feed into the PoDIUM platform to ensure a sufficient range of traffic data for the generation of traffic metrics.

The test begins with the start of the test period, during which CVs perform trips between various origin-destination pairs within the pilot area. As they travel, the CVs send CAM messages that include their current position, speed, and OD information. These are received by the Traffic Metrics Generator (TMG) service of the PoDIUM platform.

The TMG processes the data in two parallel streams: it generates OD matrices by detecting trip start and end points, and calculates travel times, speeds, and delays per road segment. All generated metrics are aggregated per integration period and then sent to the DT and the TMS, providing an up-to-date view of traffic conditions.

Meanwhile, the Traffic Status Assessment (TSA) service of PoDIUM monitors notifications of incidents coming from the TMS. When a relevant event is detected, TSA translates it into DENM messages, which are sent to CVs and CAVs potentially affected. These alerts are also delivered through the Cooperative Manoeuvre Recommender (CMR), which sends DENMs to approaching vehicles.

In response, CAVs autonomously adjust their routes, while CV drivers receive HMI warnings prompting manual action. The objective is for all vehicles to take preventive measures and avoid the incident area, validating the effectiveness of both the traffic analytics and incident response loop.

At the end of the test, logs are used to evaluate KPI_UC2_2 and KPI_UC2_3, as described in deliverable D5.1 [9].

These are the general conditions for testing Scenario 2, as well as some that are specific to iterations:

- Location: surroundings of the Gran Via Avenue (see Figure 7 for the area delimited in blue).
- Starting point for vehicle circulation: the IDIADA CV and MILLA CAV vehicles start from a point well in advance of the corridor, allowing them sufficient space to change their route and avoid the incident.
- Planned routes for the vehicles are included within the delimited area. This means that any origin and destination data sent by the vehicles will also be included in this area.
- Estimated test duration: depending on the OD of the vehicles, it could last around 6-10 minutes for the test itself and another 10 minutes for the return to the starting point.
- Time: This scenario has fewer constraints as there is no interaction with other traffic or road users (despite general traffic).
- No baseline configuration is defined for scenario 2.

Scenario 3:

Scenario 3 addresses the safety of VRUs in urban intersections. By combining AI-powered cameras for VRU detection and CAM messages from CVs, the system evaluates the risk of collisions in real time. When a high-risk situation is identified, DENM messages or App alerts are sent to vehicles and/or VRUs to trigger preventive action. This scenario enhances safety through early warning and coordinated responses between road users and infrastructure.

Pre-demonstration testing focuses on validating the real-time risk detection and reaction system. The tests are carried out in controlled conditions where both CVs/CAVs and VRUs operate around a specific intersection with the PoDIUM system either active or deactivated (baseline). The Collision Risk

Estimator (CRE) and AI vision system are monitored for their ability to detect VRUs and predict risk scenarios based on CAM data and visual input. The tools involved include CAM/DENM message logging, infrastructure elements (RSU, AI cameras, local processing unit), VRU mobile app, and vehicle onboard systems (OBU and HMI). Reaction times, deceleration behaviour, and avoidance events are logged to assess system effectiveness and calculate the relevant KPIs.

The test begins with a CV/CAV and a VRU approaching the same intersection. The vehicle transmits CAM messages while the AI-based vision system monitors the intersection for VRU activity. If the PoDIUM service is enabled, the system uses both data streams to allow the Collision Risk Estimator (CRE) to analyse the situation.

When a risk event is identified (based on proximity and trajectory) the CRE initiates alerts: DENM messages are sent to CVs/CAVs, triggering either automatic braking (CAV) or a driver warning through the HMI (CV).

Simultaneously, the VRU receives a mobile app warning, prompting them to stop or change behaviour. If PoDIUM is not enabled, VRU detection and warning do not occur, forming the baseline for comparison.

The test ends when the CV/CAV and/or VRU successfully avoid a collision. Vehicle logs and reaction timestamps are analysed to evaluate KPI_UC2_6 and KPI_UC2_7, as described in deliverable D5.1 [9].

These are the general conditions for testing scenario 3, as well as some that are specific to iterations:

- Location: Intersection between the Gran Via Avenue and Girona Street in Barcelona city (green circle, see Figure 7).
- Starting point for vehicle circulation: The IDIADA CV and MILLA CAV vehicles start at a certain point along the corridor before the intersection.
- The cameras will detect the VRUs circulating within the intersection, using the bike lanes or the pedestrian crossings.
- Estimated test duration: around 1-2 minutes for the test itself and another 5-6 minutes to return to the starting point.
- Time: morning between 10:00 and 12:30 and afternoon between 15:00 and 17:00, trying to avoid peak traffic hours on the corridor.
- Two basic sub-scenarios:
 - Baseline: without the actuation of the PoDIUM service developed to detect VRUs by the cameras.
 - With the PoDIUM service enabled.

3.1.3.3. Data logging setup and data storage

The data logging strategy for UC2 remains consistent with the plan defined in Deliverable D4.1 [2], and no changes are introduced during the pre-demonstration phase. Logging is carried out across all three scenarios in order to support both technical validation and KPI evaluation.

Logs are collected from key system components, including the TMC, CV/CAVs, the C-ITS Gateway, Risk Management services, and the VRU mobile app. The data includes CAM and DENM messages, vehicle trajectories, traffic light status, VRU detections, and traffic metrics such as OD matrices and travel times. The specific scenario tested determines which data is collected.

Storage is distributed across several secure platforms:

- **TMC warehouse:** SQL database for aggregated traffic data.
- **Local storage:** High-volume logs are stored in the PoDIUM platform.

- **Redmine:** An internal repository for shared scenario data and KPI calculations.
- **ZENODO:** Public repository for C-ITS message logs.
- **Firebase:** Cloud database for mobile app logs from VRUs.

3.1.4. Report of pre-demo testing activities

Several UC2 partners carried out pre-demonstration field tests to evaluate the functional and non-functional requirements. The tests covered various elements of the PDI innovations that had previously been integrated in laboratory and closed-circuit environments (section 3.1.2):

- On different dates, three tests were conducted to demonstrate scenario 1 related to the emergency vehicle, using a progressive approach to test several elements: corridor opening, EV positioning and priority for the EV.
- On 7–8 July 2025, several tests were conducted to evaluate the performance of installations and deployments with respect to scenario 3, which is aimed at protecting VRUs.

These pre-demo activities allowed for the demonstration of the functional and non-functional requirements, as described in the following sections.

3.1.4.1. Functional tests

These tests focus on verifying that the system behaves correctly according to its defined UC2 functional requirements. Although some modifications were made to the original scope, UC2 implementation fulfilled the vast majority of requirements (see Annex 1).

MEC testing

To fulfil the functional requirements relating to the Connected Vehicle Manager (CVM) and its role in enabling bidirectional communication between vehicles and the infrastructure, two services were successfully deployed in the MEC environment, the Gateway (developed by IDIADA) and the MQTT broker (Mosquitto open-source broker, developed by ETRA). These services were integrated and validated within the UC2 setup to ensure the effective exchange of CAM and DENM messages between the vehicles and infrastructure components.

Specifically, this implementation addresses the following functional requirements: PF_UC2-CVM_001 (receiving CAM from connected vehicles (CVs) and forwarding events from the infrastructure), PF_UC2-CVM_003 (transmitting V2X messages to RSUs via C-V2X), PF_UC2-CVM_002, PF_UC2-CVM_004 (disseminating V2X messages based on vehicle location using 5G) and PF_UC2-VRU_001 (transmitting collision risks through the CVM). Validation confirmed the interoperability and correct functioning of these functionalities under simulated and real-time environments, ensuring connected vehicles and infrastructure can communicate with each other.

Figure 27 and Figure 28 show the deployed services running in the MEC infrastructure, using the Namla platform (section 3.1.2.1). These deployments highlight the integration of key services at the network edge to support low-latency and high-reliability applications.

Figure 27: Screenshot of the UC2 IDIADA Gateway deployed on the MEC (Namla platform)

Figure 28: Screenshot of the UC2 MQTT deployed on the MEC (Namla platform)

Next Figure 29 shows a zoomed-in view of an active Pod in the NAMLA environment, which represents the interaction between IDIADA Gateway and ETRA’s MQTT, confirming that the deployed vehicle and infrastructure’s services are communicating successfully. Together, these figures provide evidence of proper deployment, service execution and end-to-end system interoperability.

Figure 29: Screenshot of the IDIADA-ETRA interaction on the MEC (Namla platform)

CLOUD testing

The Emergency Vehicle Manager (EMEBO) and TMS cloud services were successfully integrated and validated by connecting PoDIUM functionalities to existing traffic and emergency management platforms (see ‘Integration with Barcelona Traffic and Emergencies Systems’ in section 3.1.2.1). This integration enables the reception of real-time data such as EV positions and priority, as well as the dissemination of event-based information to CVs and CAVs.

Validation confirmed fulfilment of some functional requirements, including PF_UC2-EV_001 and PF_UC2-EVM_003 (sending EV position and speed to the EVM), PF_UC2-EVM_001, PF_UC2-EVM_002 (receiving corridors and EV positions), PF_UC2-EVM_004 and PF_UC2-EVM_005 (transmitting and disseminating V2X messages), and PF_UC2-TMS_009 (estimating EV arrival times and prioritising traffic lights), all relate to scenario 1. PF_UC2-TMS_001 to PF_UC2-TMS_008, regarding the scenario 2, were also successfully integrated and validated.

These services demonstrate reliable communication with infrastructure and MEC components, enabling coordinated responses to dynamic road events and improving traffic flow during emergency scenarios.

CV testing

Some integration and tests have been performed to fulfil the functional requirements related to the CV:

- The IDIADA vehicle is a connected vehicle (CV) without automated functions in UC2. The vehicle can send and receive V2X messages to/from the CVM using both 5G and C-V2X (requirements PF_UC2_CAV_002, PF_UC2_CAV_005 and PF_UC2_CAV_008). PF_UC2_CAV_004 has changed since CPMs will not be used in UC2 (see Annex 1 UC2 section 7.1.2.1).
Figure 30 presents a log from a test involving two CVs transmitting CAMs using both C-ITS and 5G. The test evaluated the consistency and reliability of real-time communication across different technologies, confirming synchronized and continuous CAM transmission.
- An HMI device (tablet) is installed in the IDIADA CV providing the driver with traffic and manoeuvre recommendations for the three scenarios in UC2 (see section 3.1.2.2) (requirements PF_UC2_CAV_006 and PF_UC2_CAV_007).
- PF_UC2-CAV_003 about CAMs transmission rate, as detailed in non-functional test for P_UC2-CAV_005 (section 3.1.4.2), has already been validated. This outlines the expected behaviour of the system and confirms that the CV meets the specified criteria for generating CAMs.
- PF_UC2_CAV_001 has not been tested so far. It will be done from September 2025 and reported on deliverable D5.2

```

2025-06-19 10:15:14 [pool-7-thread-45] INFO LogMessageProcessor - Processed 5G TX message from aspect: {"Message":"CAM","MessageId":"38","StationId":
2025-06-19 10:15:14 [pool-7-thread-40] INFO LogMessageProcessor - Processed CV2X TX message from aspect: {"Message":"CAM","MessageId":"38","StationId":
2025-06-19 10:15:14 [pool-7-thread-40] INFO LogMessageProcessor - Processed CV2X RX message from aspect: {"Message":"CAM","MessageId":"1899","StationId":
2025-06-19 10:15:14 [pool-7-thread-40] INFO LogMessageProcessor - Processed 5G RX message from aspect: {"Message":"CAM","MessageId":"1899","StationId":
2025-06-19 10:15:14 [pool-7-thread-40] INFO LogMessageProcessor - Processed CV2X TX message from aspect: {"Message":"CAM","MessageId":"38","StationId":
2025-06-19 10:15:14 [pool-7-thread-45] INFO LogMessageProcessor - Processed 5G TX message from aspect: {"Message":"CAM","MessageId":"38","StationId":

```

Figure 30: Logs from a test scenario involving CVs

CAV automated driving testing

With respect to the CAV (MILLA shuttle), next is the fulfilment of their related functional requirements. It should be noted that it was not possible to test the CAV communicating with the services installed

in the MEC. These are therefore referred to as standalone and other integration tests (see section 3.1.2.2).

- The MILLA shuttle is able of automated driving at SAE Level 4 and has been tested at speeds of up to 50 km/h in urban environments. To this end, preliminary tests in an urban environment were carried out in France by MILLA.
From these tests, message sending and reception were integrated and validated for the three scenarios (requirements PF_UC2_CAV_002, PF_UC2_CAV_005 and PF_UC2_CAV_008). The CAV responded to DENMs, triggering the planned autonomous manoeuvres, primarily for scenarios 2 (rerouting) and 3 (slow down or stop).
- Automated driving tests have not yet taken place at the UC2 test site in Barcelona. This is due to the lack of permits to circulate on Spanish roads, which were still pending at the time this deliverable was prepared.

VRU testing

The functional requirements related to VRU testing consisted of checking the road user's detection by the cameras, their trajectory tracking and the collision risk generation and dissemination. These requirements were tested on July 7th and 8th 2025 once the cameras were successfully installed on the intersection between the Gran Via Avenue and Girona St. as planned, as part of the scenario 3 related trials (3.1.4.5).

The cameras can detect various types of road users, primarily VRUs (such as bicycles, e-scooters and pedestrians), as well as other types of vehicles, including cars, motorbikes, trucks and buses. Next Figure 31 shows the detection and trajectory prediction of several of these types of road users. Each user identification has its own confidence level (from 0 to 1). As can be seen, it is easier for the AI model to detect larger, more visible objects than smaller, more distant ones.

The detection and trajectory prediction of VRUs using camera-based systems faces several constraints that, together, may impact the perception system's overall effectiveness in all situations. One key limitation is the detection distance, since objects farther from the camera appear smaller and less defined, which reduces the accuracy of recognition and tracking algorithms. The relative position and movement of VRUs can also affect detection reliability; for example, if they are walking or cycling sideways or away from the camera. GPS is used for georeferencing, but its precision may be limited in urban environments due to signal reflections or obstructions. Physical installation factors, such as the curvature of lampposts and the height or angle of the cameras, can also create blind spots or misalignments in the field of view. Additionally, the use of fisheye lenses introduces geometric distortions that particularly affect the estimation of object heights and positions. The lack of precise information about the focal aperture at each zoom level further complicates this, making accurate calibration and object size estimation more difficult.

To reduce the impact of these limitations, the following steps have been taken: we have attempted to estimate the focal aperture of the camera at each zoom point, in addition to using other known camera parameters to try to compensate for the fisheye effect; and we are using the heights of the objects visible in the images and assigning them real heights to estimate a depth factor. Requirements PF_UC2-AIC_001, PF_UC2-VRU_004 and PF_UC2-AIC_004 were fulfilled.

Potential collision risks are estimated using predefined spatial polygons to differentiate critical zones: red for vehicle-related areas and blue for VRU-related paths. If a vehicle enters a red polygon at the same time as a VRU enters a blue polygon and their predicted trajectories suggest a potential point of conflict, the system identifies this as a risk situation. This triggers the generation of a DENM, which is

then sent to warn approaching connected vehicles, and a warning to VRUs sent through the App. Requirement PF_UC2-AIC_002 and PF_UC2-AIC_003 were fulfilled; PF_UC2-CRE_001 and PF_UC2-CRE_002 fulfilled with some deviations (see Annex 1 UC2 section 7.1.2.1).

The functional requirements relating to the delivery of warnings to VRUs via the VRU-APP were tested (PF_UC2-VRU_002, PF_UC2-VRU_006), despite the access to the cloud database (Google Firebase service) for positioning VRUs and collision risk events in the VRU-APP which has been integrated and tested in the laboratory but could not be provided in time for the on-road tests in scenario 3 (requirements PF_UC2-VRU_007 to PF_UC2-VRU_009). This is currently being configured and will be reported on in the next deliverable, D5.2. Some other functional requirements (PF_UC2-VRU_003 and PF_UC2-VRU_005) have been modified and properly justified (see Annex 1 UC2 section 7.1.2.1).

Figure 31: Road users' detection inside a predefined area and identification

The RSU’s role is passive but critical for scenario 3, acting as a bridge between the infrastructure platform (Connected vehicle manager) and the vehicles. Functional requirements related to the RSU are primarily involved in the dissemination and reception of V2X messages (CAM and DENM). These requirements (PF_UC2-CVM_001, PF_UC2-CVM_003 and PF_UC2-CVM_004) were successfully tested on 8 July 2025, as part of the scenario 3 related trials (3.1.4.5).

Figure 32 shows a picture of the RSU coverage. The green point represents the location of the RSU installed at the intersection, and the blue line comprises many points representing the locations of vehicles that led to the CAM being sent. These were successfully received by the local processor dedicated to estimating collision risk.

Note that the presence of obstacles (mainly buildings and trees) limits communication between the RSU and the OBU.

Figure 32: RSU coverage

Conversely, when there is an obstruction to the direct line of sight, such as buildings, trees or other structures, wireless signals can be reflected by surfaces such as walls or glass facades. This allows them to reach the receiver via indirect paths and effectively enables the OBU to receive data without a direct connection to the RSU.

3.1.4.2. Non-functional tests

These tests focus on verifying that the system behaves correctly according to its defined UC2 non-functional requirements (see Annex 1). Below are the results from the tests for scenario 3 (3.1.4.5)

carried out on 8th July 2025 at the test site in Barcelona, as well as others in the laboratory (IDIADA premises):

- P_UC2-CAV_001: As shown in Figure 33, the elapsed time between successive GNSS (GPS) samples consistently falls within the 95 to 115 milliseconds range, confirming a stable update rate of approximately 10 Hz. This frequency ensures that even at normal urban driving speeds (50 km/h), the distance between position updates remains well below 1.5 meters, demonstrating reliable and continuous GNSS availability throughout the test.

Figure 33: Elapsed time between successive GNSS samples

- P_UC2-CAV_005: As shown in Figure 34, the transmission rate is centred around 10 CAMs per second, with most values falling between 9 and 12. This confirms that the CAV consistently maintains the required message frequency, with only minimal and acceptable deviations, indicating stable and reliable real-time communication performance.

Figure 34: Distribution of CAM transmission rates

- P_UC2-CAV_006: As shown in Figure 35, most CAM generation times fall between 0 and 5 milliseconds, with around 70% concentrated in that range. This strong performance well below the threshold (100 ms) confirms the system’s ability to generate messages in a timely and reliable manner.

Figure 35: Distribution of CAM Generation Time from GPS location

- P_UC2-CAV_007: the system meets and exceeds the expectation of handling between 1 and 10 messages per second. As shown in Figure 36, during multi-vehicle testing with three Connected Vehicles (at IDIADA premises), the system consistently processed around 10 CAMs per second and even reached 20 CAMs per second when an additional vehicle appeared. This demonstrates the robustness and scalability of the communication system in handling concurrent message traffic without performance degradation.

Figure 36: Message reception rate per second

Non-functional requirements P_UC2_CAV_002, P_UC2_CAV_003, P_UC2_CAV_004, and PNF_UC2-NET_001 to PNF_UC2-NET_003 couldn't be tested so far. These tests are planned from September 2025 and will be reported in deliverable D5.2.

3.1.4.3. Scenario 1 related trials

As stated in 3.1.3.2, the objective is to progressively test and validate the different integrations in scenario 1 that allow emergency vehicles (specifically fire department vehicles in this case) to activate traffic priority corridors in real time. This is achieved using vehicle positioning (CAM messages), Mycelium platform activation and smart traffic light systems (EMEBO), as well as the cooperative manoeuvre with CAVs. To this end, different phases have been planned.

Phase 1 - Development environment (28 November 2024):

The first phase focused on validating the basic communication between the GCOM system and the PoDIUM emergency vehicle prioritization service (EMEBO) in a fully simulated development environment. This involved sending and interpreting simulated CAM messages (vehicle position) as well as testing the assignment and cancellation of corridors. The result was successful in terms of message exchange between the GCOM and PoDIUM services, and the system behaved as expected.

Phase 2 - Real-world test with ADASA vehicle (3 May 2025):

This phase moved testing into a real-world setting using an equipped test vehicle from ADASA (technological provider of the Barcelona’s emergencies management system), though without traffic light prioritization. The corridor was activated from Mycelium system, and vehicle position data was sent and received via CAM messages every 2 seconds while driving along Gran Via (from Plaça Espanya to Plaça Tetuán). These are the results of this test:

- Successful corridor activation and positioning.
- Consistent signal loss detected in the Pau Claris–Roger de Llúria area (around 15–20 sec), possibly due to a signal jammer near Urquinaona National Police Station.
- One technical failure in EMEBO's reception, not linked to coverage, needed to be investigated.

Phase 3 - Real-world test with auxiliary fire vehicle (3 July 2025):

This phase introduced a real fire department vehicle (type MIKE, see 3.1.1.2) and tested additional functionalities, including traffic light prioritization (see Figure 37) via EMEBO. The tests were done on the full corridor (L’Eixample Fire Station to Plaça Tetuán), first without sirens and then, traffic allowing, with sirens active. TLS certificates were used to fulfil IMI's digital security requirements. These are the results of this test:

- Successful activation and positioning. Persistent signal drop at Urquinaona confirmed again.
- Traffic light priority mostly worked but failed at only one intersection between Gran Via and Comte de Borrell St.
- Some misalignments were detected between the corridor model and the vehicle position, particularly near Plaça Espanya and Universitat, which required the model to be adjusted. Figure 38 shows the reception of the EV positioning data, which is sent every two seconds, and the matching process with the corridor model (green line) created to track the EV and help assign green phases at intersections.

Figure 37: Mycelium system showing the fire vehicle with traffic light prioritisation along the corridor.

Figure 38: EV positioning along the corridor

Phase 4 – Real-world test involving a cooperative manoeuvre (planned for September–October 2025):

This upcoming phase will involve cooperative driving between the fire vehicle and a connected vehicle provided by IDIADA. Building upon all previous elements — corridor activation, CAM messaging and traffic signal priority — the test will add a layer of vehicle-to-vehicle coordination. Planned features:

- Involvement of a real emergency vehicle (type MIKE or BRAVO).
- Inclusion of Mycelium activation, CAM messages and EMEBO-based traffic light control.
- Cooperative driving manoeuvre with a connected vehicle.
- Testing conditions and schedule: Pending definition (September–October 2025).

3.1.4.4. Scenario 2 related trials

Scenario 2, which focuses on advanced traffic management, has not yet been tested due to the need for prior data collection to support its functionality. This scenario relies on traffic metrics such as speed, delay and origin-destination patterns (CAMs with OD from vehicles) across road segments to detect incidents along vehicles’ routes and generate relevant traffic messages (DENMs).

The Gran Via area is highly complex, with dense and varied traffic (buses, taxis, private vehicles, motorbikes, etc.), so a broader data collection effort is required to produce reliable, statistically meaningful insights.

It is important to note that all technical developments for Scenario 2 have been completed, including full integration with the existing TMS. What remains is the collection and analysis of the necessary traffic data to feed the TMS. However, efforts have so far been prioritised on preparing for and executing scenarios 1 and 3, which were more immediately feasible. Scenario 2 is fully prepared from

Figure 40: VRUs location at risk of collision which prompted DENM to send

Figure 41: DENMs were shown in the HMI

3.2. Use Case 3

In this chapter we describe the Use case 3 related activities of the Spanish LL.

Use case 3 will demonstrate a **real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean cross-border corridor**. The aim is to ensure smooth and safe traffic management, while enabling interoperability and validating new PDI functionalities, by leveraging and merging data from connected and automated vehicles, traffic cameras and third-party providers.

As a brief reminder, Use Case 3 explores two scenarios:

- **Scenario 1: Daily commuting service supported by traffic management.**
- **Scenario 2: Safety incidents across borders mitigated through a continuous, efficient, and resilient service.**

As per the LL change agreed with the EC, both scenarios will be tested on the C32 highway, near Barcelona (Castelldefels wider area), emulating cross-border conditions.

In the following chapters we will describe:

- e) the LL testbed, including the deployment of new and/or adaptation of existing equipment of the LL and the preparation of the test vehicles and other test facilities
- f) the integration of the WP3 PDI innovations in the LL testbed, and validation
- g) the testing methodologies, data loggers, and test plan
- h) the pre-demo testing activities relevant for this UC, in line with the checklist of Functional and Non-Functional requirements as described in D2.2 [1]

A checklist for the LL preparation and integration validation is also provided in the Annex.

3.2.1. LL description

3.2.1.1. Description of the LL infrastructure (existing and newly installed)

MEC

The common MEC setup for UC2 and UC3 is described in UC2, see 3.1.2.1.

Two private 5G networks emulating a cross-border roaming situation

The project has deployed two private 5G networks to facilitate the cross-border scenario. The operators utilize three gNBs provided by +Orange and two 5G core networks. The North operator consists of a single gNB, referred to as the North gNB, to provide PLMN2 or “France” as shown in Figure 42. The South operator comprises two gNBs, named Centre gNB and South gNB, to provide PLMN1 or “Spain”. This configuration ensures coverage of the testbed highway, spanning from the northern to the southern endpoint.

To connect vehicles to these 5G networks, two different models of 5G modems are used, the Quectel’s RM500QGL and RM520N, both mounted in RMU500EK 5G Development Kits (Figure 43). The SIM cards are installed in these 5G modems, which are connected to their respective onboard computers by USB cables. In this setup, the South operator serves as the Home Operator, while the North operator functions as the Visiting or Roaming Operator.

Figure 42: Situation of 5G gNBs and RSUs.

Figure 43: On-board modem: RMU500EK 5G development kit with RM500QGL or RM520N 5G modules

A key challenge in this setup is the service interruption zone at the border between the two operators, caused by the time required for roaming negotiation. To mitigate this, Roadside Units (RSUs) provide coverage in the affected area. If any gaps in service remain, the PDI system must be resilient enough to prevent critical failures.

Figure 44: RSU with autonomous renewable energy supply on the C32 highway

C-V2X Roadside Units (RSUs)

The project has deployed three RSUs in areas where roaming between the two 5G operators causes service disruptions. Additionally, a fourth RSU will be mounted on a vehicle (mobile RSU), allowing for flexible deployment at specific locations for ad hoc testing.

The RSUs are Cohda MK6 models, connected to Internet via their cellular interfaces and utilizing public cellular networks. They are installed on poles (Figure 44) alongside the C32 highway at the locations marked in Figure 42.

RSU-1 and RSU-2 are strategically positioned to provide C-V2X coverage for southbound traffic, ensuring connectivity as vehicles transition to the South operator's network during the roaming process. Similarly, RSU-3 is deployed to support northbound traffic under the same conditions, maintaining seamless coverage during the network roaming.

The following table shows the main configuration parameters of these three RSUs.

Table 3: C-V2X configuration parameters of the RSUs

C-V2X parameter	Value
Channel number	184
Channel frequency range	5915 MHz – 5925 MHz
Channel bandwidth	10 MHz
Transmission power	23 dBm
Side Link bandwidth	50 RBs
Subchannel size	10 RBs
Number of subchannels	5
Minimum MCS	0
Maximum MCS	8
Synchronization type	GNSS
PSCCH-PSSCH Adjacency	Adjacent

Roadside traffic sensors (AI traffic cameras)

Four PCs have been deployed for real-time traffic analysis on four traffic cameras on the C-32 (one of which has been installed specifically for PoDIUM). The processed information is transmitted to the corresponding Autopistas' Mobility Hub hosted on the PoDIUM Platform (MEC ES1, MEC ES2, or MEC FR, depending on the geographical area they correspond to) using PoDIUM's 5G communications network.

- PK51 – direction south towards Tarragona
- PK49.5 – direction north towards Barcelona (Figure 47)
- PK46.5 – direction north towards Tarragona
- PK42 – direction north towards Barcelona

Figure 45: AI Traffic PC connected to PoDIUM PDI

Figure 46: Visualisation of the AI traffic cameras capturing & identifying bypassing vehicles on C-32

Figure 47: A traffic camera installed on a pole with self-sufficient power supply in the C32 highway (PK49.5)

The locations of the connected cameras are shown in Figure 48 below:

Figure 48: Location of AI Traffic cameras on the C32 highway

3.2.1.2. Vehicles description

- **MILLA's CAV shuttle**
- **IDIADA's CV**

For the description of the above two vehicles, please refer to UC2 section 3.1.1.2, as they are common for UC2 and UC3.

- **AAE's 2 CVs**

The communication equipment of the CVs consists of a laptop that runs all processes, connected to a Cohda MK6 OBU configured with the same parameters as the RSUs (Table 3). Additionally, each vehicle is equipped with an HMI tablet, a 5G modem—one using a Quectel RM500QGL and the other an RM520N—both mounted on RMU500EK 5G Development Kits, each with external antennas, one by Taoglass (Figure 50), and the other one by Abracon. The complete setup is illustrated below.

Figure 49: Equipment mounted in a CV: PC, Modem, RSU and DC-AC converter.

Figure 50: Taoglass antennas on top of the CV.

3.2.1.3. Other test facilities

VRUs

VRUs are pedestrians equipped with a mid-range Android smartphone with the PoDIUM’s Safety App.

AAE’s Operations & Road Safety Centre (C32 highway)

The Autopistas Operations and Road Safety Center, located on the C-32 highway in Garraf (Barcelona), serves as a state-of-the-art hub for testing innovative mobility and road safety solutions. As the headquarters of AAE’ Future Road Lab, it provides a real-world testing environment for advanced technologies, including AI-powered video analytics and connected vehicle systems. Equipped with a central control system and a wide array of sensors across more than 500 km of managed roads, the

center enables real-time monitoring and rapid incident response. Its role in the PoDIUM project highlights its strategic importance as a living lab for connected and automated mobility. The Centre will be a potential location for the VRU safety app demo trials.

Figure 51: Autopistas Operations and Road Safety Center

3.2.2. PoDIUM PDI innovations' integration & validation

3.2.2.1. PDI internal integrations

Figure 52: Overview of the final implementation of the PoDIUM platform (MEC) and its integrations

- **Edge platforms (MEC):** Three MEC instances have been deployed, each responsible for managing a specific sector of the testbed:
 - MEC-FR controls the north-east sector, located in the French segment.
 - MEC-ES1 manages the central sector, located within the Spanish segment of the testbed.
 - MEC-ES2 is assigned to the south-west sector of the Spanish part.

- **Gateways:** Three gateways have been deployed, one per MEC instance. Each gateway is responsible for coordinating the transmission of ITS messages from the communication networks to both the LDM and the TMC.
 - The gateway in MEC-ES1 is connected to the South gNB, operated by the southern (Spanish) operator (see Figure 42).
 - The gateway in MEC-ES2 interfaces with the Centre gNB, also managed by the southern operator, and is additionally connected to RSU-1 and RSU-2.
 - The gateway in MEC-FR is connected to the North gNB, operated by the northern (French) operator, and is additionally connected to RSU-3.
- **LDMs:** Three LDMs have been deployed, one per MEC instance. Each LDM maintains information about the vehicles operating within the communication network managed by its corresponding MEC. Vehicles are removed from the LDM database if no updates are received for a duration of 3 seconds. For deployment simplicity, the modules “Intelligent LDM Updater” and “Optimised Awareness Distributor” have been integrated into the LDM module. These components operate as a unified system within each LDM instance.
- **VRU modules:** Three VRU modules have been deployed, one on each MEC instance. These modules interface with their respective LDMs to evaluate potential collision risks between vehicles and VRUs. When a risk is detected, the VRU module issues alert messages to both the VRU and the vehicle via the corresponding gateway.
- **TMC modules:** Three modules of the Traffic Management Centre (TMC) have been deployed, one on each MEC instance. The modules calculate the traffic status and generate alerts and traffic strategies in their respective assigned section of the highway. As input, they communicate with the respective LDMs and Hubs. Their output is handled by the respective gateways.
- **Edge Mobility Hub modules:** Similarly to the above, each MEC has its own dedicated Hub module, which handles the processed VA traffic data received from the AI cameras and publishes them on an MQTT server, then used by the TMC. Some of the Hubs handle the data from more than one camera, as per their physical locations on the highway.

The following internal **MEC interfaces** were successfully validated and demonstrated reliable performance during the integration tests:

- Gateway – LDM
- Gateway – TMC
- TMC – LDM
- VRU – LDM
- VRU – Gateway
- TMC-Hub for receiving processed VA data.
- Internal TMC interfaces:
 - Global TMC-Local TMC (cross-sections within the same country)
 - Global TMCs between each other (cross-border)
 - Connection of TMC to INRIX for floating car data acquisition.

The following **C-ITS messages** were successfully transmitted and received between the gateway and vehicles during the integration tests: CAM, DENM, IVIM, MCM and CPM.

ENIDE-MILLA Cloud integrations

- **Integration of Shuttle Passenger App (ENIDE) with Shuttle System (MILLA):** The integration connects the Shuttle Passenger App (developed by ENIDE) to the Shuttle Fleet Management System (developed by MILLA). This was achieved through the development and implementation of a **Route Scheduler**, which serves as the intermediary between the Passenger App and the Fleet Management System.
 - The **Route Scheduler** is responsible for organizing the travel plan, including route and timing. It sends the planned schedule to the Fleet Management System and receives real-time updates during the journey. Specifically, it requests the Shuttle Fleet Management System to operate at specific times and locations and monitors its responses throughout the trip.
 - The **Passenger App** communicates with the backend system, which interacts with the Route Scheduler. The Scheduler, in turn, makes the appropriate API calls to the Fleet Management System.
 - All communication is secured via the **MILLA VPN**, ensuring a protected data exchange channel.
 - The development, integration, and testing of the Route Scheduler–Fleet Management API were successfully completed. Testing was carried out and validated in the MILLA shuttle lab environment in France.

3.2.2.2. Vehicle-related integrations

On-board hardware and software integration into the vehicles: Two types of vehicles are used in the testbed:

- Milla shuttle, an autonomous driving (AD) vehicle.
- Three conventional vehicles with standard driving capabilities but with V2X communication capabilities. In this case, the vehicles are outfitted with a laptop that serves as the onboard computing unit. This laptop is connected to the 5G modem via USB, enabling cellular communication, and connected to the OBU via Ethernet, facilitating V2X messaging. The equipment configuration was shown in Figure 43.

Integration tests performed in conventional vehicles with V2X communication capabilities:

The integration of V2X communications within the onboard computing platform involves the deployment of an in-vehicle gateway capable of interfacing with both the 5G modem and the C-V2X OBU. This gateway is configured to simultaneously transmit messages over both interfaces:

- Via 5G, to forward information to the MEC.
- Via C-V2X, to broadcast information to neighbouring vehicles and RSUs, which subsequently forward this data to the MEC.

C-V2X OBU Integration: The integration of the C-V2X OBU was performed by configuring its radio parameters to match those of the RSUs. Bidirectional communication (uplink and downlink) was verified to ensure proper interoperability.

The 5G modem integration focused on validating:

- Connectivity with both mobile network operators (France and Spain).
- The ability to perform inter-PLMN handovers between operators.
- End-to-end Internet connectivity for communication with the respective MEC instances.

Observed Connectivity Issues with 5G Networks:

It is important to highlight that intermittent connectivity issues with the 5G modems have been observed throughout the integration and testing phases. While roaming procedures between operators generally function as expected, there are cases where:

- Roaming takes significantly longer than usual, or
- Connectivity fails altogether, requiring a manual modem reset, or even a core reset after notifying the technical team of the 5G core management.

These issues occur sporadically and without a clearly identifiable root cause.

We attribute these instabilities to the experimental nature of the 5G networks used in the testbed, which are based on non-commercial cores implemented using the open-source Open5GS framework. While functional for prototyping purposes, this setup occasionally leads to unexpected behaviour.

It is also important to note that no Service-Level Agreements (SLAs) were established for these networks. Therefore, while the problem is acknowledged, no direct resolution is currently feasible within the scope of the project.

MEC Selection Logic: The in-vehicle gateway determines which MEC to connect to, based on the IP address range assigned by the mobile operator:

- In the French sector, the in-vehicle gateway connects to the French MEC using a pre-configured IP address.
- In the Spanish sector, which includes two distinct areas (MEC-ES1 and MEC-ES2), the in-vehicle gateway uses geofencing to determine its location and connects to the appropriate MEC accordingly, also using pre-configured IP addresses.

System Validation: All network pathways across the two operators, including the three geographic zones and their associated MECs and RSUs, have been successfully validated. C-ITS messages were observed to be correctly routed to their intended destinations under all configurations. Specifically:

- RSU-1 and RSU-2 are connected to MEC-ES1 (Spain, central region).
- RSU-3 is connected to the French MEC.

MEC-side gateway, in-vehicle gateway and HMI Integration: The integration between the in-vehicle gateway and the MEC-side gateway was verified. All message types were correctly exchanged in both communication directions across all network interfaces.

Additionally, the connection between the in-vehicle gateway and the HMI was tested. All received C-ITS messages were accurately displayed on the HMI.

Integration tests performed in Milla vehicle (MILLA): pending finalization

For MILLA integrations, please refer to UC2, section 3.1.2.2.

OBU integration: Considering the delay in obtaining the DGT permits, the shuttle was shipped back to France. In line with the extension of the project, the integration validation of the OBU in the MILLA shuttle will be finalized in September 2025, once the vehicle returns to Spain. It will be reported in D5.2.

Next, a **summary list** of performed checks:

- C-V2X OBU – Laptop: The C-V2X OBU is bidirectionally exchanging information with the vehicle PC. The integration tests for this connection comprise:

ID	Description
OBU_PC_1	The OBU forwards all received C-V2X messages (CAM, DENM, IVIM, CPM, MCM and MAPEM) to the vehicle laptop

OBU_PC_2	The vehicle laptop forwards all messages to be transmitted (CAM, DENM and CPM) to the OBU
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- PC - 5G MODEM: The vehicle PC is communicating with the MEC services bidirectionally using a 5G modem. The integration tests for this connection comprise:

ID	Description
PC_MOD_1	The vehicle laptop sends all messages to be transmitted (CAM, DENM and CPM) to the MEC using the 5G modem
PC_MOD_2	The vehicle PC receives all messages transmitted by the MEC (CAM, DENM, IVIM, CPM, MCM and MAPEM) using the 5G modem

- PC - MILLA PC (pending final re-check)
The vehicle PC (stack OBU stack) is bidirectionally communicating with the internal MILLA PC (running the AD functions). This was tested in France. A final re-validation will be performed in Barcelona once the vehicle returns (Sep 2025), as preparation for the final demo, and reported in D5.2. The integration tests for this connection comprise:

ID	Description
PC_MILLA_1	The vehicle PC sends all relevant messages received by 5G or C-V2X to the MILLA PC.
PC_MILLA_2	The vehicle PC receives all messages (status, health, behave and global_path) generated from the MILLA PC.

- MEC – CV/CAV interface (OBU): The vehicle laptop is exchanging C-ITS messages with the MEC services (Gateway). The integration tests for this connection comprise:

ID	Description
MEC_CAV_1	All the messages generated by the Gateway service in the MEC (CAM, DENM, IVIM, CPM, MCM and MAPEM) are received and properly interpreted by the vehicle laptop
MEC_CAV_2	All the messages generated by the vehicle (CAM, DENM and CPM) reach the MEC (Gateway) and are properly interpreted

- V2V connection-I2CAT: Messages created in one vehicle are correctly received by other vehicles using their OBUs.

ID	Description
CV_CV	All messages generated by the ITS services in one vehicle (CAM) are received by other vehicles using their OBUs, and interpreted by the receiving gateway

3.2.2.3. Roadside entities integrations

5G connection validation: Several trips have been done using CVs and measuring coverage, received power and delays from the vehicle to the MEC. The following figures show a representative sample of the results.

Figure 53: 5G coverage, driving South, and with Taoglass antennas (figures indicate the operator’s identifier).

Figure 54: 5G coverage, driving North, and with Taoglass antennas (figures indicate the operator’s identifier).

Figure 55: 5G coverage, driving South, and with Abracon antennas (figures indicate the operator’s identifier).

Figure 56: 5G coverage, driving North, and with Abracon antennas (figures indicate the operator’s identifier).

Figure 57: 5G received power signal with Taoglass antennas (figures are measured in dBm). Colors represent the different gNB's sectors to which the vehicle was connected.

Figure 58: 5G Round Trip Time from vehicle to the MEC and back with Taoglass antennas (figures are measured in ms).

RSU to CVs and MEC interconnection (C-V2X): Multiple test runs have been conducted using Connected Vehicles (CVs) to evaluate the coverage area of the deployed RSUs. Figure 59 (RSU-1), Figure 60 (RSU-2) and Figure 61 (RSU-3) present a representative sample of the measurements collected during these trips of the three RSUs.

The results indicate that coverage is significantly influenced by Line-of-Sight (LoS) conditions. In particular, RSU-1 is deployed in a small valley along the highway, which leads to limited coverage on its western side, where LoS is obstructed.

Figure 59: RSU-1 coverage with Taoglass antennas

Figure 60: RSU-2 coverage with Taoglass antennas

Figure 61: RSU-3 coverage with Taoglass antennas

3.2.2.4. VRU related integrations

- **VRU safety app**

This application involves a VRU equipped with a smartphone running the PoDIUM Safety App, and the corresponding VRU module deployed in the MEC. The validation process was carried out according to the following steps:

- The VRU Safety App periodically transmits the user's location using VAMs, via its own cellular network operator.
- These messages are received by the gateway in the MEC, and the VRU's position is stored in the LDM alongside real-time vehicle location data for the same area.
- Verification was performed to ensure that all location data was correctly received and registered in the LDM.
- The VRU module within the MEC continuously monitors the spatial relationship between VRUs and vehicles, assessing the risk of potential collisions.
- Upon detecting a high-risk situation, the module generates a DENM alert, which is transmitted to both the vehicle and the VRU involved.
- Final checks confirmed that the alert messages were successfully received by both actors and that the corresponding alerts were displayed on their respective HMIs.

- **Shuttle Passenger App**

- The Passenger App and Shuttle Service have been successfully integrated and tested in a lab environment.
- App is available in Android's Google Play Beta Testing, under user invitation.
- It uses VPN-secured communication to ensure data protection.
- Regarding the demonstration activities, the main scenario currently under consideration is the C32 route and its designated stops. However, an additional scenario involving the

urban area of Barcelona (UC2) is also being explored, resembling the route characteristics of in-town stops of the initial cross-border use case (Le Boulou-La Junquera).

- A final decision on the demonstration scenario will be made from September, once the detailed implementation plans for both UC2 and UC3 are finalized.

3.2.3. Pre-demo testing methodology

3.2.3.1. Pre-test conditions

Based on the deployment milestones identified in D4.1 [2], the following pre-test conditions must be met before the test.

Table 4: Pre-test conditions for UC 3

Pre-test condition	Fulfilled	Comments
MEC deployed, operational and connected to internet (incl. TMC, GW, LDM modules)	Yes	
OBU-stack deployed in lab settings and connected to MEC	Yes	
OBU hardware and OBU-stack set up in vehicles (e.g. IDIADA)	Yes	
Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials	Partial	Pending as of 3 July: Milla CAV - RED plates and AD - Permissions (DGT) and in 2 nd step the Servei Catala de Transit (SCT) permissions for highway tests. For CVs, we do not require permissions.
Platform connected end-to-end with all interfaces (MEC), capable of emitting traffic strategies to the vehicles	Yes	
The RSUs are installed on the highway, operational and connected to the MEC	Yes	
Two 5G networks are available, one for each side of the border	Yes	Minor: Intermittent connectivity issues between the 5G modems and networks.
CAV is fully operational in SAE4 (pre-approved)	Yes	Tested in circuit, to be checked in highway
Highway permits for CAV circulation obtained	Not yet	Pending as of 3 July: Milla CAV - RED plates and AD - Permissions (DGT) and in 2 nd step the SCT permissions for highway tests.
There are in total 4 vehicle available, with their respective drivers	Yes	2 vehicles already available, 2 vehicles to be leased by AAE.
CVs and CAV fully equipped with OBUs and HMIs (tablets/laptops), and connected to internet and C-V2X	Yes	Two sets tested. The other two sets need to be tested on the final vehicles, but they are replicas of the former ones

3.2.3.2. Description of pre-demo testing methodologies, plans and tools

Storyboard: The storyboard for both Scenarios remains the same as presented in deliverable D2.1 [10].

Test cases:

Scenario 1: On-demand shuttle service demonstration (MILLA Shuttle)

1. **ENIDE’s passenger app:** the On-demand Service booking will be the first step in this scenario. This allows passengers to reserve a seat on a designated route.
2. **On-demand service scheduling:** The interconnection between the ENIDE app/cloud and MILLA cloud/MILLA supervision centre allows the shuttle to initiate its route automatically when the booking service indicates so.
3. **Autonomous driving operation on highway**
 1. AD Driving up to 80km/h with safety driver on-board
 2. Entering/exiting the highway (can be in manual mode) to reach the defined shuttle stops
 3. Connected to the PoDIUM Platform (emitting CAM messages)
4. **VRU safety app:** VRU safety is demonstrated by monitoring VRU position via mobile and sending a risk collision alert to the VRUs. This trial will take place outside the highway, in a closed, low speed, protected area, where the shuttle is designated to make stops along the route, e.g. at Petrocat gas station or Autopistas Road Safety Centre. The demo will take place first in manual mode, and if feasible also in AD mode.

Scenario 2: Connectivity & Traffic management (safety related)

1. **Autonomous driving operation on highway (at 80km/h)**
 1. AD Driving up to 80km/h
 2. Entering/exiting the highway (can be in manual mode) to reach the defined shuttle stops
 3. Emitting CAM messages to the Platform
2. **An incident** (generated virtually on the MEC, resembling a stopped vehicle) ahead on the road is flagged as a hazard and leads to a blocked lane. This requires alerting approaching vehicles (CVs & the CAV Shuttle), taking pre-emptive safety measures while approaching, as well as manoeuvring around and away from the area of the incident. The CAV shuttle handles the manoeuvres on AD mode and is supported by the Tele-supervision.
 1. AD Driving up to 80km/h
 2. Receiving an incident alert (DENM)
 3. Receiving a IVIM (new speed limit) and reducing speed to 60km/h in AD mode
 4. Receiving a MCM and increasing distance from the vehicle in front.
 5. Transferring the CAV shuttle supervision to Tele-operator before approaching the virtual incident marker.
 6. Continue driving after passing by the virtual incident marker.
3. **Safety-related issues self-reported by the shuttle** during its journey. The shuttle moves to an emergency slow down and stop and it’s flagged as a “hazard” by the TMC. Approaching CVs are notified, and the traffic strategies are modified.
 1. AD Driving up to 80km/h
 2. Transferring the CAV shuttle supervision to the Telesupervisor (while the safety driver is on stand-by).
 3. Safely slowing down gradually in AD mode and stopping on the emergency lane.
 4. Emitting a DENM alert

3.2.3.3. Data logging setup and data storage

In UC3, various data streams are collected to support the validation and evaluation of individual components as well as the overall system performance. The data collection and storage procedures fully align with the specifications outlined in Deliverable D4.1 [2], with no modifications made to the original plan.

However, it should be noted that data generated during pre-demo testing phases will not be made publicly available.

3.2.4. Report of pre-demo testing activities

The following in-field tests were primarily conducted by i2CAT, IDIADA, and AAE, using CVs in manual driving and equipped with the complete OBU stack, with the main objective of validating the functional aspects of the use case:

- **Between 27 November 2024 and 24 March 2025**, i2CAT, UPC, and AAE conducted a coordinated series of integration and validation tests to ensure the proper deployment and configuration of the equipment required for connectivity through both 5G networks and C-V2X, operating via the three gNBs and the three RSUs. During this period, close collaboration with the University of Murcia and +Orange enabled the resolution of various issues related to connectivity, Internet access, and coverage. Additionally, software debugging activities were performed on the modems used. These sessions led to the successful validation of modem connectivity to the mobile network and Internet reachability, as well as the operational communication between the RSUs and the OBUs. Driving tests were conducted multiple times along the highway and nearby areas to evaluate network coverage and roaming behaviour between operators. The exchange of CAM messages between the MEC and the vehicle was validated in both directions. Furthermore, coverage measurements were carried out using Taoglass and Abracon antennas. As a result, the modems consistently established reliable connections to the +Orange network. The three gNBs were confirmed to be fully operational, supporting two distinct cellular operators. Communication between RSUs and OBUs functioned as expected. Minor differences in coverage were observed depending on the antenna manufacturer.
- **15 May 2025**: i2CAT, UPC, IDIADA, and AAE conducted a comprehensive integration test to validate the operativity of both vehicles' equipment, test the uplink CAM transmission to the MEC, and verify the roaming between operators. Functional modules including client-side gateways, MEC gateways, and the LDM with its HMI were successfully validated. Geofencing between Spanish 1 and Spanish 2 regions was tested and confirmed. Despite these achievements, the session was marked by problems with network connectivity. Only the "French" mobile operator was operational initially, requiring support from Murcia. Some SIM cards failed to connect, and roaming transitions, while functional, were very slow. RM500Q modems performed correctly.
- **23 May 2025**: i2CAT, IDIADA, and AAE continued the integration and validation activities to check the full operativity of both vehicles' equipment, ensure correct uplink CAM transmission to the MEC, and verify the switch of V2X gateways between North and South operators. Additional objectives included confirming RSU-1 and RSU-2 coverage and functionality, as well as software debugging. Network issues at the start of the session limited effective testing time. However, alerts generated from the TMC were validated for the first time. V2V communication was confirmed, while V2I connectivity remained inconsistent, with downlink problems observed in some networks. The uplink CAM exchange and the operation of the South gateway and LDM were successfully validated.
- **29 May 2025**: i2CAT, IDIADA, and AAE continued the testing activities to validate alert transmission, modem performance, and the overall integration of the system. Despite minor issues with modems and alert reception during the morning, i2CAT successfully received alerts

later in the day, confirming the proper operation of the system components. The RSUs, previously problematic, were monitored for the first time using Grafana. RM500Q modems struggled significantly with connectivity and handover, while Teltonika modems showed more reliable performance and were considered a viable alternative. However, some alerts from i2CAT’s MEC gateway were still not received. Partners identified further actions, including improvements to modem configurations, ensuring proper alert routing between gateways, and automating the deployment of client modules.

- 05 June 2025:** Prior to this session, several technical improvements were made: i2CAT enabled compatibility with Teltonika modems, IDIADA provided an API to support their integration, Grafana was extended to monitor client-side modules, and the LDM HMI was updated to display alerts and traffic strategies for debugging. The field test began with typical 5G connectivity issues but progressed positively. All functional modules operated as expected, and previously observed issues were successfully resolved. Traffic strategies were generated correctly in response to virtual incidents, though manoeuvre recommendations and alerts did not initially reach the OBUs, likely due to the TMC–GW interface. Corrective actions were agreed upon.
- 19 June 2025:** The main objective of this session was to perform an end-to-end trial demonstrating all the functionalities of the UC3 demo components (Autopistas, IDIADA, i2CAT) and to gather additional performance metrics for D4.2, covering the non-functional requirements. The TMC–GW connection was validated as operational, and strategies were received by the vehicles’ OBUs. However, Teltonika modems—which had shown promise—began to present connectivity issues, prompting i2CAT to revert to RM500Q modems, which functioned reliably. An issue with i2CAT’s client-side gateway caused alerts to be continuously repeated on the IDIADA driver’s HMI due to a lack of message filtering. The collected metrics did not meet performance expectations and are not suitable for inclusion in project deliverables. It was agreed that harmonisation of the client GW and OBU-PC interface is needed, with implementation fixes planned for July and pre-demo trials to resume in September. All other system integrations were considered validated.

3.2.4.1. Functional tests

All functional components of the PoDIUM system required to realize UC3 were tested according to the requirements definition in D2.2 [1]. Our implementation fulfilled the grand majority requirements, albeit with some modifications from the original scope. The detailed checklist of the requirements is summarized in Annex 1.

MEC testing

Responsible: AAE, I2CAT, IDIADA

- Most MEC-related requirements were fulfilled, with some implemented via architectural changes (PF_UC3-MEC_002 to PF_UC3-MEC_005, PF_UC3-MEC_013, PF_UC3-MEC_021 to PF_UC3-MEC_023).
- The Mobility Hub Edge is used only to transmit video analytics (VA) data; other components like the TMC, LDM, and Digital Twin run directly on the MEC (PF_UC3-MEC_002 to MEC_004).
- The VA module runs on roadside PCs, not on the MEC, and only transmits processed results to the MEC (PF_UC3-MEC_005).
- Communication between the TMC and other MEC components (e.g. LDM, Gateways) is implemented via REST APIs, diverging from the original Hub Edge concept (PF_UC3-MEC_021).

- The Gateways feed the LDM directly and are used to send information to road users, bypassing the Mobility Hub Edge (PF_UC3-MEC_022, PF_UC3-MEC_023).

Specifically for the Traffic Management Centre (TMC)

The TMC modules are responsible for managing the strategies in three different sectors: FR, ES1 and ES2. Each sector has two directions, therefore there are **six scenarios** in the testbed, as shown in the screenshots of the TMC strategies visualizer below. As a highlight, cross-border (between FR and ES1) and cross-section (between ES1 and ES2) strategies have been tested to verify the communication between different TMC Global and within one TMC Global with two TMC Edge.

Scenario 1 – Road hazard in FR, direction west:

Figure 62: Traffic strategy when a road hazard is found in FR, direction west

Scenario 2 – Road hazard in FR, direction east with cross-border strategy in ES1:

Figure 63: Traffic strategy when a road hazard is found in FR, direction east, with cross-border

Scenario 3 – Road hazard in ES1, direction west with cross-border strategy in FR:

Figure 64: Traffic strategy when a road hazard is found in ES1, direction west, with cross-border

Scenario 4 – Road hazard in ES1, direction east with cross-section strategy in ES2:

Figure 65: Traffic strategy when a road hazard is found in ES1, direction east, with cross-section

Scenario 5 – Road hazard in ES2, direction west with cross-section strategy in ES1:

Figure 66: Traffic strategy when a road hazard is found in ES2, direction west, with cross-section

Scenario 6 – Road hazard in ES2, direction east:

Figure 67: Traffic strategy when a road hazard is found in ES2, direction east

The majority of the functional requirements tested and validated during testing. The general overview of the test conclusions in relation to the initial functional requirements is explained in the following sections.

CLOUD testing

Responsible: AAE, ENIDE, MILLA

- Architectural modifications: The Mobility Hub Cloud is used only to provide INRIX third-party traffic data to the TMC. It no longer acts as a data broker between the MEC and the Cloud TMC. Instead, the original data exchange architecture was replaced by a direct interface between the Local TMC (Edge) and the Global TMC (Cloud). (PF_UC3-CLOUD_001, PF_UC3-MEC_013)
- Mobility Hub Cloud Platform modules such as the data repository, management module, and gateway were not implemented due to architectural redesign. These components were deemed unnecessary in the final system implementation. (PF_UC3-CLOUD_002)
- TMC Edge ↔ TMC Global orchestration logic was successfully validated. Each TMC Edge collects local data and generates preliminary strategies. These are sent to the TMC Global, which evaluates whether a cross-section or cross-border strategy is required. If a cross-section strategy is selected, the TMC Global overrides the local strategies and instructs all involved TMC Edge modules accordingly. For cross-border coordination, the originating TMC Global shares only the necessary data with the neighbouring TMC Global, which then computes its own strategy. This approach ensures decentralised computation while maintaining coordinated control. (PF_UC3-CLOUD_003, PF_UC3-CLOUD_004). The TMC relationship model is depicted in Figure 68.
- The Remote Shuttle Supervision Service (MILLA) does not directly interface with the Mobility Hub or TMC as initially planned. Instead, it exchanges trip-related information via the ENIDE Cloud. (PF_UC3-CLOUD_007)

Figure 68: TMC relationship model

CV testing

Responsible: I2CAT & IDIADA

Focus: CV interconnection and driver’s response to PDI recommendations

- 3 “Onboard V2X-PC stacks” were configured and tested successfully by i2CAT.
- The IDIADA vehicle is a connected vehicle (CV) without automated driving functions (PF_UC3-CAV_004b, PF_UC3-CAV_005b).
- IDIADA’s processing unit consists of a laptop connected to the OBU and HMI, but not directly integrated with the internal vehicle systems (PF_UC3-CAV_010).
- An HMI device (tablet) is available in the IDIADA vehicle and displays traffic and manoeuvre recommendations to the driver (PF_UC3-CAV_011).
- During field tests, the IDIADA OBU was initially forwarding all received MEC messages to the HMI without filtering, resulting in repetitive alerts. This will be later addressed through interface harmonisation between IDIADA and i2CAT (related to PF_UC3-CAV_010/011).

In the figure below, we can see a Screenshot of the CV’s HMI (tablet) screen. It is showing a vehicle moving along the road while displaying the received traffic manoeuvre recommendations (speed limit, distance from vehicle in front, lane 2 closed) and alert of an upcoming incident up ahead.

Figure 69: Screenshot of the CV's HMI (tablet) screen, with manoeuvre recommendations and incident alert

CAV automated driving testing

This section **applies only to the MILLA CAV shuttle**. The IDIADA vehicle does not have automated driving capabilities and served only as a connected vehicle (PF_UC3-CAV_004b).

High-speed AD Testing on the Highway

- The MILLA shuttle is capable of automated driving at SAE Level 4, tested up to 80 km/h on highway segments. High-speed automated driving tests did not yet take place in Spain (C32 highway). Preliminary tests for highway driving up to 80km/h were carried out in France by MILLA (PF_UC3-CAV_004).
- The IDIADA vehicle does not have automated driving capabilities and served only as a connected vehicle (PF_UC3-CAV_004b).

Automated Manoeuvres Testing as Response to PDI Instructions

- Testing only took place in a limited scope in France, since the shuttle could not circulate yet in Spain due to the lack of the special matriculation plates, to be issued by the DGT.
- The MILLA shuttle successfully responded to infrastructure-triggered speed limit and following distance modifications (PF_UC3-CAV_005). Automated lane changes will not take place on the highway, due to safety limitations.
- All the above AD tests including emergency stops, and interaction with VRUs will take place upon return of the shuttle in Spain, from September onwards, conditional on obtaining the AD permits from the DGT.

Cross-border relevant interconnections as applicable for the C-32 highway LL environment

- As per the local logic (LL) configuration, the MILLA shuttle maintains seamless internet connectivity through a public 5G network SIM card (PF_UC3-CAV_012).
- A fallback C-V2X communication channel between the MILLA Cloud and the shuttle, originally envisioned, was not implemented due to infrastructure constraints (PF_UC3-CAV_015).

- Direct emergency notifications from infrastructure to the service owner were also not implemented, as real-time geolocation monitoring by the Fleet Manager through the MILLA platform was deemed sufficient (PF_UC3-CAV_014).

VRU testing

Responsible: I2CAT

- The VRU app transmitted VAM messages and received CAM, DENM, and CPM messages, although only DENM was used to alert in case of high collision risk (PF_UC3-VRU_002, PF_UC3-VRU_003).
- The MEC processed collision risk and issued alerts accordingly, instead of broadcasting all CAMs/CPMs to the VRU app. This deviation did not affect use case outcomes (PF_UC3-VRU_003).
- The app triggered safety alarms (through DENMs) based on proximity to detected vehicles
- The Shuttle on-demand service passenger app (developed by ENIDE) was completed in beta mode. It supports passenger functions such as registration, fast check-in, trip tracking, and logistics (PF_UC3-VRU_004 to PF_UC3-VRU_009).

RSU testing

Responsible: I2CAT

- Three fixed RSUs and one mobile RSU were deployed, covering both directions and all lanes of the Spanish test section (PF_UC3-RSU_003).
- 5G coverage is provided via a private +Orange network, and the detected coverage gaps were supplemented with C-V2X (PF_UC3-RSU_001).
- RSUs were monitored through Grafana in the final test iterations, supporting debugging and coverage validation.

3.2.4.2. Non-functional tests

All non-functional components of the PoDIUM system are necessary for the realization of UC3 were tested in accordance with the requirements defined in D2.2 [1]. The main outcomes are summarized below, while the complete list of non-functional requirements can be found in Annex 1.

- P_UC3-CAV_001: GNSS signal remained uninterrupted throughout the testbed area, which is fully open-air. The requirement was achieved as planned.
- P_UC3-CAV_002: RTK service was configured for the MILLA CAV, the only vehicle for which it is relevant. RTK corrections were received via public network SIM.
- P_UC3-CAV_003: Originally required NTRIP-based RTK correction was not used; instead, RTK corrections were successfully received through the MILLA CAV's commercial SIM card. This requirement is considered obsolete.
- P_UC3-CAV_004: Seamless internet connectivity was maintained for the CAV via a commercial SIM. However, during CV roaming between the "French" and "Spanish" mobile operators, temporary loss of 5G connectivity (30–70 seconds) was observed. This gap was mitigated by continuous C-ITS messaging over RSU-based C-V2X connectivity.
- P_UC3-CAV_005: The CAM generation latency requirement (<100 ms) is expected to be met based on lab and field performance, but final verification measurements will be conducted in September 2025 (to be reported in D5.2).

- P_UC3-CAV_006: CVs are expected to meet the internal message-handling capacity (>10 messages/sec). Stress testing of the V2X-OBUS stack with up to 200 messages/sec will be reported in September 2025 (in D5.2).
- P_UC3-NET_001: Latency remained well below 1 second (RTT ~150 ms). The observed throughput (~200–400 kbps) was lower than originally specified due to the limited number of vehicles and the shift of video analytics to roadside PCs. Reliability was deemed sufficient, with no observed queuing or packet loss.
- P_UC3-NET_002: Original requirements for real-time video streaming (latency <100 ms, 1 Mbps throughput) were modified. Since video analytics are now handled at roadside PCs, only processed data are transmitted to the MEC, significantly reducing bandwidth needs. Measurements to confirm performance will be conducted in September.
- P_UC3-NET_003: Incident alert transmission (e.g. DENM) latency was significantly below 1 second (RTT ~150 ms). Throughput and reliability met the requirement.
- P_UC3-NET_004: Tele-supervision performance (latency, throughput, and reliability) is not yet verified. Field tests will take place after the MILLA shuttle returns to Barcelona (post-September 2025).
- P_UC3-NET_005: The MEC-Cloud connection was restructured into a fully edge-based implementation where the Global TMC functions are hosted within the MEC. As such, latency is effectively negligible, and throughput far exceeds original expectations. This requirement is considered fulfilled with architectural changes.

4. Italian Living Lab

The Italian LL has two different sites, for two different types of use cases: an urban site and a highway site. The urban site is located in the city of Turin, within the hospital area, particularly a intersection with moderate flow of VRUs. The highway site is on the Autostrada del Brennero with different locations following the various scenarios. Both sites have complementary features since they face different approaches to the application, but the platforms behind them are mostly similar in their workflow. Each site is associated with a use case, UC4 to the urban site and UC5 to the highway site.

4.1. Use Case 4

In this chapter we describe UC4 activities of the Italian Living Lab.

Use case 4 demonstrates how the PDI can give more valuable information to CAVs, with respect to single vehicle sensors, allowing CAVs to perform manoeuvres in urban environments, protecting actively VRUs.

UC4 explores the following scenarios (as described in D3.2 [11] and D3.3 [3]):

- **Scenario 1: Straight**
- **Scenario 2: Right Turn**
- **Scenario 3: Left Turn**

In the following sections we will describe:

- e) the UC4 test site, including the deployment of new and/or adaptation of existing equipment of the LL and the preparation of the test vehicles and other test facilities
- f) the integration of the WP3 PDI innovations in the LL test site, and validation
- g) the testing methodologies, data loggers, and test plan
- h) the pre-demo testing activities relevant for this UC, in line with the checklist of Functional and Non-Functional requirements as described in D2.2 [1].

A checklist for the LL preparation and integration validation is also provided in the Annex.

4.1.1. LL description

The UC4 is located in Turin Italy, at the intersection of Corso Spezia and Via Ventimiglia. This intersection includes the main road and auxiliary roads, one on each direction; pedestrians are allowed to cross in all directions through the pedestrian lanes properly defined. The intersection is characterized by a high traffic of vehicles and VRUs (many vehicles are parked and circulating constantly). The zone is a hospital location with 4 hospitals within a few blocks.

The intersection has a proper traffic light infrastructure and real-time information is available from the city municipality in the form of standard SPATEM and MAPEM messages.

With respect of the previous D4.1 [2] in the section 2.4.3, the LL is facing the update of the RSU for the PC5 interface at the moment this document is being finalised. The VRU app and bicycle hardware have already been finished and are contributing to real-time intersection data.

4.1.1.1. Description of the LL infrastructure (existing and newly installed)

Existing LL Infrastructure

The MEC, as hardware infrastructure provided by TIM, was already installed and working. The required software components were installed after the necessary credentials and permissions were ready. These components were the C-ITS broker, Digital Twin, fusion module and VIMA.

Figure 70: LINKS RSU and camera/LIDAR sensors for UC4

The RSU was installed at the target intersection in Corso Spezia (Figure 70). The upgrade to PC5 interfaces is planned but not completed at the time of writing this document. The missing PC5 interfaces at the time does not prevent the execution of the tests.

4.1.1.2. Vehicles description

The CAV prototype is a Maserati Ghibli (Figure 71), in which PoDIUM on board system has been integrated to get trusted and highly reliable data about Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) such as pedestrian and cyclists at the crossroads from the PoDIUM infrastructure-based platform.

Figure 71: CRF CAV prototype for UC4

In addition to the pre-existing Automated Driving (AD) electronic control unit (ECU), the system integrates:

- the V2X On-Bboard Unit (OBU) by Links, which handles vehicle positioning and bidirectional data exchange between PoDIUM and the vehicles
- the Main PoDIUM ECU, hosting CRF software applications, which combine vehicle dynamics, sensing and V2X, to assist the driver or the AD Function
- the on-board display showing the HMI dedicated to PoDIUM (see Figure 73), by CRF

Most of the prototype components are installed on a metal rack in the vehicle boot (Figure 72).

Figure 72: Electronic components in the car boot

Figure 73: PoDIUM display (screen at the bottom)

4.1.1.3. Other test facilities

The VRU app is currently working on a Samsung Galaxy A54 5G and it interacts with the bicycle hardware via Wi-Fi. The bicycle hardware uses smartphone's internet connection to access RTK corrections via Wi-Fi. For the hardware used in the bicycle, a u-blox F9R receiver has been integrated into an Arduino shield hardware, with host and Wi-Fi functionality. The whole device is integrated into a 3D-printed case and fixed to an assisted electric bicycle with a standard mechanical attachment in the rear fork (see Figure 74).

Figure 74: PoDIUM VRU Bicycle hardware and VRU APP

4.1.2. PoDIUM PDI innovations’ integration & validation

4.1.2.1. PDI internal integrations

Within the Italian LL platform, the VIMA system receives messages from both the environment and the CAV. Based on this data, it determines whether there is a potential risk of collision between the CAV and a VRU.

To ensure the correct functioning of the service, the following checks are carried out periodically:

Table 5: VIMA verification checks

ID	Description
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_1	Verification of the reception of MAPEM messages and their proper loading into the service cache
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_2	Verification of the reception of SPATEM messages and consistency check of data related to the received MAPEM
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_3	Verification of the reception of CAM messages and consistency check of data related to the received MAPEM
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_4	Verification that CAM messages indicate an approach toward an intersection
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_5	Verification of the reception of CPM messages
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_6	Verification that SPATEM messages are synchronized with the actual traffic light signals
VIMA_CAV_1	Verification of IVIM message transmission

4.1.2.2. Vehicle-related integrations

On-board hardware and software integration into the vehicles

- V2X OBU – PoDIUM infrastructure:

The V2X OBU exchanges V2X messages from the PoDIUM infrastructure. The integration tests indicated in Table 6 have been performed.

Table 6: Integration tests between V2X OBU and PoDIUM

ID	Description
V2X-OBU_PoDIUM-INFRA_1	Correspondence of GNSS positions with the positioning data included in CAM (done with a GNSS simulator)
V2X-OBU_PoDIUM-INFRA_2	CPM Messages transmission from OBU and their amounts of objects in the message
V2X-OBU_PoDIUM-INFRA_3	CAM messages generated, sent and located on a map in real time on infrastructure
V2X-OBU_PoDIUM-INFRA_4	Check of SPAT information received with respect to the visual status of the corresponding traffic light
V2X-OBU_PoDIUM-INFRA_5	Verification of IVIM messages generated during turn scenarios

The interface between the Main PoDIUM ECU (hosting CRF software) and the V2X OBU (provided by Links) is based on a dedicated Controller Area Network (CAN) bus. The message map was jointly defined by CRF and Links, specifying the data exchanged within the limits of CAN capacity:

- From the Main PoDIUM ECU to V2X OBU: vehicle network signals and objects detected by on-board sensors, to enable the encoding and sending of CAM and CPM.
- From the V2X OBU to Main PoDIUM ECU: the GNSS positioning data and the V2X data concerning relevant objects and events received from the PoDIUM platform, such as road users/obstacles, warnings, traffic light phases, local maps and signage/precedence

Integration tests between the V2X OBU and the PoDIUM main PC onboard the vehicle are reported in Table 7.

Table 7: Integration tests between V2X OBU and PoDIUM main PC onboard the vehicle

ID	Description
V2X-OBU_PoDIUM-ECU_1	The OBU forwards the objects related to relevant C-V2X messages (from received CAM, DENM, IVIM, CPM, SPATEM and MAPEM) to the PoDIUM main PC over CAN bus
V2X-OBU_PoDIUM-ECU_2	The PoDIUM main PC forwards the sensor detections data to be transmitted (CPM) to the OBU over CAN bus

- Main PoDIUM ECU – HMI:

The data received by the V2X OBU are then fused and stored in a Local Dynamic Map (LDM). Based on the LDM, an application

- Shows detected objects on a virtual driving scene on the car display
- Informs the driver of VRU crossing and related timing, suggesting cross/stop manoeuvres

- Warns of hazards

These functionalities are shown to the user in the dedicated onboard display. The layout is reported in Figure 75. A virtual driving scene shows an underlying map of the intersection with dynamic objects represented. Box shapes indicate vehicles (similar to a cube) or VRUs (thinner boxes), while the colour indicates whether the object is sensed only by vehicle sensors only (blue) or by sensors & CPM data fusion (red). Above the virtual driving scene, an area is dedicated to the precedence indications (from IVIM data), besides a pictogram of pedestrian crossing that turns coloured whenever a danger is present (from DENM data). Traffic Light Phase (from SPATEM) is shown as contextual information.

Figure 75: PoDIUM UC4 display explained

The integration tests done after integrating the PoDIUM vehicle application on the main PC are reported in Table 8.

Table 8: Tests performed after integrating the PoDIUM application on the main PC

ID	Description
PoDIUM ECU – APP_1	V2X objects displayed on HMI
PoDIUM ECU – APP_2	V2X warnings and suggestions displayed on HMI
PoDIUM ECU – APP_3	Maps displayed on HMI
PoDIUM ECU – APP_4	System status check (GNSS, V2X connection)

4.1.2.3. Roadside entities integrations

The following integration verifications were performed (Table 9). The RSU was tested according to the messages it generates, sends and receives. First of all, the generation of CPMs is a base for the data floor required to support the use case, so message generations were checked before any tests. Also, a verification of the required computing power exposed by the GPU in order to avoid overheating was considered. Firstly, interactions with the infrastructure were considered and then with short range.

Table 9: Tests verifying the PoDIUM infrastructure integration

ID	Description
RSU-INFRA_1	CPM objects displayed on a map in real-time to check their broad location with respect to the video stream. Fine location of a pedestrian in a known location

RSU-INFRA_2	Subscriptions to C-ITS broker for short range messages
RSU-INFRA_3	Display of real-time LIDAR objects detected

4.1.2.4. VRU related integrations

The VRU-related integration tests are reported in Table 10. VRU integrations have two stages since VRUs can be pedestrians or bikes. VRU APP interacts with both the infrastructure and the bicycle hardware.

Table 10: Tests verifying the integration on VRU components

ID	Description
VRU-INFRA_1	VAM objects received from app
VRU-BIKE_1	Check correct interactions with bicycle OBU GNSS
VRU-BIKE_2	Check bike RTK connectivity via smartphone

4.1.3. Pre-demo testing methodology

4.1.3.1. Pre-test conditions

The pre-test conditions for Use Case 4 are listed hereafter. All of them have been met, apart from the short-range communication on the RSU which is not available. However, UC4 concept can be demonstrated even with the RSU being connected V2N only (5G).

Table 11: Pre-test conditions for UC 4

Pre-test condition	Fulfilled	Comments
MEC components deployed	Yes	
RSUs and sensors installed	Yes	V2N only
Roadside Sensors ready and configured to produce CPMs	Yes	
OBU installed on vehicle and able to send vehicle CPMs and originate CAMs	Yes	
OBU able to receive CPMs and able to calculate the relevance of received SPAT	Yes	
VRU APP able to produce VAMs when using the APP	Yes	
SPAT (from Municipality of Torino) and MAP (from SWM) available with all required signal groups	Yes	
CAV able to produce CPM from Onboard detections	Yes	
CAV equipped and operational in UC4 scenarios (including HMI)	Yes	
Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials	Yes	Regards MEC access

4.1.3.2. Description of pre-demo testing methodologies, plans and tools

The pre-demo test plan is based on the scenarios defined in D3.3 [3], which are executed directly on the LL in the centre of Turin. The plan intends to test the scenarios in all their configurations (sub-scenarios). The goal of pre-demo testing is to debug the system and verify its functionalities. Being a preparation and system refinement phase, the system is not yet evaluated against its performance requirements and KPI's.

Scenario 1:

This kind of scenario is triggered when the CAV is going to pass the intersection straight, as shown in Figure 76. The RSU/SPU continuously feed CPMs with information into the infrastructure. VIMA (VRU Intersection Movement Assistance) identifies a collision risk in case the VRU crosses (violating red light).

Figure 76: Straight scenario

This kind of scenario is split in two main points or sub-scenarios:

- Sc. 1.1: Straight-Pass: The VRU is standing at the cross-roads, therefore, no obstacle is considered by the CAV.
- Sc. 1.2: Straight-Warn/Brake: The CAV has green light, but the VRU violates its red and crosses.

The first one is considered was tested for technical purpose, namely, to check the system's performance in filtering out the negative cases. The demonstration focus is actually Sc. 1.2 and timeline refers to this scenario.

Timeline – Storyboard steps

- t0 - Vehicle and VRU start moving.
- t1 - Vehicle and VRU (app) broadcast standard messages while moving.
- t2 - CAV and VRU (app) are notified of the presence of each other.
- t3 - Truthfulness Module identifies that both road users are in collision course due to red violation by the VRU.
- t4 - A collision warning DENM is sent by TM to the relevant road users.
- t5 - CAV waits or modulates speed to let VRU cross first.
- t6 - CAV ends the crossing.

Test Cases

Table 12 lists the test cases in which the vehicle crosses straight at the intersection. What changes is the pedestrian’s position: in one case the VRU is simply standing, in the other case he/she intends to cross

Table 12: Test cases for UC 4 – vehicle proceeds straight

ID	Description	Test method and tools
UC4_1.1	Straight pass VRU is standing at the cross-roads, no crossing	Pedestrian standing on test site
UC4_1.2	Straight-Warn/Brake: CAV has green light, but VRU violates its red and crosses.	Pedestrian crossing on test site in controlled and safe condition, addressing the storyboard steps

Scenario 2:

The vehicle arrives at the intersection, it breaks and gives way to the VRU. Both the CAV and the VRU have green light, but the vehicle must give way to pedestrian (Figure 77). The vehicle is assisted by the infrastructure that notifies both the presence of a VRU (supported by VAM/CPM from infrastructure) and the Integrity Measurement Architecture (IMA) indication (supported by IVIM from infrastructure).

Figure 77: Right turn scenario

Right turn scenario includes:

- Sc. 2.1: VRU precedence management: VIMA handles the precedence and VRU respects it.
- Sc. 2.2: two VRU case.

With respect to D3.3 [3], the plans for SC.2.2 and SC2.3 have been updated, because they are very difficult to test in the LL. The former descriptions included VRU sudden crossing (SC.2.2) and precedence management after a sudden crossing (SC2.3).

Timeline – Storyboard steps

- t0 - CAV and VRU start moving.
- t1 - CAV and VRU broadcast standard messages while moving. CAV indicates its intention to turn right by letting the turn-right light on.
- t2 - CAV and VRU are notified of the presence of other road users.
- t3 - IMA risk assessment identifies that both road users are in collision course due to both have GREEN light.
- t4 - Information is sent using C-ITS to the relevant road users to arbitrate the crossing.
 - t4.1 - CAV receives an indication to break and wait.
 - t4.2 - VRU receives an indication to pass.
- t5 - CAV undertakes slowly the turn but stops some meters before the VRU crossing.
- t6 - VRU finishes crossing the intersection.
- t7 - CAV receives an indication to start moving and turn to the right, if there is a green light (IVIM update). Two IVIM messages are sent.

Test Cases

Hereafter in Table 13, the test cases for scenario 2 are listed: just one pedestrian (case UC4_2.1) or two/more pedestrians (case UC4_2.2) cross the intersection.

Table 13: Test cases for UC 4 – vehicle turns right

ID	Description	Test method and tools
UC4_2.1	VRU precedence management: VIMA handles the precedence and VRU respects it.	Pedestrian crossing on test site in controlled and safe condition, addressing the storyboard steps
UC4_2.2	Two VRU crossing	Two (or more) pedestrian crossing on test site in sequence. Checking that the system merges the detections and sends out VIMA and/or DENM taking both pedestrians into consideration.

Scenario 3:

In the Left Turn scenario (Figure 78), the vehicle needs to turn left and is assisted by the road infrastructure, which considers both the presence of oncoming vehicles and the pedestrian crossing.

Figure 78: Left turn scenario

Timeline – Storyboard steps

The following timeline represents a step-by-step guide on how the scenario is expected to evolve in real life.

- t0 - CAV and VRU start moving
- t1 - CAV and VRU broadcast standard messages while moving. CAV indicates its intention to turn left by turning on its turn-left exterior light
- t2 - CAV and VRU are notified of the presence of other road users
- t3 - IMA risk assessment identifies that the road users are in collision course
 - t3.1 - IMA analyses the opposite vehicle trajectory
 - t3.2 - IMA analyses the VRU trajectory
- t4 - Information is sent using C-ITS to the relevant road users to arbitrate the crossing
 - t4.1 - CAV receives an indication to break and wait
 - t4.2 - VRU receives an indication to pass
- t5 - CAV moves towards the centre of the intersection and stops there waiting for the other road users to cross
- t6 - Non equipped vehicle finalizes to pass the intersection
- t7 - VRU finishes crossing the intersection
- t8 - CAV receives an indication to start moving and turn to the left, if there is a green light

Test Cases

Scenario 3 (Table 14) is tested in only one case, but a rather complex case: the vehicle turns left and has to give precedence first to any oncoming vehicles coming from the opposite direction, then to the pedestrian.

Table 14: Test cases for UC 4 – vehicle turns left

ID	Description	Test method and tools
UC4_3	Left Turn	Pedestrian crossing on test site in controlled and safe condition. Possible traffic coming from the opposite direction with respect to the vehicle (not controllable during the tests).

Scenario 4: Trust

This scenario has been completely finished and deployed into a test environment in a parallel on board unit. Various functional tests were carried out using the EMBRAVE framework during the last year of the project.

The testbed comprised two TCB platforms acting as EMBRAVE Agents and includes all components in the Trusted Domain of the EMBRAVE architecture. Both platforms had an external board with a TPM 2.0 (IRIDIUM SLM 9670 TPM2.0 with an OPTIGA™ TPM SLM 9670 chip). We set the default IMA (Integrity Measurement Architecture) policy for both platforms. The Verifier, Join Service, and MQTT broker were deployed on an off-the-shelf server.

The first functional tests verified correct communication between the Join Service, Verifier, Agent, and MQTT Broker. Next, we verified that the Join Phase of Agents was successful and that the Join Service called a Verifier to start the Remote Attestation. Then, we verified that the verifier correctly identifies the attestation result as trusted when all verifications are successful and as untrusted when the SW has been tampered with, such as an unexpected event in the IMA log or a change to the TPM 2.0 quote signature.

The final test was an incremental control of the IMA log, which was performed by simulating a second process in the Agents that extended the IMA log with new entries. The attestation procedure receives the entire IMA log the first time and then successfully verifies only the new entries, reducing the Verifier's workload.

4.1.3.3. Data logging setup and data storage

In every service, logs are produced via the Linux system and Docker logs for the respective components.

LINKS has placed a shared drive accessible to partners to upload temporary log files and video recordings intended for dissemination.

All data logs from the OBU and MEC components are logged and retrieved from the MEC and the OBU and are then stored in a local PC in LINKS premises. Files are named with the date of the test sessions and the type of component logging.

During May and June 2025, the logs obtained from the test sessions were processed in order to decode them and perform checks, such as the verification of positions contained in CAMs, and the timing of DENM and IVIM messages.

4.1.4. Report of pre-demo testing activities

Several pre-demo testing activities were performed in UC4, both at the partners' premises and on the test site. Hereafter, the whole testing activities, from integration to the scenario pre-demo tests is reported.

- In January 2024, at its premises in Orbassano (Turin), CRF verified CAV sensors data on the main PC and HMI, for pedestrian and cyclist detection.
- In February 2024, CRF verified CAV sensors data lane line detection, also at its own premises.
- In March and April 2024, CRF tested the integration of the V2X OBU with the onboard system (Main PC and HMI) in the lab, with V2X messages input based on LINKS specifications of DENM, SPAT, CPM, IVIM.
- In July 2024, first two joint test sessions with project partners on Turin Test Site were performed, with the vehicle prototype receiving messages from the PoDIUM infrastructure, addressing straight crossing and right turn scenarios. The CAV application logic could be improved after the first test results. DENM and SPAT were tested. CPM and IVIM were implemented but could not be tested (only preliminary CPM message, but no IVIM was triggered).
- In September 2024, two additional test sessions were performed on the Living Lab, focusing on CPM and IVIM generation and reception. Beyond the triggering conditions, the timing of the special IVIM (VIMA) was checked.
- In October and November 2024, test sessions were repeated on different scenarios, addressing straight, right turn and, for the first time, left turn. While straight and right turn gave preliminary results showing implementation progress, left turn still had issues. Sometimes SPAT message was not available (SPAT is legacy message from the Municipality, not PoDIUM implementation). Overall, scenario functionality could be tested, but the OBU positioning had to be improved.
- In December 2024, TIM performed the predisposition of SEN (Service Edge Node) environment for the project and provided the SIM for the project (configuring the access to SEN).
- In January 2025 LINKS procured an additional connected vehicle (CV) to support the Living Lab, as most tests left regarded the connectivity between the PoDIUM infrastructure and the V2X OBU. The CV is a rental car hosting the OBU (without vehicle data access).
- In February 2025, eight lab tests were performed on the V2X OBU and using a Hardware-in-the-Loop facility at CRF, which uses artificially generated GNSS constellation to simulate drive tests at the test site. The tests aimed at verifying the V2X OBU I/O and the GNSS system in its basic functionality (without RTK corrections and without IMU data fusion). In parallel, LINKS performed the first test in Turin on the LL with its OBU on the rented vehicle. Furthermore, CRF enhanced its logging system onboard the CAV and tested it on the Turin LL.
- In May 2025, LINKS performed V2X OBU tests on-site using a rental car, in collaboration with SWM and TIM. The objective was to test the OBU functionalities and the integration with the PoDIUM infrastructure, after all components were installed on MEC.
- In May and June 2025, five joint test sessions were organized. Four sessions were with LINKS vehicle and SWM, plus one more test with all partners.
- In July LINKS, TIM and SWM tested in 4 sessions the complete chain of messages and data. In one session, logs were captured in CAN blf format and were shared with CRF for validation. Tests allowed to get some bugs fixed in different components. Joint tests with all partners including CRF with the vehicle demonstrator, were done on 29th of July on the site. Data were

recorded and are currently being analysed. As a whole, the system is now integrated but still needs fine tuning.

4.1.4.1. Functional tests

The functional requirements are listed and reported in the Annex. UC4 has met 85% of all requirements so far, the rest have partial achievement, and others have changed since the definition of the requirements.

- PC5 is not yet installed in RSU but it is installed on OBU, the later without configuration yet, so this partially affects achievement of requirement CAV_007, PF_UC4-CAV_006 and PF_UC4-CAV_015.
- SYA_005 Secure communication to preserve data integrity Not yet available in OBU but in another TCB.
- SYA_006 Privacy-preserving software integrity checks Not yet available
- PF_UC4-CAV_009 MAPEM messages reception is changed since MAPEM is not yet transmitted by municipality, but LINKS is transmitting a MAPEM created by SWM.
- PF_UC4-SEC_004 Blocking misbehaving OBUs/RSUs Not yet available, but its achievement is ongoing.

Some requirements have changed:

- In SER_078 “TLA” now called “VIMA” for precedence management as defined in requirement SER_078
- In requirement SYA_003 RSUs were supposed to challenge OBUS, but Only MEC and Cloud perform trust challenges, RSU is excluded given that both nodes communicate in short range.
- CAV uses either local MAP or MAPEM as requirement PF_UC4-CAV_004
- Uses time of pedestrian lane occupancy instead of “time-to-pass” as the requirement PF_UC4-CAV_011 .
- Truthfulness module integrated within Digital Twin (DT) changes compliance for PF_UC4-CE_005 .
- RSU is TCB but not an attestation entity, which modifies compliance with PF_UC4-SEC_002.
- MQTT protocol replaced by AMQP, changing compliance of COM_031 and SER_075
- “TLA” now called “VIMA” for precedence management as defined in requirement SER_078.
- In requirement SYA_003 RSUs were supposed to challenge OBUS, but Only MEC and Cloud perform trust challenges, RSU is excluded given that both nodes communicate in short range.
- CAV uses either local MAP or MAPEM as requirement PF_UC4-CAV_004.
- In UC4 the CAV Uses time of pedestrian lane occupancy instead of “time-to-pass” as the requirement PF_UC4-CAV_011.
- Truthfulness module integrated within Digital Twin (DT) changes compliance for PF_UC4-CE_005.
- RSU is a TCB but not an attestation entity, which modifies compliance with PF_UC4-SEC_002.

MEC testing

In April 2025, software components were installed on the project MEC server provided by TIM (previously, they had run on a provisional LINKS MEC).

During May and June 2025 some tests were conducted using simulated positions in order to avoid the cost of testing with the vehicles. The main outcomes are the verification of the reception of the required messages behind the particular conditions of the vehicle.

CLOUD testing

The tests conducted to verify the correct functioning of VIMA in the cloud are the same as those described in section 4.1.2.1, since VIMA operates identically regardless of the environment in which it is deployed. For the system to function correctly, it is essential that VIMA receives all required messages without issues. An additional test carried out in this context involves measuring the latency in message reception and transmission, which may be affected using the Cloud. Table 15 describes the VIMA functioning tests.

Table 15: VIMA functioning tests

ID	Description
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_1	Verification of the reception of MAPEM messages and their proper loading into the service cache
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_2	Verification of the reception of SPATEM messages and consistency check of data related to the received MAPEM
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_3	Verification of the reception of CAM messages and consistency check of data related to the received MAPEM
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_4	Verification that CAM messages indicate an approach toward an intersection
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_5	Verification of the reception of CPM messages
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_6	Verification that SPATEM messages are synchronized with the actual traffic light signals
VIMA_PoDIUM-INFRA_7	Messages reception latency measurement
VIMA_CAV_1	Verification of IVIM message transmission
VIMA_CAV_2	Messages sending latency measurement

CV testing

Between January and July 2025, LINKS performed seven sessions of tests with a CV and a LINKS OBU. The main activity was to check the positioning corresponding to CAM messages, the accuracy and continuity of position and the reception of messages (checked via log) to the OBU according to the definition of the scenarios.

CAV testing

CAV’s core functionalities and scenarios were thoroughly tested during 2024. This included data fusion, driving recommendations and the HMI display of detected objects, which were tested both in the laboratory and on the Living Lab. Based on the first test results, the system was improved by adding the map of intersection to the display for the 2025 release.

VRU testing

During 2024 the VRU App was tested, initially in the positioning part, and lately in the message generation part.

In 2025, the APP has been tested by comparing different sources of positioning, considering also the bicycle OBU positioning sensors and the stability of their main functions. VRU tests have been done also with the LINKS CV in two tests sessions.

RSU testing

Tests on were RSU done during early 2024 with the fusion of LIDAR and camera, and the verification of the accuracy in the generation of CPMs. Initially a calibration was done using the VRU app precise positions to confirm the position perceived by the detection algorithm. All these tests during 2024 were done by connecting to a LINKS cloud hosting applications (Figure 79).

Figure 79: Debug interface developed by LINKS to check the real-time detection of VRUs and other road users and CPM generation

Currently a work around is present to allow communication between the RSU and the MEC. In 2025, the SIM card installed on the RSU was not able to access the MEC since it was a commercial SIM with no access to the MEC infrastructure. Previously, in 2024, the LINKS cloud was accessible with the same SIM. Given the impossibility to change the permissions administratively, the SIM will be changed during the hardware update planned in the next months (already planned to install the PC5 update). RSU communication with the MEC currently passes through another RSU belonging to LINKS that has access to the MEC.

4.1.4.2. Non-functional tests

Most of the non-functional tests have been suspended, since the complete integration tests have yet to be performed. There are some non-functional requirements that partners have already checked for compliance, either directly or indirectly

Regarding PNF_UC4-CAV_002 related with the precision of the positioning of the OBU, this has been achieved by using RTK and dead reckoning. In the Figure 80 below a plot of a measurement campaign was depicted with the confidence intervals for 95% of possible values. Fixes are obtained with values in the centimetre range.

Figure 80: Position tracking using confidence ellipse intervals with RTK + Dead Reckoning

Regarding latency in PNF_UC4_CAV_003, PNF_UC4_NET_001 and PNF_UC4_NET_002 during the tests done in 2024 on the LINKS cloud (less reliable than the actual project’s MEC), partners measured latency and reliability in the compound of the experiments to find the proper timing for messages to arrive. This was done for vehicles following the triggering events described in the scenarios. Strict measurements have still to be made in order to calculate KPIs related to timing.

Regarding UC4_D5.1_2 all partners have permissions to execute trials, except for SWM, which is using a work around to check and control the components in the MEC during trials.

4.1.4.3. Scenario 1 related trials

Table 16 is a checklist of the test cases of scenario 1.

Table 16: UC4 scenario 1 related trials

ID	Description	Functionality verified	Correct trials after debug
UC4_1.1	Straight pass VRU is standing at the cross-roads, no crossing	Yes	2
UC4_1.2	Straight-Warn/Brake: CAV has green light, but VRU violates its red and crosses.	Yes	2

4.1.4.4. Scenario 2 related trials

Table 17 shows the trials of scenario 2. SUC4 pilot focuses on precedent management of pedestrian precedence management through VIMA functionality, and test cases 2.1 and 2.2 involve the basic version of this functionality (test case 2.3 and scenario 3 are more complex), most of the trials of this pre-demo phase covered the indeed 2.1 and 2.2.

Table 17: UC4 scenario 2 related trials

ID	Description	Functionality verified	Correct trials after debug
UC4_2.1	VRU precedence management: VIMA handles the precedence and VRU respects it.	Yes	8
UC4_2.2	VRU sudden crossing: VIMA handles the precedence, but VRU crosses outside the timeslot.	Yes	7
UC4_2.3	Precedence management after sudden crossing: two VRU crossing.	Pending	Pending

4.1.4.5. Scenario 3 related trials

Table 18 reports, analogously to the previous tables, the number of correct trials performed on the left turn scenario after debugging the functionalities. We highlight here, that several trials have been done in the debug phase using the project CAV between September and December 2024. In recent months, other tests were done with the LINKS' CV, verifying qualitatively the proper generation of the messages: CAM, CPM, DENM and IVIM.

Table 18: UC4 scenario 3 related trials

ID	Description	Functionality verified	Correct trials after debug
UC4_3	Left turn	Preliminary tests only with CV	3

4.2. Use Case 5

In this chapter we describe the Use case 5 activities of the Italian LL.

Use case 5 will demonstrate how connected and automated vehicles (CAV) can be assisted by the PoDIUM infrastructure in highway tunnels, thanks to a risk management subsystem that collects data from the motorway, evaluates risk and generates high-quality information for CAVs.

As a brief reminder, Use Case5 explores the following scenarios:

- **Scenario 1: Road Works Warning applied to Cooperative ACC**
- **Scenario 2: Traffic Jam Ahead Warning**
- **Scenario 3: AD Operational Design Domain in presence of Traffic Jam**

In the following chapters we will describe:

- i) the LL testbed, including the deployment of new and/or adaptation of existing equipment of the LL and the preparation of the test vehicles and other test facilities
- j) the integration of the WP3 PDI innovations in the LL testbed, and validation
- k) the testing methodologies, data loggers, and test plan
- l) the pre-demo testing activities relevant for this UC, in line with the checklist of Functional and Non-Functional requirements as described in D2.2 [1]

A checklist for the LL preparation and integration validation is also provided in the Annex.

4.2.1. LL description

4.2.1.1. Description of the LL infrastructure (existing and newly installed)

The C-ITS infrastructure, including the data flow from the Traffic Control Centre (TCC) to the C-ITS server and RSUs, was already in place and reused for the project. Software updates were applied to both the server and the RSUs to extend support for mobility-related scenarios.

To meet the project's objectives, A22 installed six additional RSUs near the Tush Tunnel.

Four RSUs dedicated to the V2XLocate positioning system were installed along the southbound direction outside the tunnel (Figure 83), due to legal and technical constraints that prevented installation inside. These RSUs operate independently of the C-ITS infrastructure, though they are integrated into the A22 network.

Two RSUs were installed next to the Variable Message Signs (VMS) at the tunnel entrance and exit to broadcast C-ITS messages. These are fully integrated into the existing C-ITS system.

In addition, two RSUs equipped with dedicated cameras, provided by project partner LINKS, were installed alongside the A22 RSUs at the tunnel entrance and exit.

These RSUs are part of the Risk Assessment module and are integrated into both the A22 network and the C-ITS ecosystem to monitor traffic levels and support real-time risk evaluation (Figure 82). Additionally, they feature modem-based connectivity, allowing secure remote monitoring and control by external partners.

Figure 81: Pilot Site – Tush Tunnel near Bozen city

Figure 82: A22 – C-ITS RSU and LINKS - RSU with camera for the Risk Assessment module

Figure 83: A22 – V2XLocate RSU installed

4.2.1.2. Vehicles description

For UC5, two vehicle prototypes (CAV, Maserati Levante and CV, FIAT 500e) show how the advances in positioning technology can enable Connected and Automated Driving even in GNSS denied environment (Figure 84).

Both prototype vehicles have:

- Precise GNSS with RTK corrections for open sky positioning
- Dead reckoning based on relative localization when entering and within the tunnel
- V2X positioning based on trilateration within the tunnel

Figure 84: PoDIUM UC5 CAV (left) and CV (right)

Both cars feature Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control (C-ACC) supported by:

- V2V Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAM) of the cooperative vehicle ahead being followed
- V2I and V2N to exchange messages with the PoDIUM Road infrastructure, about road hazards and dynamic signage

Both exchange sensor information through Collective Perception Messages (CPMs).

The CAV features automation levels up to SAE L4 (up to perception, not actuation) and ODD information. An example is the preliminary test on C-ACC car follow with level4 ODD, conducted in a motorway tunnel near Trento City (see Figure 85).

Figure 85: CAV following CV in tunnel, then experiencing a cut-in

In Use Case 5, the prototypes have a legacy AD/ADAS basis and then a PoDIUM-dedicated development, namely: the integrated positioning system, which is intended to seamlessly combine the three sources (GNSS+RTK, trilateration and dead reckoning); the CPM standard feature, replacing former solutions based on CPM surrogate using CAM; unified logics combining V2V-based C-ACC with messages from PoDIUM infrastructure (high quality DENM/IVIM from the risk management module).

4.2.1.3. Other test facilities

Two additional test facilities supported UC5 activities:

- Safety Park, a private test track near Bolzano (Figure 86), and
- a dedicated area within the Motorway Safety Center (CSA) of A22 near S. Michele (Figure 87).

Both sites were used to conduct field tests of the V2XLocate positioning system and to evaluate all UC5 scenarios. The testing involved both CRF/BRE prototype vehicles and an A22 vehicle equipped with a mobile RSU, which broadcast warning messages to emulate real-world conditions.

This A22 vehicle also acted as a non-connected vehicle in selected scenarios to assess system behaviour in mixed traffic environments.

Three test sessions were carried out on separate days: the first and third at Safety Park and the second at the CSA site. These sessions aimed to simulate all vehicle-related aspects of UC5 and assess V2XLocate system performance, both standalone and in combination with on-board sensors.

To analyse positioning accuracy, RSU configurations were varied between the two Safety Park sessions. In the third session, RSUs were deployed along the main straight, where UC5 manoeuvres were performed, to improve coverage and test performance under more realistic conditions.

Figure 86: Safety Park Bolzano - First First and Third Test Session, RSU position setup

Figure 87: Motorway Safety Center (CSA) S. Michele - Second Test Session, RSU position setup

4.2.2. PoDIUM PDI innovations' integration & validation

4.2.2.1. PDI internal integrations

The A22 C-ITS system was enhanced to receive and forward CPMs, over both ITS-G5 and IP channels, without generating them directly.

A dedicated module for risk assessment and digital twin functionalities was also integrated. This module processes data collected by the LINKS camera-equipped RSUs, incoming CPMs from CRF vehicles, and existing C-ITS system inputs. Additionally, communication in the reverse direction was enabled to update and adapt active C-ITS scenarios in real time based on risk analysis outcomes.

4.2.2.2. Vehicle-related integrations

Key integration aspects regarded:

- Collective Perception: populating a CPM with vehicle detections (NOTE: the UC5 CPM is featured by CRF)

ID	Description
V2X-OBUECU_1	Collect vehicle detections coming from on-vehicle (remote vehicles and pedestrian) validating the correctness of the collected data
V2X-OBUECU_2	Prepare CPM messages including vehicle detections absolute positions and characteristics (e.g. classification) and validation of CPM message through V2X debug tool.
V2X-OBUECU_3	Test at CRF facilities with pedestrian to validate correctness between real scene and V2X messages sent by the V2X-OBUECU
V2X-OBUECU_4	Test at Bolzano Safety Park with other vehicles to validate the correctness of CPM content

- Integration of event messages from PoDIUM infrastructure with C-ACC logics / L4 ODD

ID	Description
V2X-ECU-APP	V2X & Sensors objects correctly displayed on HMI
V2X-ECU-APP	Sensor Fusion Module matches V2X&Sensors objects
V2X-ECU-APP	Correct computation of the ego and remote lanes based on HD Maps
V2X-ECU-APP	Tuning parameters for C-ACC logics
V2X-ECU-APP	Correct engagement of the C-ACC Cut-In scenario
V2X-ECU-APP	Evaluation of check conditions for L4 ODD

- Data fusion of the three positioning solutions into the vehicle positioning manager application

ID	Description
V2X-POS-APP_1	V2XLocate – first infrastructure test in A22 parking area, to verify correct configuration of OBU and infrastructure RSU, and communication between the two.
V2X-POS-APP_2	Test on Bolzano Safety Park test track with RSUs positioned around the track. Test performed to evaluate overall system performance in a controlled scenario. The GNSS antenna of the Locate unit was disconnected to simulate tunnel occlusion.
V2X-POS-APP_3	V2XLocate test in A22 area at A22 roofed area “San Michele”. Overall positioning test in an artificially sky-occluded area. Test performed to check a denser RSU placement in a straight-line configuration, similar to a tunnel.
V2X-POS-APP_4	Second test on Bolzano test track with different RSU placement. This time, RSUs were placed only along the straight section.
V2X-POS-APP_5	Test in a real tunnel to check system performance and verify correct RSU-OBU communication.

4.2.2.3. Roadside entities integrations

The A22 RSUs were enhanced with new software capabilities to support CPMs, enabling validation of UC5 scenarios and ensuring interoperability with functionalities developed by CRF. For the V2XLocate system, four dedicated RSUs were installed and integrated into the A22's network. The main innovations here were the deployment of centimetre-level positioning services and the validation of positioning performance in complex environments. Integration required precise RSU placement, supported by topographic analysis, and configuration of the V2XLocate software stack.

Powering these RSUs located between carriageways required the extension of the local network, including the installation of a new switch and specialised rodent-resistant cabling. Two additional camera-equipped RSUs, developed by LINKS, were deployed to support real-time traffic monitoring to support risk assessment functions. Integration included secure remote access management, cybersecurity safeguards, and validation of camera data fusion within the PoDIUM architecture, which is currently being verified. At the moment, the RSU south camera was damaged during transportation to A22 test site and had to be transported back to LINKS premises in order to be fixed again. So an initial deploy was possible, but its continuous usage is still delayed until it is fixed and installed.

At the moment, these units are being integrated into the central Risk Assessment module to enable real-time evaluation and decision-making support.

Civil works were carried out as part of this integration effort, enabling the physical deployment and connection of all equipment necessary to validate the PoDIUM PDI features in real-world conditions.

4.2.3. Pre-demo testing methodology

4.2.3.1. Pre-test conditions

Some of the conditions are still not met, mainly due to the absence of all the RSUs installed. At the moment one RSU is installed and working, so its video stream is available to perform vehicle counting

and classification, but the maintenance of the number of vehicles in the tunnel requires both cameras and consequently the complete risk status is not yet practically calculated using live data. Also, as DT and cloud components are still being integrated with A22 components, the tests involving this message exchanges will be completed. The table below summarizes a list of checked pre-test conditions that will be necessary to achieve the Traffic Jam Alert (TJA) scenario.

Table 19: Pre-test conditions for UC 5

Pre-test condition	Fulfilled	Comments
CAV, CV and vehicle counting roadside sensors operational in UC5 scenarios	YES	
Infrastructure C-ITS warning messages available	YES	
Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials	YES	
C-ITS messages being received and decoded by LINKS Cloud	YES	
Video Stream for northern RSU available and counting algorithm	YES	
Maintenance of number of vehicles present in tunnel and their type	NOT YET	Both north and south cameras are required
Continuous calculation of risk information of the tunnel	NOT YET	North Camera stream has just recently obtained
Generation of DENM triggering ODD from LINKS Cloud	NOT YET	Not generated from DT but from program
Video Stream for southern RSU available and counting algorithm	NOT YET	Only North RSU has been mounted

4.2.3.2. Description of pre-demo testing methodologies, plans and tools

Scenario 1:

In the first sub-scenario (Figure 88), the single CAV approaching Road Works can be informed with due advance by the road infrastructure and perform a lane change and speed adaptation based on information received by the road infrastructure. Continuity of CCAM service reception and geo-referencing is provided by the in-tunnel positioning solution.

Figure 88: UC5 Scenario: Road Works Warning – CAV only (note : figure not in scale)

Timeline – Storyboard steps

- t0 - CAV drives on the right lane: ACC is engaged at user-defined target speed
- t1 - CAV receives RWW from road infrastructure, just before tunnel
- t2 - CAV reaches the DENM validity area (> 600m) and notifies driver about lane change need
- t3 - CAV changes lane
- t4 - CAV uses IVI speed limit or RWW DENM speed limit specification to adapt its speed influencing for longitudinal control
- t5 - CAV proceeds autonomously at V2X specified speed along the construction zone (DENM speed limit)
- t6 - After construction zone end, CAV returns to user-defined target speed

Sub-scenario 2 demonstrates C-ACC functionality at roadworks, in tunnel.

In sub-scenario “car follow” (Figure 89), C-ACC is handled before, during, and after the roadworks (engaged/disengaged). This is tested in the tunnel.

Figure 89: UC5 Scenario Road Works Warning – CAV and CV: car follow with C-ACC

Timeline – Storyboard steps (“car follow” sub-scenario)

t0 - CAV and CV proceed on right lane with C-ACC engaged (CAV speed follows CV speed from CAM)

t1 – CAV and CV receive RWW from road infrastructure, just before tunnel

t2 - As soon as CV changes lane, C-ACC is disengaged

t3 - CAV reaches the DENM validity area (ca. 600m) and notifies driver about lane change need

t4 - CAV changes to the same lane as CV. C-ACC is available again.

t5 - CAV User engages C-ACC again.

t6 - CAV controls speed in construction zone according to CV, within the speed limit received via V2Xtt
 In sub-scenario “cut-in” (Figure 90), the CAV can automatically adjust the C-ACC target speed and slow down when the CV sends its intentions to merge, before the roadworks. Then the CAV follows the CV within the construction site, as in the previous sub-scenario. The manoeuvres are performed in the tunnel.

Figure 90: UC5 Scenario: “cut-in” with C-ACC (at Road Works)

Timeline – Storyboard steps (“cut-in” sub-scenario)

t0 - CAV proceeds on the left lane with ACC engaged.

t1 - CAV receives RWW from road infrastructure, just before tunnel t2 - CAV reaches the DENM validity area (ca. 600m) and notifies driver about Road Works

t3 - CV intends to cut-in, in order to change to left lane, which is open; CV intention is expressed by the turn indicator (communicated via V2X too)

t4 – Upon CAV user cut-in validation, CAV slows down autonomously to ease CV cut-in

t5 - CV changes to the same lane as CAV. C-ACC is available on CAV

t6 - CAV User engages C-ACC.

t7 - CAV controls speed in construction zone according to CV, within the speed limit received via V2X

Table 20 lists the tests cases for scenario 1, namely the Roadworks. Three cases are considered, following the three sub-scenarios' storyboards. For each case, the test is performed in open sky, which is the baseline configuration, and in tunnel or GNSS denied environment, which is the target configuration.

Table 20: Test cases for UC 5 – scenario 1: Roadworks

ID	Description	Test method and tools
UC5_1.1	Single CAV approaching roadworks	Run scenario as in storyboard steps (from t1 to the end) in two conditions: Open Sky (baseline) in GNSS-denied environment (target)
UC5_1.2	CAV and CV in car follow	
UC5_1.3	CV cuts in, CAV gives way	

Scenario 2:

In scenario 2 the single CAV approaches a traffic jam in or just outside (downstream) the tunnel (Figure 91).

Figure 91: UC5 Traffic Jam Alert with CAV only

Timeline – Storyboard steps (“TJA with CAV only” sub-scenario)

- t0 - RSU’s with vehicle counters detect traffic in the tunnel area
- t1 - Risk Management module is informed of queue in tunnel from RSU and publishes HLN-TJA DENM
- t2 - CAV approaches with Highway assist (SAE L2) or ACC (L1)
- t3 - HLN-TJA DENM is received at CAV
- t4 - CAV reaches DENM validity area (>600m from event position) and notifies take-over need
- t5 - Driver disengages automated function (L2 or L1) to manual driving (L0).

Table 21 refers to the test case for scenario 2 . As in Scenario 1, the case is run in open sky and GNSS-denied environment, to compare the system performance.

Table 21: Test cases for UC 5 – scenario 2: Traffic Jam Alert, CAV only

ID	Description	Test method and tools
UC5_2	Traffic Jam Alert, CAV only	<p>Run scenario as in storyboard steps (from t1 to the end) in two conditions:</p> <p>Open Sky (baseline)</p> <p>in GNSS-denied environment (target)</p>

Scenario 3:

In scenario 3 CAV and CV are approaching the Traffic Jam as in scenario 2, but in this case the CAV is coming in a state of high automation (note: SAE L4 in terms perception only). Among the ODD conditions, the ego-vehicle must position itself at lane level, follow a CV with C-ACC (with no vehicle in the middle) and get detected objects by the CV being followed with the ego-vehicle. The CV is with Highway Assist (SAE L2) or ACC (L1).

In sub-scenario “L4 ODD keep” (Figure 92), CAV follows the CV with no vehicle in the middle, thus L4 ODD conditions are kept.

Figure 92: UC5 Scenario “L4 ODD keep”

Timeline – Storyboard steps (“Traffic Jam Alert with CAV and CV, ODD keep” scenario)

- t0 -RSU’s with vehicle counters detect traffic in the tunnel area
- t1 - Risk Management module is informed of queue in tunnel from RSU and publishes HLN-TJA DENM
- t2 - CAV is coming in L4 perception ODD: C-ACC “car follow” (through CAM) AND “extended perception” (CPM)
- t3 - HLN-TJA DENM is received at CAV
- t4 - CAV reaches DENM validity area (>600m from event position) and notifies TJA and slowdown need

t5 - CAV slows down keeping in ODD, as car-follow and extended perception are still enabled

In sub-scenario “L4 ODD exit” (Figure 93), CAV follows the CV but a non-equipped vehicle cuts-in, thus L4 ODD conditions are no longer kept.

Figure 93: UC5 Scenario Traffic Jam Alert where vehicle exits the ODD

Timeline – Storyboard steps (“Traffic Jam Alert with CAV and CV, ODD exit” scenario)

- t0 -RSU’s with vehicle counters detect traffic in the tunnel area
- t1 - Risk Management module is informed of queue in tunnel from RSU and publishes HLN-TJA DENM
- t2- CAV is coming in L4 perception ODD: C-ACC “car follow” (through CAM) AND “extended perception” (CPM)
- t3 - HLN-TJA DENM is received at CAV
- t4 - CAV reaches DENM validity area (>600m from event position) and notifies TJA and slowdown need
- t5 - Not-connected vehicle cuts-in. ODD exit. CAV slows down in ACC (L1) or manually (L0).

In Table 22, the test cases of scenario 3 are listed. These cases regard the L4 automation level at CAV, which is evaluated in terms of perception capabilities both during the trials and in post-processing. The expectation is that, in the target GNSS denied environment the so-called “extended perception” thanks to V2V cooperative messages (CPM, CAM) is degraded with respect to the baseline, but the positioning solutions developed in PoDIUM still enable the basic functionalities to a certain extent (in space-time) within the tunnel.

Table 22: Test cases for UC 5 – scenario 3: Traffic Jam Alert and L4 ODD

ID	Description	Test method and tools
UC5_3.1	Traffic Jam Alert, CV and CAV, ODD keep	Run scenario with CAV and CV as in storyboard steps (from t1 to the end) in two conditions: Open Sky (baseline) and GNSS-denied environment (target)
UC5_3.2	Traffic Jam Alert, CV and CAV, ODD exit	Run scenario with CAV, CV and another test vehicle (not equipped) that cuts in. Follow storyboard steps (from t1 to the end) in two conditions :Open Sky (baseline) and GNSS-denied environment (target)

4.2.3.3. Data logging setup and data storage

In UC5, the modules for logging from DT and RMT (Risk Management in Tunnel) are currently ready to be used in the Cloud and LINKS RSUs. Logs are aligned with the specifications described in document D4.1 [2], being handled manually and decoded using an ad-hoc tool in order to calculate KPIs and other metrics. Files remain stored in a private LINKS server for future reference.

4.2.4. Report of pre-demo testing activities

In UC5, several pre-demo testing activities were performed with CAV, CV and the PoDIUM infrastructure in several locations: on the motorway near Trento area, on highway tunnels along the A22 including the target tunnel of the LL, and on the Bolzano Safety Park test track.

- In February 2024, CRF tested vehicle sensors and data fusion modules, and the Cooperative ACC algorithm integration into the vehicle were tested on Trento motorway. Four sessions were conducted in total.
- In May 2024, CRF tested in Bolzano Safety Park, on the Trento Motorway and on the A22, which is operated by BRE. The four sessions covered scenarios 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 mainly in open sky conditions.
- In June 2024, a tests session on C-ACC scenarios (car follow and cut-in) was performed in a motorway Tunnel near Trento. The two lanes carriageway can be considered a highway environment for the CAV.
- In July 2024, a joint test session by CRF and A22 verified the correct warning display of TJA (scenario 2.1).
- In August 2024, further tests on C-ACC car follow and cut-in scenarios were performed to finetune the system.
- In September 2024, the CPM transmission and reception software developed by CRF, which was preparatory to scenarios 3.1 and 3.2, was integrated for the first time on the CAV and CV, and tested on the prototype running in Trento motorway.

- In October 2024, the L4 ODD conditions and SAE Level transitions were verified on the motorway. In addition, a first test session of V2X-based positioning systems was performed in a dedicated parking area at BRE premises, to configure the BRE “V2X Locate” RSU and verify the communication with the CRF “V2X Locate” OBU.
- In November 2024, three test sessions were carried out at Bolzano Safety Park running all UC5 scenarios: the CAV and CV had GNSS disabled and V2X locate and dead reckoning enabled. The “V2X Locate” RSU’s were placed along the track, whereas the V2I warning message was sent by a mobile RSU on a stationary van by BRE.
- In February 2025, three additional experimental sessions were done on the V2X locate positioning system, with the goal of evaluating the best RSU configurations and collecting as many data as possible to finetune the system before going to the target tunnel.
- In March 2025, two test sessions were performed at the “Tusch” target tunnel north of Bolzano, receiving messages from BRE RSUs.
- In April 2025, a partial demo was carried out in the tunnel and recorded on video, running all scenarios. The TJA scenario was run without utilizing the LINKS RSUs, since they were not yet installed; instead, the demo was run emulating the DENM messages necessary for the TJA tests.
- In July 2025 several tests with the counting algorithm are planned, using the video stream from North RSU in preparation for the complete test site availability when the South RSU will be installed.

4.2.4.1. Functional tests

Referring to the table in Annex 1, some differences will be described herein. On the LINKS side, mostly the delay in the installation of the RSUs has been determinant in the deviations from original requirements. On the A22 side, the impossibility of installing one of the indoor positioning techniques due to regulatory issues risen during the project.

CLOUD testing

The cloud components are currently being integrated with the A22 infrastructure and are present into the LINKS Cloud. Some of the components are already tested for UC4 in Turin. Given that during 2025 UC4 tests are mainly on MEC infrastructure, LINKS Cloud components are being reused for UC5 and their basic interactions and interfaces can be considered tested. The missing tests relate to specific components for UC5, such as RMT, and the interfaces with C-ITS. These are being tested within the delivery this document.

CCR_007, CCR008 and CCR_009 have changed since UC5 does not deal with VRUs; these requirements were supposed to be removed from the list.

The part related with the Risk Level Assessment (RLA) calculation is still missing since no data has been added yet to the Digital twin, so SER_094 SER_095 and SER_096 are still to be achieved.

CCR_10 is not yet accomplished, since LINKS RSUs and their respective sensors are not yet installed. This also impacts CCR_012, which is partially accomplished since the Cloud service present in LINKS premises is able to interact with other C-ITS services. The same assumptions are valid for LINKS RSUs.

SIE_10 was probably only applicable to UC4 since SPATEM, MAPEM and VAM messages are not considered in UC5, so the target requirement has changed.

CV and CAV testing

The CV and CAV are often tested together, and both have the same data exchange with the PoDIUM infrastructure.

Specifically regarding the CAV, automated longitudinal control is operated each time the driving scenario is tested. Lateral control is operated in terms of lane centring, whereas lane change is left to the driver, based on recommendations provided by the onboard system. The UC5 test plan does not envisage specific automated manoeuvre assessment, but evaluates if the automated driving function, driving recommendation, target speed and SAE Level conditions and transitions work correctly also with support of PoDIUM infrastructure messages (such as the warnings sent by the PoDIUM risk management module).

RSU testing

The functionality of the A22 RSUs was evaluated through live monitoring, log analysis, and packet-level inspection. A central monitoring station confirmed real-time message transmission, while RSU logs and PCAP files were analysed, using Wireshark, to verify compliance with ETSI standards in both message type and content. No anomalies were detected, and the RSUs performed within expected parameters. In parallel, field tests with CRF's CAVs and CVs confirmed successful reception and decoding of C-ITS messages in real-world conditions, validating end-to-end system performance.

Regarding indoor positioning described in SIE_011 and SIE_012, deployment was blocked by legislative constraints imposed after the project launched, preventing their installation.

4.2.4.2. Non-functional tests

Preliminary non-functional tests have been done, and the results have been reported in the Checklist table (see Annex). Additional tests and consolidated results on positioning technology and roadside infrastructure performance will be reported in WP5 deliverables (D5.2).

4.2.4.3. Scenario 1 related trials

Table 23 reports, for each test case of scenario 1, the number of trials in which the functionalities work correctly, i.e. after the debug phase.

Table 23: UC5 scenario 1 related trials

ID	Description	Functionality verified	Correct trials after debug
1.1	RWW	YES	16
1.2	C-ACC	YES	13
1.3	C-ACC cut-in	YES	13

4.2.4.4. Scenario 2 related trials

As in the previous, Table 24 reports, the number of trials for Scenario 2.

Table 24: UC5 scenario 2 related trials

ID	Description	Functionality verified	Correct trials after debug
2.1	TJA	YES	16

4.2.4.5. Scenario 3 related trials

In Table 25 the trials for Scenario 3 are reported.

Table 25: UC5 scenario 3 related trials

ID	Description	Functionality verified	Correct trials after debug
3.1	ODD Keep	YES	14
3.2	ODD Exit	YES	13

5. Conclusions

This chapter summarizes the progress achieved during the PoDIUM project's integration and pre-evaluation activities across the German, Spanish, and Italian Living Labs. It highlights the significant milestones completed in each use case, outlines the current state of integration, and identifies pending tasks essential for full operational validation. These conclusions will guide the final demonstration phases, ensuring all PoDIUM platform components meet their intended performance and interoperability objectives.

1. Summary of Work Achieved

On the German LL:

- **UC1** (Ulm): Successful integration of two CAVs (VW Golf, Mercedes E-Class) and a connected VRU with MEC-based infrastructure. Cooperative as well as offloaded functionalities were validated in initial tests.

On the Spanish LL:

- **UC2** (Barcelona): The EV and CV were effectively integrated with the infrastructure. In the first scenario, the EV's real-time positioning was shared with the platform to enable dynamic traffic light prioritisation along a predefined corridor. In the third scenario, reliable VRU detection and risk management triggered V2X messages to enhance safety.
- **UC3** (C32 highway): Achieved integration and initial validation of cooperative traffic management capabilities using two CVs, emulating cross-border conditions, and confirming functionality related to VRU detection and real-time risk warnings. Additionally, the on-demand shuttle service app was validated and is available for use.

On the Italian LL:

- **UC4** (Turin urban site): Achieved the integration of vehicle prototype and infrastructure components; performed a preliminary pre-demo validation for intersection safety scenarios, including vehicle-infrastructure data fusion, CCAM messages data flow and the step-by-step storyboard for all scenarios.
- **UC5** (Autostrada del Brennero highway): Successful integration of vehicle prototypes and the main infrastructure components; performed validation of scenarios within the highway tunnels in comparison to open-sky condition, for the subsequent analysis within WP5.

2. Pending Tests and Integration Work

Several integration and testing activities remain incomplete or require refinement:

On the German LL:

- **UC1**: The UC is completed and demonstrated. The demonstration results will be presented in deliverable D5.2.

On the Spanish LL:

- **For both UCs:** Automated driving trials with the MILLA CAV pending, conditional to obtaining the necessary permits.
- **UC2:** Completing the integration and testing of cooperative manoeuvres in the EV scenario. Mobility data collection from CVs to support traffic management functions. Orchestrated trials with all the systems running simultaneously are pending to take place.
- **UC3:** Streamlining the CV driver's HMI to correctly display the strategies and alerts received. Capturing data logs and measuring the non-functional requirements. Updating the passenger app with the final shuttle route.

On the Italian LL:

- **UC4:** RSU short-range communication (PC5 interface) remains pending completion. Some technical issues at the infrastructure prevented us from doing an extensive testing phase with CAV on all three scenarios (third scenario was tested with CV only). The overall system performance in the different scenarios is being improved, prior to the demonstration phase.
- **UC5:** Roadside camera systems necessary for comprehensive risk assessment integration are not yet fully operational; a test involving the risk management module and system latency measurements remains pending.

The final project phase, until December 2025, will address these remaining integration tasks to ensure robust validation and the successful final demonstration of the PoDIUM systems in real-world scenarios in each of the LLS.

6. References

- [1] D2.2 PoDIUM Platform Requirements and Specifications
- [2] D4.1 Deployment of PoDIUM architecture to the LLS and development of data collection tools
- [3] D3.3 Final Report on PoDIUM Platform Requirements
- [4] A. Scheible, T. Griebel, and M. Buchholz, “Self-Monitored Clutter Rate Estimation for the Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter” in 2024 27th International Conference on Information Fusion (FUSION), 2024, pp. 1–7
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- [6] <https://qpud.apache.org/proton/index.html>
- [7] https://github.com/uulm-mrm/v2x_etsi_asn1/tree/develop/v2x_etsi_asn1_lib/asn1
- [8] <https://projekt-lukas.de/>
- [9] D5.1 PoDIUM evaluation methodology
- [10] D2.1 PoDIUM use cases description and specifications
- [11] D3.2 Initial Report on PoDIUM Platform Requirements

7. Annexes

The Annexes below provide further supporting information about the project activities.

7.1. Annex 1 – Complete checklist of requirements and their achievement

7.1.1. German LL (UC1)

7.1.1.1. Use Case 1

Table 26. Functional requirements for UC1

No.	Requirement description	Achievement/Comment	If CHANGED, description of the deviation from original requirement
PF_UC1-001	The CAV shall be able to send its environment model to the MEC.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC1-002	The CAV shall be able to send its position to the MEC.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC1-003	The VRU shall be able to send its position to the MEC.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC1-004	The SPU shall be able to send object detections to the MEC. This applies only to the second scenario and the baseline implementation of the first scenario.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC1-005	The MEC shall be able to fuse information from different sources to calculate/update the DT.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC1-006	The MEC shall be able to plan cooperative maneuver based on the information of the DT.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC1-007	The CAV and VRU shall be able to send its route to the MEC.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC1-008	The MEC shall be able to send the DT (as CPM) to the CAV.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC1-009	The CAV and VRU shall be able to receive cooperative maneuver.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC1-010	The MEC shall be able to send the cooperative maneuver to the CAV and VRU.	YES AS PLANNED	

PF_UC1-012	The CAV shall be able to to send the DT (as CPM) to the MEC.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC1-013	The CAVs shall be able to react on received cooperative maneuver accordingly, limited to use case needs (e.g., overtaking, stopping).	YES AS PLANNED	

Table 27. Non-Functional requirements for UC1

No.	Requirement description	Achievement/Comment	If CHANGED, description of the deviation from original requirement
PNF_UC1_CAV_001	Two connected and automated vehicles are available.	One CAV is provided by BOSCH and one from UULM.	
PNF_UC1_CAV_002	The CAVs shall be able to communicate with the MEC server or RSU via redundant paths	Confirmed with ping tests.	
PNF_UC1-NET_001	Platform should support latency of 200 ms between sensors/vehicles and edge	Yes, detailed evaluation in D5.2	
PNF_UC1-NET_002	Platform should support a bandwidth of 1 Mbps between sensors/vehicles and edge	Yes, detailed evaluation in D5.2	
PNF_UC1-NET_003	platform should support Reliability of 99% between sensors/vehicles and edge	Yes, detailed evaluation in D5.2	

7.1.2. Spanish LL (UC2 & UC3)

7.1.2.1. Use Case 2

Table 28. Requirements checklist – Spanish LL – UC2

No.	Requirement description	Achievement	If CHANGED, description of the deviation from original requirement
PF_UC2-AIC_001	AIC shall be able to detect VRUs in the video	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-AIC_002	AIC shall be able to detect if VRUs are inside of a predefined dangerous area or not.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-AIC_003	AIC shall notify the CRE the detection of VRUs	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-AIC_004	The AIC shall periodically provide the CRE with the following information about the VRU detected in its vision area: anonymized unique identifier, position, VRU type and, if possible, direction, speed and behaviour type	CHANGED	Due to technical constraints, such as the fisheye lenses used by the cameras, the detection distance and occlusions, it will not be possible to provide speeds
PF_UC2-CRE_001	The CRE shall estimate the probability of occurrence of an incident between actors that interact on the road network.	CHANGED	The current deterministic approach prioritises real-time responsiveness and simplicity over probabilistic rigour due to a lack of historical incident data with which to train the model
PF_UC2-CRE_002	If the risk of an interaction exceeds a certain value, the CRE shall notify its clients, which in turn shall finally resend them road users	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-CVM_001	The Connected Vehicle Manager (CVM) shall be able to receive the CAM and CPM messages sent from the CVs (including the EV), and inform them about events sent from the infrastructure.	CHANGED	CPM from vehicles is not implemented: the infrastructure already performs detection and shares this information with vehicles via the CVM. Thus, CPM reception from CVs is not essential to fulfil safety and awareness goals
PF_UC2-CVM_002	The CVM shall inform the CVs and CAVs about the	YES AS PLANNED	

	EVs approaching to their position and provide generic recommendations		
PF_UC2-CVM_003	The CVM shall be able to transmit V2X messages to the relevant RSUs for their dissemination to the relevant areas using C-V2X	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-CVM_004	The CVM shall be able to disseminate V2X messages based on the location of the Road Users (CVs and CAVs) using 5G technology	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-EV_001	The EV shall periodically notify the EVM of the position and speed in its route through the predefined itinerary (if possible, direction should also be included and, also if possible, position should have lane-level accuracy [$<2m$])	YES AS PLANNED	There are some points along the corridor where position accuracy can't be guaranteed. Therefore, the location mapping model used to track the vehicle must be flexible enough to avoid losing it along the corridor
PF_UC2-EVM_001	The platform shall have an Emergency Vehicle Manager (EVM) able to receive the available corridors from the infrastructure and the updated location of the Emergency Vehicle.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-EVM_002	The EVM shall notify the beginning of a trip of an EV through a predefined itinerary to the TMS	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-EVM_003	The EVM shall periodically notify the TMS of the position and speed in its route through its itinerary (if possible, direction should also be included)	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-EVM_004	The EVM shall be able to transmit V2X messages to the relevant RSUs for their dissemination to the relevant areas using C-V2X	CHANGED	In this scenario V2X messages are transmitted via 5G to ensure broader coverage, network coordination and centralized control. 5G offers sufficient

			latency guarantees for the events being managed in this scenario
PF_UC2-EVM_005	The EVM shall be able to disseminate V2X messages based on the location of the Road Users using 5G technology	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-TMS_001	The TMS shall process the information of the origins and destinations of the planned trips of connected vehicles to generate an M-OD of planned trips	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-TMS_002	Each second, the TMS shall receive the anonymized unique identifier, the georeferenced position, and the speed of each connected vehicle	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-TMS_003	The TMS shall process the position and speed of each CV along time and update the M-OD data model each time a CV begins and ends a trip	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-TMS_004	The TMS shall calculate the travel time of each vehicle moving through a link (road segment between two junctions) and record it in the link data model.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-TMS_005	Each traffic control cycle, the TMS shall calculate an average travel time of the vehicles driving along each link (road segment between two junctions) and update the result in the link data model.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-TMS_006	The TMS shall calculate the average travel time for each origin-destination pair (TT-OD) as the	YES AS PLANNED	

	average travel time for the path with minimum travel time between the origin and the destination		
PF_UC2-TMS_007	The TMS shall calculate the aggregated delay of each entry to each junction per cycle	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-TMS_008	Each time a CV enters a junction the TMS shall store a delay record in the junction model associated with the entry and containing the delay of the vehicle	CHANGED	Not visible externally, part of the service algorithm
PF_UC2-TMS_009	The TMS shall estimate the arrival time of the EV to each traffic light and take the necessary actions to give traffic light priority to the EVs in their trip across predefined itineraries	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-TMS_010	The TMS must inform VRUs and other users of the road network of the current or imminent presence of an EV by activating a Visual Warning Device	CHANGED	It was finally considered more interesting to analyse the interaction between each VRU and the general vehicles, due to the characteristics of the selected zone and the intersection
PF_UC2-VRU_001	CRE must be able to notify vehicles, via the CVM when there is high risk of collision with a VRU	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-VRU_002	The VRU-APP shall allow a VRU to subscribe to the services of a VRUM	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-VRU_003	The VRU-APP shall request the VRU to provide some relevant personal data for the classification of the VRU	CHANGED	The AI environmental perception model can detect and distinguish different types of VRUs, but not the VRU-APP. This may be due to personal data issues
PF_UC2-VRU_004	AICs must be able to detect the trajectory of previously detected VRUs.	YES AS PLANNED	

PF_UC2-VRU_005	The VRU-APP shall notify VRUM about of the beginning of a trip, the origin and the expected destination of the trip	CHANGED	The VRU-APP will not inform about the VRU trip. As the goal is to detect and respond to collision risks in real time, positioning and motion tracking of VRUs are sufficient (already covered). Trip information is not required to assess proximity, trajectory conflict, or risk level
PF_UC2-VRU_006	The VRUMs shall exchange information with the VRUs they have made a subscription to the services it shall offer.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-VRU_007	A VRUM shall periodically receive from VRU-APPS information with the identification of each VRU, its position, its direction and its speed.	CHANGED	It was decided to focus on AIC detection, capable to detect unequipped user, instead of restricting to VRUs using the VRU-APP. This enhances the inclusivity and robustness of the safety system
PF_UC2-VRU_007	The VRU APP shall notify periodically the position, direction and speed of the VRU to the VRUM	CHANGED	Same as PF_UC2-VRU_007
PF_UC2-VRU_008	The VRU-APP shall notify the VRU the detection of a high risk of collision	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2-VRU_009	The VRUM shall send to the VRUs the high-risk-of-collision alerts that affect them	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2_CAV_001	The CVs shall acquire positioning information from a GNSS device. If possible, with lane-level accuracy (<2m)	NOT YET	From September 2025
PF_UC2_CAV_002	The CVs shall send and receive V2X messages to/from the CVM using both communication technologies (5G and C-V2X)	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2_CAV_003	The CVs shall send CAM messages at a 10Hz with the corresponding station	YES AS PLANNED	It has been validated with the CV. Pending with the CAV (from September 2025)

	type, timestamp and positioning information.		
PF_UC2_CAV_004	The CVs, if capable, shall generate, encode and send CPM messages at a 10Hz with perception information from its sensors.	CHANGED	Same as PF_UC2-CVM_001
PF_UC2_CAV_005	The CVs shall be able to receive and decode CAM, CPM, DENM, IVIM and MCM messages.	CHANGED	Additionally, IVIM and MCM are not included in the current UC2 setup. Restricting message handling to CAM and DENM reduced the processing overhead in the CV stack and enabled a greater focus on reliable messages
PF_UC2_CAV_006	The CVs shall be able to check the relevance of the received messages depending on its station type, location and dynamics information.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC2_CAV_007	The CVs shall present relevant information from DENMs, IVIMs and MCMs via an HMI in form of a warning/recommendation	CHANGED	Same as PF_UC2_CAV_005
PF_UC2_CAV_008	The CVs shall switch between C-V2X and 5G technology based on their location / network availability	YES AS PLANNED	

Table 29. Non-functional requirements for UC2

No.	Requirement description	Achievement	If CHANGED, description of the deviation from original requirement
P_UC2-CAV_001	GNSS signal must not be lost for more than 50 meters or 5 seconds	YES AS PLANNED	
P_UC2_CAV_002	RTK service must be configured for every vehicle (to be)	NOT YET	From September 2025
P_UC2-CAV_003	GNSS receiver must accept RTK corrections via NTRIP	NOT YET	From September 2025

P_UC2-CAV_004	Internet Connection should not disconnect for more than 5 s	NOT YET	From September 2025
P_UC2-CAV_005	CAV should send CAM messages at a rate of 10Hz	YES AS PLANNED	
P_UC2-CAV_006	The CVs shall take less than 100ms to generate a CAM message from the corresponding GNSS sample	YES AS PLANNED	
P_UC2-CAV_007	The CVs shall be able to handle between 1 and 10 messages per second to be processed internally	YES AS PLANNED	
PNF_UC2-NET_001	Platform should offer 2 s of end-to-end transmission delay for dynamic events, 200 kbps minimum and 99.99% of reliability	NOT YET	From September 2025
PNF_UC2-NET_002	Platform should offer 2 s of end-to-end transmission delay for maneuvers coordination messages, 100 kbps minimum and 99.99% of reliability	NOT YET	From September 2025
PNF_UC2-NET_003	Platform should offer 3 s of end-to-end transmission delay for traffic management messages, 10 kbps minimum and 95% of reliability	NOT YET	From September 2025

7.1.2.2. Use Case 3

Table 30: Functional requirements for UC3

No.	Requirement description	Achievement	If CHANGED, description of the deviation from original requirement
PF_UC3-CAV_001	The use case will take place with max 2 CAVs (MILLA and IDIADA) and at least 2 additional connected conventional vehicles	Partially achieved up to now	4 vehicles are planned. Two (MILLA & IDIADA) are already equipped. The other two have their OBU stacks ready for integration and will be leased (AAE) when the time of the final demo arrives. The IDIADA is only CV (no AD functions).
PF_UC3-CAV_002	The CAVs (MILLA and IDIADA) shall have frontal sensors to perceive other vehicles and VRUs	Yes, partially.	IDIADA's CV may not have perception

PF_UC3-CAV_003	The CAVs shall be aware of road events through received DENM ITS messages	Yes	
PF_UC3-CAV_004	The MILLA shuttle CAV will be capable of autonomously driving on the highway at SAE 4, at an appropriate speed for driving on the highway in real traffic	Yes	Up to 80km/h
	[OPTIONAL] The same for IDIADA CAV	No	IDIADA's vehicle is only CV
PF_UC3-CAV_005	The MILLA CAV shuttle shall respond to the speed/maneuver recommendations sent by the infrastructure automatically	Yes	For UC3, only speed limit change, and distance from vehicle in front. Changing lane automatically on the high-speed highway is not feasible safety-wise.
	[OPTIONAL] The same for IDIADA CAV	No	IDIADA's vehicle is only CV
PF_UC3-CAV_007	The CAVs and CVs shall have 5G and C-V2X connectivity simultaneously (via an OBU and an on-board 5G modem)	Yes	
PF_UC3-CAV_008	The CAVs and CVs shall have a GNSS with lane-level accuracy (if possible)	Yes	
PF_UC3-CAV_009	The OBUs/TCUs of all CAVs and CVs shall be able to transmit and receive messages to/from the Gateway in the formats selected, including CAM, CPM, MCM, DENM, IVIM and Raw ITS messages	Yes	
PF_UC3-CAV_010	The IDIADA CAV shall have a processing unit able to interact between the TCU, the HMI and the internal vehicle systems	Yes	Partially fulfilled. Laptop/PC connected to OBU and the HMI (not to internal vehicle systems)
PF_UC3-CAV_011	The IDIADA CAV and each conventional CV will have an HMI device (e.g. tablet) to show traffic/maneuver recommendations to the drivers	Yes	
PF_UC3-CAV_012	The MILLA shuttle CAV will communicate with the "Remote Shuttle Supervision Service" (human) and shall be remotely monitored and controlled by it	Yes	
PF_UC3-CAV_013	The infrastructure should integrate a connectivity strategy to guarantee that CAVs Fleet-Manager has a perception of the vehicle under the scope	Yes, partially	The LDM publishes the geolocation of the shuttle using an MQTT broker, where the CAV Fleet manager can subscribe to receive it.

	of the infrastructure (e.g. transmit geolocation of the CAV from infrastructure to Fleet Manager)		
PF_UC3-CAV_014	In case of incident involving the CAV (Shuttle), the infrastructure will inform to the service owner about it	This is not applicable to the CAV.	This is not needed anymore. As per CAV_013, the MILLA Fleet Manager will know if the shuttle has come to an unplanned emergency stop via the geolocation information. Also, in the current UC implementation the MILLA shuttle is always connected to the internet, and therefore to the Fleet manager, via a public SIM card.
PF_UC3-CAV_015	The infrastructure (e.g. cloud) should enable a secondary communication channel via C-V2X between the MILLA Cloud fleet managers and the MILLA CAV, in case of loss of 5G communication	Yes, with changes	In the new LL (C32) having an external cloud to connect to the RSUs is not feasible as the installed RSUs do not have general internet connectivity (only to the private 5G network set up for PoDIUM UC3). In any case, the seamless 5G connection of the shuttle is ensured by a public network SIM.
PF_UC3-RSU_001	5G network shall be offered at an available private or public frequency band.	Yes	Private 5G network setup (+Orange)
	5G Network shall cover the whole demo area, both directions, all lanes and including singular spots (i.e. service area, rest zones...)	Yes	Zones without 5G coverage have been covered with C-V2X network.
PF_UC3-RSU_002	The infrastructure shall offer 4G connectivity at the service pickup/drop-off points, for the CAVs to connect to service-oriented applications	Yes	
PF_UC3-RSU_003	In the Spanish section of the highway, at least 4 RSUs with C-V2X will be installed, with sufficient connectivity coverage for both directions and all the lanes and singular spots	Yes	3 fixed RSUs are installed. 1 mobile RSU will be used flexibly.
PF_UC3-RSU_004	The highway shall feature at least 5 Full HD or 4K cameras, connected and feeding real-time video footage to the local MEC (Hub Edge)	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_001	The highway shall be equipped with at least 2 MECs in the Spanish side and at least 1 MEC	Yes	

	in the French side (i.e. side of the border)		
PF_UC3-MEC_002	The MEC shall have a Mobility Hub Edge Platform module, over which is possible to deploy specific software components, incl. Video Analytics (VA), Local TMC, and Digital Twin (DT)	Yes, with changes	Architecture change: The Hub Edge is only used to transmit the VA data in our implementation. The rest of the components (TMC, DT/LDM, etc) are installed directly on the MEC.
PF_UC3-MEC_003	The Mobility Hub Edge Platform shall receive all data coming from local infrastructure, vehicles and devices (via Gateways) and distribute them to the respective MEC software modules	Yes, with changes	Architecture change: Hub is only receiving VA data. The Gateway, as an independent MEC component, receives vehicle data.
PF_UC3-MEC_004	The Mobility Hub Edge Platform shall transmit data, including traffic management information or traffic instructions to the vehicles in its local area (via Gateways)	Yes, with changes	Architecture change: Hub is only receiving VA data. The Gateway, as an independent MEC component, transmits vehicle data.
PF_UC3-MEC_005	The MEC shall have a Video Analytics (VA) module which will run on top of the Mobility Hub Edge and shall receive real-time video feed, process it, and transmit the traffic perception info to the DT and Local TMC	Yes, with changes	Architecture change: The VA module is installed on roadside dedicated PCs, not on the MEC. The video feed is processed there and only the processed VA data are transmitted to the MEC.
PF_UC3-MEC_006	The VA shall be able to detect vehicles (moving or static), recognise their type/category, and capture their location, speed, trajectory	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_007	The MEC shall have a Digital Twin (DT) module which will run on top of the Mobility Hub Edge	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_008	The Digital Twin (DT) shall have a Local Dynamic Map (LDM) that is updated using the data (e.g. geolocation, speed) transmitted by vehicles and VRUs	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_009	The LDM shall contain static road attributes	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_010	The LDM shall provide as output the future expected trajectories of each road actor (vehicles and pedestrians) in the short term	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_011	The DT shall calculate and store a local traffic status periodically,	Yes	

	using as input the fusion of data sources (camera data, LDM data, obstacle/incident data)		
PF_UC3-MEC_012	The local traffic status shall be periodically transmitted from the MEC to the Cloud	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_013	The MEC shall have a Local Traffic Management Center (TMC) module which will run on top of the Mobility Hub Edge	Yes, with changes	Architecture change: The TMC runs as an independent MEC component, not on top of the Hub Edge
PF_UC3-MEC_014	Periodically the TMC shall calculate an average travel time of the vehicles driving along each highway section and store the result	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_015	The Local TMC will identify and register local incidents and create a notification/alert to be communicated to the relevant vehicles	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_016	The Local TMC shall calculate the local traffic management strategies, for low-latency	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_017	The traffic management strategy messages transmitted by the infrastructure to the vehicles shall be related to a) modify max speed, b) modify distance from car in-front, c) closed/open lane (to be avoided / preferred)	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_018	The V2X Gateways shall enable to transmit Facilities messages over IPv4 over cellular networks	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_019	The Gateways shall enable to transmit Facilities messages over LTE-PC5 radio technology	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_020	The Gateways shall translate messages between different radio technologies	Yes	
PF_UC3-MEC_021	Both Gateways shall have the same interfaces to communicate with the Hub Edge	Yes, with changes	Architecture change: The TMC communicates with the LDM using an API REST interface. The TMC communicates with the Gateways using an API REST interface.
PF_UC3-MEC_022	The Gateways shall feed the Hub Edge with the incoming messages from the vehicles and VRUs	Yes, with changes	Architecture change: The Gateways feed the LDM, not the Hub Edge.

PF_UC3-MEC_023	The Gateways shall allow the infrastructure (via Hub Edge) to send information to the road users (CAM, CPM, MCM, DENM, IVIM)	Yes	Additionally: MAPEM messages
PF_UC3-MEC_024	The i2CAT Gateway shall optimize the Cooperative Awareness (CA) information transmitted to road users by aggregating CA information into CPM messages	Yes	
PF_UC3-CLOUD_001	The Mobility Hub Cloud Platform shall transmit and receive data to/from the Hub Edge Platform(s)	Yes, with changes	Architecture change: this is obsolete and not needed anymore. The data are communicated between the Local TMC (Edge) and Global TMC (Cloud)
PF_UC3-CLOUD_002	The Mobility Hub Cloud Platform shall contain a data repository, a data management module and data gateway, and interconnects with the Global TMC and other components such as the Shuttle Supervision Service	No	Architecture change: this is obsolete and not needed anymore.
PF_UC3-CLOUD_003	The Global TMC will construct the macroscopic global perception of traffic for multiple sections of the highway	Yes	
PF_UC3-CLOUD_004	The Global TMC will simulate and select the best global traffic management strategies	Yes	Clarification: ...cross multiple sections of the highway, covered by more than 1 Local TMCs.
PF_UC3-CLOUD_005	The MILLA Remote Shuttle Supervision Service shall monitor the location and status of the MILLA CAV (displayed via a web HMI)	Yes	
PF_UC3-CLOUD_006	The Remote Shuttle Supervision Service shall communicate driving/manoeuvre directions to the CAV, as well as new route destination	Yes	
PF_UC3-CLOUD_007	The Remote Shuttle Supervision Service shall intercommunicate with the (Global) Mobility Hub and TMC	Yes, with changes	The Remote Shuttle Supervision Service communicates with the (ENIDE) Cloud to send and receive trip information of the on-demand transport service.
PF_UC3-VRU_001	The VRUs and the MILLA shuttle passengers shall have an Android mobile phone	Yes	

	application, connected to the internet via 4G or 5G, and feature a GPS sensor. Communication is done via TCP/IPv4 and cellular networks		
PF_UC3-VRU_002	The VRUs app shall transmit VAM messages with their position, speed and direction at a frequency high enough to detect dangerous situations	Yes	
PF_UC3-VRU_003	VRUs app shall receive CAMs, DENMs and CPMs from the infrastructure, at a frequency high enough to detect dangerous situations	Yes, with changes	VRUs are able to receive CAMs, DENMs and CPMs, but the system calculates collision risk in the MEC and only sends DENM to the VRU in case of high collision risk. This does not affect the outcome of the UC.
PF_UC3-VRU_004	The VRU app shall trigger an alarm when a vehicle (e.g. MILLA CAV) detected by PoDIUM system is too close to the VRU and represents a threat for her/his safety	Yes	
PF_UC3-VRU_005	The MILLA shuttle passenger App shall allow users (passengers) to register	Yes	
PF_UC3-VRU_006	The MILLA shuttle passenger App shall have a Fast check-in system to directly access the shuttle at the shuttle stop, without pre-reservation	Yes	
PF_UC3-VRU_007	The Passenger App shall be able to receive relevant shuttle trip information from the infrastructure (e.g. shuttle location, next time of departure, time of arrival at destination)	Yes, with changes	The shuttle location is shared to the Passenger App from the MILLA fleet manager cloud, instead of the PoDIUM platform.
PF_UC3-VRU_008	The Passenger App shall display travel related information to the user	Yes	
PF_UC3-VRU_009	The Passenger App shall have a modality to allow users to send light packets (unattended) from point to point using the MILLA shuttle (logistics)	Yes	

Table 31: Non-Functional requirements for UC3

No.	Requirement description	Achievement	If CHANGED, description of the deviation from original requirement
P_UC3-CAV_001	GNSS signal must not be lost for more than 50 meters or 5 seconds	Yes, as planned	The whole testbed is in openair, and GNSS signal is not lost any time
P_UC3_CAV_002	RTK service must be configured for every vehicle	Yes	Only relevant to the CAV vehicle (MILLA). The RTK is receiving data from the public network SIM card.
P_UC3-CAV_003	GNSS receiver must accept RTK corrections via NTRIP	N/A	Not needed anymore. The MILLA vehicle is receiving RTK corrections through the public network SIM card.
P_UC3-CAV_004	Internet Connection should not disconnect for more than 5 seconds	Yes, with changes	For CVs: During roaming transitions between the “French” and “Spanish” operators, a temporary loss of Internet connectivity occurs (5G-only cut-off time, 30-70 seconds, refer to Figure 58) because of using an experimental private 5G network operated by +Orange and UM. This connectivity gap is mitigated by the coverage provided by the RSUs (C-V2X), which ensure continuous transmission of C-ITS messages during these periods. The CAV has its own public network SIM, ensuring seamless connectivity for its AD and Telesupervision functions.

<p>P_UC3-CAV_005</p>	<p>The CVs shall take less than 100ms to generate a CAM message from the corresponding GNSS sample</p>	<p>Yes – verification to TBC</p>	<p>Expected to comply without problems. The system functioned well in lab and in the field. Verifications measurements will be taken in September 2025 (to be included in D5.2).</p>
<p>P_UC3-CAV_006</p>	<p>The CVs shall be able to handle > 10 messages per second to be processed internally (input)</p>	<p>Yes, measurements to be provided later.</p>	<p>Expected to function as per the requirement. We will provide the lab stress-test results of the V2X-OBUS stack with up to 200 messages per second in September (included in D5.2).</p>
<p>P_UC3-NET_001</p>	<p>Networking latency (CAM, CPM, etc.) of < 1 seconds, Throughput 1-5 Mbps, and Reliability > 95%</p>	<p>Yes, with one change (lower need for throughput)</p>	<p>In terms of latency, RTT was measured at max 150 ms (see Figure 58), therefore significantly < 1s. The number of vehicles in the Living Lab is not sufficient to require throughputs in the range of 1–5 Mbps (we estimate about 200-400 kbps). Additionally with the shift of the VA capabilities to the roadside PCs, there is no longer the need to transfer the live video feed from the cameras to the MEC, rather we transfer only the processed data, which are much lighter. The throughput observed during the tests was adequate, as it did not cause queuing delays or packet loss due to channel saturation. Reliability was deemed sufficient.</p>

<p>P_UC3-NET_002</p>	<p>Traffic Camera feed (via 5G): latency < 100 ms, Throughput 1 Mbps (for HD, 15fps), and Reliability > 95%</p>	<p>Yes, with changes</p>	<p>With the shift of the VA capabilities to the roadside PCs, there is no longer the need to transfer the live video feed from the cameras to the MEC, rather we transfer only the processed data. The latency, throughput and reliability are deemed sufficient, however specific measurements, where needed, will be carried out in September, due to lack of time.</p>
<p>P_UC3-NET_003</p>	<p>Low-latency Incident alert (e.g. DENM): transmission latency (from PDI to CVs) < 1 s, Throughput 10-100 kbps, Reliability > 99%</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>In terms of latency, RTT was measured at max 150 ms (see Figure 58), therefore significantly < 1s. Throughput and reliability are deemed sufficient.</p>
<p>P_UC3-NET_004</p>	<p>Tele-supervision function: Latency < 100 ms, Throughput 2-5 Mbps, and Reliability > 90%</p>	<p>NOT YET</p>	<p>In-field tests to be done upon return of the shuttle in Barcelona (after Sep 2025)</p>
<p>P_UC3-NET_005</p>	<p>MEC-CLOUD Connection latency of <1 seconds, Throughput 1-5 Mbps, and Reliability > 95%</p>	<p>Yes, with changes</p>	<p>[AAE] TMC edge and cloud integrated inside the MEC (Edge-Cloud implementation). Latency is zero and throughput is much higher. Hence, these initial requirements are irrelevant.</p>

7.1.3. Italian LL (UC4 & UC5)

7.1.3.1. Use Case 4

Table 32. Functional and non-functional requirements for UC4

No.	Requirement description	Achievement	If CHANGED, description of the deviation from original requirement
CCR_001	At least one CAV shall be available in each Use Case	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_002	Each CAV shall support cellular communication	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_003	All non-automated CVs shall have a Human Machine Interface (HMI)	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_004	All CAVs shall provide localisation with at least lane-level accuracy	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_005	All CVs shall support localisation via GNSS	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_006	At least one CAV shall be available in each Use Case	YES AS PLANNED	CCR_006 is the same as CCR_001
CCR_007	The VRUs shall be able to exchange VAM messages	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_008	The VRU app shall work on a smart device	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_009	CAVs, CVs and connected VRUs devices need to support localisation	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_010	The service layer shall provide Digital Twins (DT) functionality to describe the traffic situation on the road	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_011	The services can run either on the Edge or in the Cloud	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_012	The services shall be able to process information ETSI C-ITS messages when communicating with CV, CAVs and/or connected VRUs	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_013	The communications between the layer of services and end-users (CVs, CAVs and connected VRUs) shall be based on ETSI C-ITS messages	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_014	The supporting infrastructure entities (SIE) such as ITS stations and Edge should support ETSI C-ITS messages.	YES AS PLANNED	

CCR_015	Long-range communications shall support 5G, unless only 4G is available	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_016	Direct/Short-range communications shall support G5 or C-V2X (LTE PC5)	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_005	[UC4] At least one Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) shall be available	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_007	[UC4] CAV shall be equipped with C-V2X communication (PC5 and Uu)	NOT YET	PC5 missing, to be installed during deliverable writing.
CAV_013	[UC4 and UC5] CAV shall implement an HMI to interact with the driver	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_015	[UC4, UC5] GNSS positioning of CAV shall allow for lane-level accuracy	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_016	[UC4] The vehicle on-board ITS station shall support CAM, IVIM, DENM, SPAT, MAP	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_038	[UC4] The vehicle on-board ITS station shall support CAM	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_039	[UC4] The vehicle on-board ITS station shall support IVIM	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_040	[UC4] The vehicle onboard ITS station shall support DENM	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_041	[UC4] The vehicle onboard ITS station shall support SPAT messages	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_042	[UC4] The vehicle on-board ITS station shall support MAP messages	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_046	[UC4] The vehicle on-board ITS station shall support CPM transmission functionality	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_003	[UC4 and UC5] Access Level: For short range communications ITS-G5 (ETSI EN 302 663) or C-V2X (3GPP Rel-14, Rel-15) systems shall be used	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_004	[UC4 and UC5] Transport Level: Data packets shall be transported via TCP (RFC 9293), IPv4 (RFC 791), IPv6 (RFC8200), and/or UDP (RFC768) protocols according to ITS application requirements	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_005	[UC4 and UC5] Facilities Level: ITS applications aiming at alerting users regarding a specific event	YES AS PLANNED	

	detected on the road shall use Decentralized Environmental Notification Basic Service		
COM_006	[UC4 and UC5] Facilities Level: ITS applications aiming at creating awareness between vehicles and road users as well as supporting cooperative performance in the road network shall use Cooperative Awareness Basic Service	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_007	[UC2 and UC4] Facilities Level: ITS applications aiming at conveying geographic road information and/or processing signal phase and timing should refer to MAP and SPAT services	YES AS PLANNED (SPAT) YES (MAP)	SPAT ok, but MAP not by Municipality but done by SWM and sent by LINKS
COM_009	[UC4 and UC5] Facilities Level: Position and time data to support ITS Applications shall be compliant with Position and Time (PoTi) services	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_027	[UC4 and UC5] Facilities Level: generation, transmission, and reception of information about mandatory and advisory road signage should be implemented through IVI service.	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_028	[UC4 and UC5] Facilities Level: generation, transmission, and reception of information about mandatory and advisory road signage should be implemented through IVI service.	YES AS PLANNED	Same as COM_027
COM_029	[UC4] Access Level: For long-range communications 5G (3GPP Rel-15) cellular networks shall be used	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_031	[UC4] Facilities Level: ITS applications using CAM and DENM services should support the MQTT (ISO/IEC PRF 20922) publish-subscribe protocols	CHANGED	AMQP is used instead of MQTT
SER_051	[UC4, UC5] The Digital Twin should collect data in real-time and make them available to applications using Open APIs	YES AS PLANNED	
SER_052	[UC4] Data coming from different sources can be fused to increase a "trust-index" of the information	YES AS PLANNED	

SER_074	[UC4] The infrastructure shall provide an AMQP broker to distribute ETSI messages (CAM + DENM + IVIM)	YES AS PLANNED	
SER_075	[UC4] The IMA shall be able to receive VRU-related messages via AMQP broker and MQTT	CHANGED	AMQP is used instead of MQTT
SER_077	[UC4] The IMA shall dispatch messages by the following protocol AMQP (OASIS Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) Version 1.0) (Basic Interface)	YES AS PLANNED	
SER_078	[UC4] The IMA shall be able to send TLA (traffic light assistance) data to the CAV	CHANGED SWM to check	TLA term is no longer used The new nomenclature is VIMA data for precedence management
SIE_010	[UC4, UC5] Edge and cloud should support CAM, IVIM, DENM, SPATEM, MAPEM, VAM	YES AS PLANNED	
SIE_032	[UC4] The Traffic Management System should manage SPATEM and MAPEM for traffic light intersections	YES AS PLANNED	
SYA_001	[UC4] On-board Units (OBUs) and Road-Side Units (RSUs) must act as Trusted Computing Bases (TBC) and be able to check software integrity	YES AS PLANNED	
SYA_002	[UC4] OBU and RSUs leverage software integrity verification at boot and run time and trigger the proper countermeasures in the event of violations	YES AS PLANNED	
SYA_003	[UC4] A special node (RSU or MEC or Cloud Server) shall be able to challenge OBUs and RSUs for verifying their trust status	CHANGED	Only MEC and Cloud are able to challenge.
SYA_004	[UC4] OBUs and RSUs shall have their own digital identity in accordance with X.509-base PKI	YES AS PLANNED	
SYA_005	[UC4] Communications between from/to OBUs and RSUs shall be secured to preserve the data integrity and confidentiality	NOT YET	This feature is being integrated in parallel nodes
SYA_006	[UC4] When and where possible software integrity verification shall be implemented in a privacy-	NOT YET	This feature is being integrated in parallel nodes

	preserving manner to avoid identification and linking		
PF_UC4-CAV_001	CAV shall have frontal sensors to perceive VRU and other vehicles	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CAV_002	CAV shall be able to receive V2X DENM messages about road events	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CAV_003	CAV shall use GNSS and RTK corrections to localize	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CAV_004	CAV shall match on the local intersection map, received from the MAPEM	CHANGED	CAV uses a local MAP or the MAPEM
PF_UC4-CAV_005	CAV shall implement an AMQP client to exchange messages with MEC	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CAV_006	CAV shall include an OBU for C-V2X direct communication (PC5) to exchange messages with RSU	NOT YET	It will be installed shortly
PF_UC4-CAV_007	CAV shall send/receive message with geo-networking header, security header and message payload over AMQP	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CAV_008	CAV shall encode and send perceived objects via CPM	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CAV_009	CAV shall receive IVI, SPAT, MAP, DENM messages	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CAV_010	CAV shall have 5G network connectivity to a MEC	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CAV_011	CAV shall use time-to-pass information from IVI messages to evaluate next manoeuvres	CHANGED	The time information is the time of pedestrian lane occupancy
PF_UC4-CAV_012	CAV shall evaluate AD level based on perceived objects and road events	CHANGED	Not in focus for UC4. Must be removed
PF_UC4-CAV_013	CAV shall give advice to the driver on when to pass the intersection	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CAV_014	CAV shall inform the driver about the allowed level of automation (current and future)	CHANGED	Not in focus for UC4. Must be removed
PF_UC4-NET_001	RSU shall be connected physically with a camera sensor and LIDAR via ethernet. RSU is also connected to the MEC server via 5G.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CE_001	The Camera/LIDAR sensors shall point to the crossing point with pedestrian crossings.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CE_002	The RSU perceives and tracks pedestrians and other road users and transmits perceptions to the	YES AS PLANNED	

	Digital Twin service running on the MEC server.		
PF_UC4-CAV_015	CAVs shall communicate their sensor information (CPM, CAM messages) to the MEC server using hybrid CV2X (via RSU) and 5G.	YES AS PLANNED NOT YET	NOT YET via RSU
PF_UC4-CE_003	VRUs can communicate to the MEC server their position and planned path through a smartphone.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CE_004	The Digital twin keeps updated the status of the cross point intersection with the sensor and road user's dynamic information via CCAM messages.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-CE_005	The truthfulness module subscribes to the Digital Twin and calculates truth indexes on the information in the digital twin.	CHANGED	The truthfulness module is implemented as a DT module
PF_UC4-CE_006	The VIMA service shall subscribe to the Digital Twin to produce IVIM indications for CAV.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-SEC_002	MEC server and RSU act as attestation entities of the attestation protocol.	CHANGED	RSUs are only TCB but not attestation entity or verifier
PF_UC4-SEC_003	Attestation Entities allow the attestation of the trustworthiness of the OBUs and RSUs present in the system.	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC4-SEC_004	Attestation entities might block a RSU or OBU from transmitting data to the PDI.	NOT YET	
PF_UC4-SEC_005	Attestation entities communicate periodically with OBUs and RSUs for trustworthiness.	YES AS PLANNED	
PNF_UC4-CAV_001	The CAV shall generate/receive reliable CCAM messages (false positive/negative <1%, <10% tolerated for Living Lab proof-of-concept)	NOT YET	
PNF_UC4-CAV_002	Positioning accuracy shall be <1.5 m, and < 0.2m with RTK correction	YES	Achieved with RTK + DR
PNF_UC4-CAV_003	The latency introduced by information processing (from message reception to actuation/warning should not exceed 100ms.	YES AS PLANNED	

PNF_UC4-NET_001	Platform should offer 40 ms of OW delay, 20-30 kbps minimum for dynamic data and 99.99% of reliability	YES AS PLANNED	
PNF_UC4-NET_002	Platform should offer 40 ms of OW delay, 4 Mbps minimum and 99.9% of reliability to support UC4.	YES AS PLANNED	
UC4_D5.1_1	CAV, POoDIUM platform service and infrastructure equipped and operational	YES AS PLANNED	A LINKS MEC for tests and not yet the TIM MEC
UC4_D5.1_2	Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials	YES AS PLANNED	With a work around for SWM to access MEC infrastructure
UC4_D5.1_3	CAV operational in UC4 scenarios	YES AS PLANNED	

7.1.3.2. Use Case 5

Table 33: Functional and non-functional requirements for UC5

No.	Requirement description	Achievement	If CHANGED, description of the deviation from original requirement
CCR_001	At least one CAV shall be available in each Use Case	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_002	Each CAV shall support cellular communication	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_003	All non-automated CVs shall have a Human Machine Interface (HMI)	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_004	All CAVs shall provide localisation with at least lane-level accuracy	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_005	All CVs shall support localisation via GNSS	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_006	At least one CAV shall be available in each Use Case	YES AS PLANNED	NOTE: CCR_006 is the same as CCR_001
CCR_007	The VRUs shall be able to exchange VAM messages	CHANGED	No VRU in UC5 (as was originally planned). Delete requirement. Requirement to be deleted.

CCR_008	The VRU app shall work on a smart device	CHANGED	No VRU in UC5 (as was originally planned). Requirement to be deleted.
CCR_009	CAVs, CVs and connected VRUs devices need to support localisation	YES AS PLANNED	VRU part of requirement is applicable only to UC4, not to UC5
CCR_010	The service layer shall provide Digital Twins (DT) functionality to describe the traffic situation on the road	NOT YET	Since RSUs are not yet installed.
CCR_011	The services can run either on the Edge or in the Cloud	YES AS PLANNED	UC5 has been implemented only in cloud
CCR_012	The services shall be able to process information ETSI C-ITS messages when communicating with CV, CAVs and/or connected VRUs	NOT YET	Links RSU's to be installed
CCR_013	The communications between the layer of services and end-users (CVs, CAVs and connected VRUs) shall be based on ETSI C-ITS messages	YES AS PLANNED	Even if Links RSU's are still to be installed, their interactions use C-ITS.
CCR_014	The supporting infrastructure entities (SIE) such as ITS stations and Edge should support ETSI C-ITS messages.	YES AS PLANNED	
CCR_015	Long-range communications shall support 5G, unless only 4G is available	YES AS PLANNED	only 4G is available
CCR_016	Direct/Short-range communications shall support G5 or C-V2X (LTE PC5)	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_004	[UC5] At least one Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) and one connected vehicle shall be available	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_006	[UC5] Both the connected vehicle and CAV shall be equipped with C-V2X communication (PC5 and Uu)	YES AS PLANNED	

CAV_008	[UC5] CAV shall be used as the main demonstrator (alias: Host Vehicle)	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_009	[UC5] The connected vehicle shall be used in some motorway scenarios, as the other vehicle communicating with CAV	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_010	[UC5] CAV shall be capable of SAE level 3	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_011	[UC5] CAV shall be capable of using V2X for actuation	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_012	[UC5] CAV shall be capable of using V2X for advanced ODD estimation and SAE level reduction	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_013	[UC4 and UC5] CAV shall implement an HMI to interact with the driver	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_014	[UC5] The onboard system of both CAV and Connected Vehicle shall be capable of supporting GNSS in a tunnel	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_015	[UC4, UC5] GNSS positioning of CAV shall allow for lane-level accuracy	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_017	[UC5] The vehicle on-board ITS station shall support CAM, IVIM, DENM	YES AS PLANNED	
CAV_043	[UC5] The vehicle on-board ITS station shall support CAM	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_003	[UC4 and UC5] Access Level: For short range communications ITS-G5 (ETSI EN 302 663) or C-V2X (3GPP Rel-14, Rel-15) systems shall be used	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_004	[UC4 and UC5] Transport Level: Data packets shall be transported via TCP (RFC 9293), IPv4 (RFC 791), IPv6 (RFC8200), and/or UDP (RFC768) protocols according to ITS application requirements	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_005	[UC4 and UC5] Facilities Level: ITS applications aiming at alerting users regarding a specific event detected on the	YES AS PLANNED	

	road shall use Decentralized Environmental Notification Basic Service		
COM_006	[UC4 and UC5] Facilities Level: ITS applications aiming at creating awareness between vehicles and road users as well as supporting cooperative performance in the road network shall use Cooperative Awareness Basic Service	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_009	[UC4 and UC5] Facilities Level: Position and time data to support ITS Applications shall be compliant with Position and Time (PoTi) services	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_027	[UC4 and UC5] Facilities Level: generation, transmission, and reception of information about mandatory and advisory road signage should be implemented through IVI service.	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_028	[UC4 and UC5] Facilities Level: generation, transmission, and reception of information about mandatory and advisory road signage should be implemented through IVI service.	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_030	[UC5] Access Level: For long-range communications 4G (3GPP Rel-7 and following releases) cellular network shall be used	YES AS PLANNED	
COM_032	[UC5] Facilities Level: ITS applications using CAM and DENM services should support the AMQP (OASIS Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) Version 1.0) publish-subscribe protocols	YES AS PLANNED	
SER_022	[UC5] The infrastructure shall provide an AMQP broker to distribute ETSI messages (CAM + DENM + IVIM)	YES AS PLANNED	
SER_023	[UC5] The infrastructure shall send ETSI messages (CAM + DENM + IVIM) to RSUs	YES AS PLANNED	

SER_051	[UC4, UC5] The Digital Twin should collect data in real-time and make them available to applications using Open APIs	YES AS PLANNED	DT used in UC4 used also in UC5 is able to expose Open APIs
SER_094	[UC5] Tunnel Risk Level Assessment shall be published to make it available to all actors	NOT YET	
SER_095	[UC5] Tunnel Risk Level Assessment service shall access the tunnel's Digital Twin to calculate the current risk level regularly.	NOT YET	
SER_096	[UC5] RLA (Risk Level Assessment) is monitored by a Risk Manager Service (RMS) and it publishes notifications generated on any risk level change.	NOT YET	
SIE_003	[UC5] The ITS stations shall support CAM, IVIM, DENM	YES AS PLANNED	
SIE_010	[UC4, UC5] Edge and cloud should support CAM, IVIM, DENM, SPATEM, MAPEM, VAM	CHANGED	SPATEM, MAPEM, VAM not used in highway UC5. Requirement should be separated between UC4 and UC5.
SIE_011	[UC5] The system for indoor GNSS signal provision shall cover the entire length of the tunnel	NO	
SIE_012	[UC5] A system for indoor GNSS signal provision shall be installed on a tunnel	NO	Deployment was blocked by legislative constraints imposed post-project launch, preventing installation
SIE_013	[UC5] RSU sensors shall be able to count and classify vehicles in and out of the tunnel in real-time	YES AS PLANNED	At the time of this deliverable, the classification was done in the lab with recorded videos.

SIE_014	[UC5] RSU sensors classification must consider at least the type of vehicle passing by	YES AS PLANNED	
SIE_015	[UC5] Infrastructure shall host a Digital Twin to maintain tunnel information	NOT YET	Tunnel information not integrated to LINKS cloud yet
SIE_016	[UC5] Tunnel Risk Level Assessment service shall access the tunnel's Digital Twin to calculate the current risk level regularly.	NOT YET	Tunnel information not integrated to LINKS cloud yet
SIE_022	[UC5] The ITS stations shall support CAM messages v1.4.1	YES AS PLANNED	
SIE_023	[UC5] The ITS stations shall support DEN messages v2.1.1	YES AS PLANNED	
SIE_024	[UC5] The ITS stations shall support IVIM messages v2.1.1	YES AS PLANNED	
SIE_025	[UC5] RLA (Risk Level Assessment) shall be monitored by a Risk Manager Service (RMS) and publish notifications generated on any risk level change.	NOT YET	Not yet installed
PF_UC5-CAV_001	CAV shall have frontal sensors to perceive other vehicles	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_002	CAV shall be aware of road events through V2X DENM	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_003	CAV shall be aware of road signs (speed limit and other signage) through V2X IVI	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_004	CAV shall use V2V, V2I and sensor data in combination, for understanding the scene and AD ODD	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_005	CAV shall use GNSS signal and RTK corrections to localize outside the tunnel	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_006	CAV shall use the indoor positioning solutions to localize inside the tunnel	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_007	CAV shall use the indoor positioning solutions as time reference for the V2X short range communication	YES AS PLANNED	

PF_UC5-CAV_008	CAV shall implement an AMQP client to receive message from cloud	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_009	CAV shall include an OBU for C-V2X direct communication (PC5) to exchange messages with RSU	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_010	CAV shall receive messages with geo-networking header, security header and message payload over AMQP	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_011	CAV shall receive IVI and DENM messages	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_012	CAV shall have at 4G network connectivity to cloud service	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_013	CAV shall use V2V and V2I information to evaluate next manoeuvres	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_014	CAV shall evaluate AD level based on perceived objects and road events	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_015	CAV shall utilize sensor and V2X information for cruise control	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_016	CAV shall be capable of L3 Highway Chauffeur (although not de facto actuated on public roads, it shall be “available” for engagement)	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_017	CAV shall utilize sensor and V2X information for lane change recommendations	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_018	CAV shall inform the driver about hazard warning	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5-CAV_019	CAV shall inform the driver about the allowed level of automation (current and future)	YES AS PLANNED	
PF_UC5_CE_001	RSUs with camera sensor perceive vehicles coming in and out the tunnel and characterize their type.	PENDING	A single RSU has been deployed, with functionality undergoing verification and testing
PF_UC5_NET_001	RSUs send the perceived vehicle perceptions and vehicle counts and send them to the cloud digital twin using 4G.	PENDING	A single RSU has been deployed, with functionality undergoing

			verification and testing
PF_UC5_CE_002	The cloud RMT calculates the risk level status from Digital Twin	NOT YET	Not yet installed
PF_UC5_CE_003	The cloud Risk Level Assessment Publisher publishes notifications to vehicles via AMQP	NOT YET	Not yet installed
PF_UC5_NET_002	Tunnel infrastructure will recreate GNSS signals inside the tunnel to support CAV localization	NO	Deployment was blocked by legislative constraints imposed post-project launch, preventing installation
PF_UC5_NET_003	CAV will use also ITS-G5 received signals from RSUs (trilateration) to localize inside the tunnel	YES AS PLANNED	
PNF_UC5-CAV_001	ODD exit indication should be given according to the SAE Level of automation.	YES AS PLANNED	
PNF_UC5_CAV_002	Imminent hazard condition detection should be performed with a maximum reaction time < 100 ms at CAV (message reception to actuation)	YES	The maximum reaction time is 25ms, significantly below the target threshold of 100ms. Average reaction time is approximately 8ms.
PNF_UC5-CAV_003	Positioning accuracy inside the tunnel shall meet at least 1.5 m	YES AS PLANNED	From the initial results, with dead reckoning we achieve accuracies of less than or up to 1.5 meters laterally.
PNF_UC5-CAV_004	The CAV shall be capable of having a continuous position and timing reference when entering/exiting a tunnel, with tolerated outage of 100 ms (maximum value).	PARTIALLY (position: when entering/exiting; time: when entering)	Position reference is continuous because the GPS receiver we use employs IMU and odometry to always provide a

			position, even in the absence of satellites. However, time reference for V2X is lost after a certain distance, and “V2X Locate” does not provide a time reference. We were relying on the synthetic GNSS which has not been installed.
P_UC5-NET_001	Platform should offer 40 ms of OW delay, 4 Mbps minimum and 99.9% of reliability to support UC4, in accordance to UC category cooperative Driving with sensor sharing of processed data.	PENDING	this requirement seems to belong to UC4 and not UC5.
P_UC5-NET_002	Platform should guarantee an OW delay in the order 1 s, 10 kbps and 95% of reliability, in accordance to UC Category Traffic management	YES AS PLANNED	
P_UC5-NET_003	The system for indoor GNSS signal provision shall cover the entire length of the tunnel with an appropriate signal equivalent to the signal level outside.	CHANGED	No longer applicable
UC5_D5.1_1	CAV, CV and vehicle counting roadside sensors operational in UC5 scenarios	YES AS PLANNED For CAV and CV. NOT YET for roadside sensors	
UC5_D5.1_2	Infrastructure C-ITS warning messages available	YES AS PLANNED	
UC5_D5.1_3	Use case partners have all the necessary permits for the execution of trials	YES AS PLANNED	